

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2023 Annual Report

Appendices

Focal Project Results (A), Non-focal Project Results (B), Vegetation Data (C)

Burntwood-Langenkamp, July 2023, Image Captured from Drone Flight.

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**THE OHIO STATE
UNIVERSITY**
COLLEGE OF FOOD, AGRICULTURAL,
AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

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Appendix A

Focal Projects

Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Sampling Locations

Table A1.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project.

Location Code	Location Description
BROP_01	Murphys Run Inflow
BROP_02	Main Pool
BROP_03	Wetland Stream Outflow
BROP_04	Buckeye Lake
BROP_05	West Pool
BROP_06	Mid-wetland Stream

Sampling Locations

- 01. Murphys Run Inflow
- 02. Main Pool
- 03. Wetland Stream Outflow
- 04. Buckeye Lake
- 05. West Pool
- 06. Mid-wetland Stream

Figure A1.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A1.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Murphys Run Inflow	53 \pm 15	38	0–85
02. Main Pool	48 \pm 19	48	0–90
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	41 \pm 22	48	0–70
04. Buckeye Lake	56 \pm 28	36	0–100
05. West Pool	23 \pm 11	51	0–60
06. Mid-wetland Stream	40 \pm 16	26	10–79

Figure A1.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A1.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	31 \pm 24	43	0–90
Spring	50 \pm 20	61	8–100
Summer	43 \pm 21	94	0–90
Fall	44 \pm 20	49	0–88

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A1.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Murphys Run Inflow	0.014 \pm 0	55 (28)	0–0.23	0.076 \pm 0.1	56 (4)	0–0.76
02. Main Pool	0.016 \pm 0	57 (32)	0–0.32	0.089 \pm 0.1	56 (2)	0–0.73
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	0.011 \pm 0	58 (36)	0–0.23	0.112 \pm 0.1	57 (3)	0–0.84
04. Buckeye Lake	0.006 \pm 0	55 (38)	0–0.09	0.118 \pm 0.1	56 (3)	0–0.35
05. West Pool	0.007 \pm 0	62 (49)	0–0.24	0.09 \pm 0.1	60 (2)	0–0.9
06. Mid-wetland Stream	0.019 \pm 0	21 (14)	0–0.22	0.092 \pm 0.1	22 (3)	0–0.42

Table A1.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.01 \pm 0	48 (27)	0–0.1	0.053 \pm 0.1	48 (7)	0–0.27
Spring	0.009 \pm 0	78 (43)	0–0.06	0.09 \pm 0.1	78 (7)	0–0.76
Summer	0.008 \pm 0	102 (75)	0–0.24	0.13 \pm 0.1	102 (0)	0.01–0.9
Fall	0.019 \pm 0.1	80 (52)	0–0.32	0.087 \pm 0.1	79 (3)	0–0.44

Figure A1.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A1.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Murphys Run Inflow	1.618 \pm 1.9	56 (6)	0–10.95	0.044 \pm 0.1	45 (2)	0–0.61	2.671 \pm 2.3	56 (0)	0.28–14.03
02. Main Pool	1.518 \pm 2	58 (6)	0–10.58	0.046 \pm 0.1	44 (2)	0–0.64	2.523 \pm 2.3	56 (0)	0.23–15.13
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	1.193 \pm 1.8	61 (10)	0–11.66	0.05 \pm 0.1	45 (5)	0–0.65	2.613 \pm 2	57 (0)	0.45–13.63
04. Buckeye Lake	0.84 \pm 1	56 (16)	0–4.35	0.065 \pm 0.1	45 (9)	0–0.6	2.489 \pm 1	56 (0)	0.89–6.89
05. West Pool	0.047 \pm 0.3	64 (56)	0–2.76	0.005 \pm 0	45 (9)	0–0.02	1.125 \pm 0.7	60 (0)	0.27–4.05
06. Mid-wetland Stream	0.831 \pm 0.7	22 (5)	0–2.22	0.029 \pm 0	11 (0)	0.01–0.06	1.613 \pm 0.8	22 (0)	0.35–3.35

Table A1.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	1.544 \pm 0.9	48 (9)	0–3.35	0.02 \pm 0	48 (1)	0–0.09	2.017 \pm 0.9	48 (0)	0.35–3.72
Spring	1.659 \pm 2.4	78 (13)	0–11.66	0.079 \pm 0.2	72 (5)	0–0.65	2.729 \pm 2.8	78 (0)	0.46–15.13
Summer	0.602 \pm 1.3	102 (51)	0–7.72	0.019 \pm 0	54 (12)	0–0.09	2.309 \pm 1.7	102 (0)	0.26–8.66
Fall	0.617 \pm 0.9	89 (26)	0–3.05	0.033 \pm 0	61 (9)	0–0.16	1.734 \pm 0.9	79 (0)	0.23–3.63

Soil Characteristics

Table A1.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Main Pool	7.506 \pm 0.1	6	7.33–7.64	274 \pm 110.7	6	188.2–440
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	7.094 \pm 0.3	6	6.56–7.4	125.8 \pm 61.5	6	55.3–226
05. West Pool	6.91 \pm 0.5	6	6.44–7.74	128.867 \pm 72.9	6	56–264

Table A1.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	7.17 \pm 0.4	18	6.44–7.74	176.222 \pm 106.5	18	55.3–440

Table A1.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Main Pool	21.665 \pm 11.7	8	8.76–47.84	787.687 \pm 450.3	8	341.04–1495.41	463.096 \pm 124.2	8	241.28–616.63	75.109 \pm 28.9	8	37.82–116.93
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	14.962 \pm 8.1	7	5.82–31.55	479.238 \pm 232.5	7	164.09–739.03	530.638 \pm 180	7	351.14–781.09	72.493 \pm 30	7	46.2–121.16
05. West Pool	14.501 \pm 5.3	8	5.28–21.35	627.293 \pm 283.3	8	222.9–1005.06	798.804 \pm 83.5	8	687.66–930.12	111.939 \pm 17.4	8	96.01–144.66

Table A1.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	17.133 \pm 9	23	5.28–47.84	638.022 \pm 347.9	23	164.09–1495.41	600.42 \pm 196.7	23	241.28–930.12	87.123 \pm 30.9	23	37.82–144.66

Figure A1.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A1.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Main Pool	0.274 \pm 0.4	8	0–0.96	0.725 \pm 1.8	8	0–5.09	0.103 \pm 0.3	8	0–0.77	1004.297 \pm 808.5	8	174.72–2574.9	549.109 \pm 248.6	8	335–1087.09
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	0.567 \pm 0.3	7	0.01–0.95	6.902 \pm 4.9	7	1.6–15.42	1.14 \pm 2.6	7	0–7.06	839.503 \pm 382.6	7	431.59–1448.1	443.15 \pm 185.1	7	142.03–705.79
05. West Pool	0.206 \pm 0.3	8	0–0.74	5.148 \pm 5.6	8	0.34–15.21	2.665 \pm 5.4	8	0–15.4	1270.226 \pm 662.8	8	598.17–2223.63	508.058 \pm 280.8	8	244.06–959.91

Table A1.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.339 \pm 0.3	23	0–0.96	4.144 \pm 5	23	0–15.42	1.31 \pm 3.5	23	0–15.4	1046.64 \pm 648.2	23	174.72–2574.9	502.582 \pm 236.7	23	142.03–1087.09

Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)
Sampling Locations

Table A2.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project.

Location Code	Location Description
BWLK_01	Burntwood Creek
BWLK_02	Settling Pool
BWLK_03	Overland Drainage
BWLK_04	1st Flat
BWLK_05	Outflow
BWLK_06	Overland Pool A

- Sampling Locations**
01. Burntwood Creek
02. Settling Pool
03. Overland Drainage
04. 1st Flat
05. Outflow
06. Overland Pool A

Figure A2.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A2.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Burntwood Creek	42 \pm 25	80	0–125
02. Settling Pool	21 \pm 13	85	0–60
03. Overland Drainage	7 \pm 12	52	0–40
04. 1st Flat	24 \pm 20	57	0–110
05. Outflow	18 \pm 19	71	0–100
06. Overland Pool A	12 \pm 10	44	0–37

Figure A2.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A2.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	20 \pm 13	66	0–50
Spring	36 \pm 30	87	0–125
Summer	26 \pm 19	109	0–110
Fall	11 \pm 10	127	0–40

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A2.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Burntwood Creek	0.134 \pm 0.2	87 (5)	0–1.01	0.263 \pm 0.3	88 (0)	0.02–1.43
02. Settling Pool	0.045 \pm 0.1	73 (33)	0–0.46	0.27 \pm 0.3	79 (0)	0.01–1.29
03. Overland Drainage	0.029 \pm 0.1	14 (5)	0–0.28	0.271 \pm 0.2	14 (0)	0.09–0.94
04. 1st Flat	0.01 \pm 0	30 (20)	0–0.22	0.149 \pm 0.1	40 (0)	0.02–0.67
05. Outflow	0.029 \pm 0.1	54 (25)	0–0.28	0.26 \pm 0.2	58 (0)	0.04–1.13
06. Overland Pool A	0.026 \pm 0.1	22 (11)	0–0.29	0.211 \pm 0.2	26 (0)	0.03–0.98

Table A2.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.108 \pm 0.1	51 (17)	0–0.5	0.36 \pm 0.3	56 (0)	0.04–1.29
Spring	0.04 \pm 0.1	89 (32)	0–0.33	0.242 \pm 0.2	89 (0)	0.02–0.94
Summer	0.033 \pm 0.1	86 (42)	0–0.33	0.165 \pm 0.1	86 (0)	0.01–0.79
Fall	0.109 \pm 0.2	54 (8)	0–1.01	0.256 \pm 0.3	74 (0)	0.04–1.43

Figure A2.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A2.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Burntwood Creek	6.43 \pm 8.2	88 (22)	0–35.34	0.09 \pm 0.1	60 (0)	0–0.61	8.53 \pm 9.4	88 (0)	0.62–65.75
02. Settling Pool	1.971 \pm 3.7	79 (34)	0–15.75	0.051 \pm 0.1	53 (0)	0–0.43	4.655 \pm 4.8	79 (0)	0.65–24.57
03. Overland Drainage	1.102 \pm 2.4	14 (7)	0–6.85	0.029 \pm 0	9 (0)	0–0.08	3.605 \pm 2.7	14 (0)	0.85–9.78
04. 1st Flat	1.507 \pm 2.9	40 (14)	0–12.77	0.023 \pm 0	14 (0)	0–0.06	3.879 \pm 4.1	40 (0)	1.1–22.9
05. Outflow	1.62 \pm 2.7	56 (19)	0–12.16	0.097 \pm 0.1	31 (0)	0–0.54	4.33 \pm 3.6	58 (0)	0.46–19.8
06. Overland Pool A	0.561 \pm 1.6	26 (9)	0–6.12	0.039 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.16	2.506 \pm 1.7	26 (0)	0.73–7.77

Table A2.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	4.329 \pm 6.6	52 (16)	0–28.87	0.076 \pm 0.1	51 (0)	0–0.34	6.157 \pm 6.6	55 (0)	0.46–25.8
Spring	5.569 \pm 6.4	89 (17)	0–35.34	0.06 \pm 0.1	73 (0)	0–0.54	8.112 \pm 8.2	89 (0)	0.85–65.75
Summer	2.082 \pm 4.8	86 (44)	0–24.09	0.098 \pm 0.2	30 (0)	0–0.61	4.701 \pm 5.5	86 (0)	0.93–24.42
Fall	0.037 \pm 0.1	76 (28)	0–0.96	0.037 \pm 0.1	24 (0)	0–0.34	2.34 \pm 0.9	75 (0)	0.62–5.14

Soil Characteristics

Table A2.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Settling Pool	7.681 \pm 0.2	3	7.46–7.84	84.233 \pm 30.5	3	53.4–114.3
04. 1st Flat	7.531 \pm NA	1	7.53–7.53	90.6 \pm NA	1	90.6–90.6
05. Outflow	7.604 \pm NA	1	7.6–7.6	106.3 \pm NA	1	106.3–106.3
06. Overland Pool A	7.577 \pm NA	1	7.58–7.58	59 \pm NA	1	59–59

Table A2.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	7.636 \pm 0.1	2	7.53–7.74	102.45 \pm 16.8	2	90.6–114.3
Fall	7.62 \pm 0.2	4	7.46–7.84	75.925 \pm 24.5	4	53.4–106.3

Table A2.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Settling Pool	39.648 \pm 62.7	5	1.02–146.85	149.294 \pm 181.3	5	24.81–457.65	504.255 \pm 174.6	5	273.62–703.71	44.533 \pm 32.8	5	0–80.77
04. 1st Flat	1.878 \pm NA	1	1.88–1.88	30.069 \pm NA	1	30.07–30.07	197.161 \pm NA	1	197.16–197.16	22.424 \pm NA	1	22.42–22.42
05. Outflow	58.408 \pm 72.9	2	6.86–109.96	164.588 \pm 66.7	2	117.46–211.72	524.787 \pm 312.5	2	303.8–745.78	42.636 \pm 60.3	2	0–85.27
06. Overland Pool A	49.339 \pm 60.8	2	6.37–92.31	131.685 \pm 67.9	2	83.66–179.71	484.086 \pm 41.1	2	455–513.17	25.252 \pm 35.7	2	0–50.5

Table A2.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	2.341 \pm 0.7	2	1.88–2.8	37.64 \pm 10.7	2	30.07–45.21	289.738 \pm 130.9	2	197.16–382.32	33.009 \pm 15	2	22.42–43.59
Fall	51.366 \pm 57.5	8	1.02–146.85	161.725 \pm 136	8	24.81–457.65	519.588 \pm 171.6	8	273.62–745.78	39.356 \pm 37.3	8	0–85.27

Figure A2.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A2.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Settling Pool	0.883 \pm 1.8	5	0–4.08	8.605 \pm 8.2	5	1.82–22.14	0.356 \pm 0.5	5	0–1.14	724.303 \pm 648.8	5	287.97–1769.03	394.417 \pm 334.9	5	118–908.52
04. 1st Flat	1.676 \pm NA	1	1.68–1.68	2.938 \pm NA	1	2.94–2.94	0.062 \pm NA	1	0.06–0.06	506.816 \pm NA	1	506.82–506.82	274.804 \pm NA	1	274.8–274.8
05. Outflow	0.88 \pm 0.4	2	0.63–1.13	11.591 \pm 2	2	10.19–13	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	1105.867 \pm 377.9	2	838.65–1373.09	579.926 \pm 384.4	2	308.1–851.75
06. Overland Pool A	1.111 \pm 0.8	2	0.55–1.68	11.835 \pm 15.9	2	0.61–23.06	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	930.912 \pm 756	2	396.35–1465.47	600.778 \pm 287.3	2	397.62–803.93

Table A2.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.838 \pm 1.2	2	0–1.68	2.616 \pm 0.5	2	2.29–2.94	0.031 \pm 0	2	0–0.06	413.921 \pm 131.4	2	321.03–506.82	275.112 \pm 0.4	2	274.8–275.42
Fall	1.05 \pm 1.3	8	0–4.08	10.948 \pm 8.3	8	0.61–23.06	0.222 \pm 0.4	8	0–1.14	921.756 \pm 573.2	8	287.97–1769.03	507.259 \pm 320.1	8	118–908.52

Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Sampling Locations

Table A3.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project.

Location Code	Location Description
FORB_01	Wetland Complex 1 Pool A
FORB_02	Wetland Complex 1 Pool B
FORB_03	Wetland Complex 1 Pool C
FORB_04	Wetland Complex 2
FORB_05	Wetland Complex 3 Pool A
FORB_06	Wetland Complex 3 Pool B
FORB_07	Wetland Complex 3 Pool C
FORB_08	Wetland Complex 3 Pool D
FORB_09	Wetland Complex 4 Pool A
FORB_10	Wetland Complex 4 Pool B
FORB_11	Wetland Complex 4 Pool C
FORB_12	Wetland Complex 4 Pool D
FORB_13	Wetland Complex 4 Pool E
FORB_14	Wetland Complex 4 Pool F
FORB_15	SW Tile Outlet
FORB_16	Maumee River
FORB_17	Stream 1
FORB_18	Stream 2

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A
- 02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B
- 03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C
- 04. Wetland Complex 2
- 05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A
- 06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B
- 07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C
- 08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D
- 09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A
- 10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B
- 11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C
- 12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D
- 13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E
- 14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F
- 15. SW Tile Outlet
- 16. Maumee River
- 17. Stream 1
- 18. Stream 2

Figure A3.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A3.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	4 \pm 5	40	0–16
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	3 \pm 5	25	0–18
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	8 \pm 13	30	0–50
04. Wetland Complex 2	0 \pm 2	20	0–10
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	5 \pm 5	24	0–15
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	4 \pm 4	24	0–12
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	4 \pm 4	22	0–14
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	14 \pm 10	29	0–35
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	16 \pm 13	26	0–37
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	18 \pm 13	24	0–40
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	25 \pm 14	25	0–50
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	25 \pm 13	26	0–50
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	2 \pm 4	19	0–12
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	11 \pm 11	22	0–32
15. SW Tile Outlet	5 \pm 10	17	0–30
16. Maumee River	42 \pm 26	24	0–100
17. Stream 1	8 \pm 11	40	0–60
18. Stream 2	1 \pm 1	15	0–4

Figure A3.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A3.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	16 \pm 18	66	0–100
Spring	12 \pm 13	99	0–50
Summer	11 \pm 16	171	0–100
Fall	7 \pm 12	116	0–50

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A3.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	0.051 \pm 0.1	17 (4)	0–0.26	0.305 \pm 0.6	15 (0)	0.05–2.27
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	0.039 \pm 0	11 (4)	0–0.13	0.14 \pm 0.1	11 (0)	0.03–0.47
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	0.058 \pm 0.1	24 (6)	0–0.25	0.165 \pm 0.2	24 (0)	0.03–0.74
04. Wetland Complex 2	0.379 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.38–0.38	0.54 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.54–0.54
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	0.02 \pm 0	12 (4)	0–0.08	0.22 \pm 0.2	11 (0)	0.04–0.66
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	0.046 \pm 0	8 (1)	0–0.09	0.328 \pm 0.3	7 (0)	0.13–0.88
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	0.076 \pm 0.1	10 (0)	0.01–0.15	0.461 \pm 0.6	8 (0)	0.12–1.72
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	0.026 \pm 0	19 (3)	0–0.07	0.341 \pm 0.5	16 (0)	0.05–2.1
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	0.052 \pm 0.1	16 (5)	0–0.23	0.432 \pm 0.4	14 (0)	0.1–1.7
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	0.073 \pm 0.1	16 (4)	0–0.39	0.455 \pm 0.5	14 (0)	0.02–1.59
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	0.027 \pm 0	18 (4)	0–0.13	0.262 \pm 0.2	16 (0)	0.05–1.08
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	0.063 \pm 0.1	19 (4)	0–0.34	0.738 \pm 1.4	17 (0)	0.02–5.66

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	0.047 ± 0	6 (1)	0–0.1	0.336 ± 0.3	6 (0)	0.12–1.03
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	0.045 ± 0.1	11 (5)	0–0.33	0.739 ± 1.5	10 (0)	0.12–5.11
15. SW Tile Outlet	0.051 ± 0	6 (0)	0.03–0.08	0.372 ± 0.2	6 (0)	0.21–0.71
16. Maumee River	0.109 ± 0	17 (1)	0–0.17	0.487 ± 0.7	16 (0)	0.12–2.3
17. Stream 1	0.043 ± 0	27 (2)	0–0.15	0.21 ± 0.2	26 (0)	0.05–0.98
18. Stream 2	0.04 ± 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.08	0.1 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.04–0.16

Table A3.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.088 \pm 0.1	38 (1)	0–0.38	0.271 \pm 0.1	39 (0)	0.06–0.57
Spring	0.017 \pm 0	76 (33)	0–0.14	0.202 \pm 0.2	76 (0)	0.04–0.88
Summer	0.075 \pm 0.1	61 (7)	0–0.39	0.824 \pm 1.1	53 (0)	0.04–5.66
Fall	0.054 \pm 0.1	65 (8)	0–0.25	0.176 \pm 0.1	52 (0)	0.02–0.55

Figure A3.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A3.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	0.07 \pm 0.1	15 (6)	0–0.39	0.012 \pm 0	17 (12)	0–0.11	0.804 \pm 0.5	15 (0)	0.16–1.84
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	0.06 \pm 0.1	11 (3)	0–0.14	0.02 \pm 0	11 (7)	0–0.13	0.847 \pm 0.6	11 (0)	0.3–1.9
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	0.042 \pm 0.1	24 (9)	0–0.19	0.01 \pm 0	24 (20)	0–0.08	0.783 \pm 0.7	24 (0)	0.04–3.77
04. Wetland Complex 2	0.106 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.11–0.11	0.051 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	0.79 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.79–0.79
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	0.053 \pm 0.1	12 (5)	0–0.16	0.013 \pm 0	12 (9)	0–0.07	0.948 \pm 0.6	11 (0)	0.04–2.31
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	0.056 \pm 0.1	8 (4)	0–0.15	0.042 \pm 0.1	8 (6)	0–0.29	0.932 \pm 0.5	7 (1)	0–1.62
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	0.072 \pm 0.1	10 (4)	0–0.21	0.01 \pm 0	10 (7)	0–0.07	1.572 \pm 2.4	8 (0)	0.08–7.37
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	0.106 \pm 0.2	19 (6)	0–0.99	0.445 \pm 1.9	19 (12)	0–8.21	1.773 \pm 4	16 (0)	0.05–16.63
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	0.181 \pm 0.4	16 (5)	0–1.58	0.019 \pm 0	16 (12)	0–0.12	2.279 \pm 1.3	14 (0)	0.11–5.86
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	0.285 \pm 0.6	16 (6)	0–2.11	0.036 \pm 0.1	16 (10)	0–0.19	2.017 \pm 1.3	14 (0)	0.11–4.87

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	0.783 ± 1.9	18 (7)	0–6.99	0.016 ± 0	18 (12)	0–0.08	2.017 ± 1.4	16 (0)	0.07–5.05
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	0.744 ± 1.4	19 (7)	0–5.09	0.757 ± 2.1	19 (9)	0–8.79	3.863 ± 6.3	17 (0)	0.42–27.28
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	0.888 ± 1.3	6 (1)	0–2.82	0 ± 0	6 (6)	0–0	1.985 ± 1.6	6 (0)	0.12–4.34
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	0.069 ± 0.1	11 (4)	0–0.16	0.102 ± 0.3	11 (7)	0–0.91	1.617 ± 1.1	10 (0)	0.58–4.44
15. SW Tile Outlet	1.092 ± 1.2	6 (2)	0–3.15	0.232 ± 0.4	6 (2)	0–0.94	2.301 ± 1.8	6 (0)	0.02–5.29
16. Maumee River	3.538 ± 3.1	17 (0)	1.08–14.31	0.037 ± 0.1	17 (9)	0–0.23	4.357 ± 3.8	16 (0)	0.12–16.1
17. Stream 1	0.876 ± 1.3	27 (4)	0–5.07	0.068 ± 0.1	27 (13)	0–0.66	1.832 ± 1.6	26 (0)	0.07–6
18. Stream 2	0.097 ± 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.19	0.08 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.03–0.13	0.555 ± 0.2	2 (0)	0.42–0.69

Table A3.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	1.318 \pm 1.7	38 (11)	0–5.62	0.026 \pm 0.1	38 (23)	0–0.28	2.444 \pm 1.9	39 (0)	0.26–7.88
Spring	0.263 \pm 0.8	76 (24)	0–5.1	0.087 \pm 0.2	76 (36)	0–1.83	1.357 \pm 1	76 (1)	0–4.95
Summer	0.739 \pm 2	59 (24)	0–14.31	0.373 \pm 1.6	61 (35)	0–8.79	2.921 \pm 4.8	53 (0)	0.02–27.28
Fall	0.39 \pm 1.2	65 (15)	0–6.99	0.002 \pm 0	65 (59)	0–0.04	1.231 \pm 1	52 (0)	0.36–5.86

Soil Characteristics

Table A3.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	7.235 \pm 0.3	8	6.8–7.45	495.312 \pm 710.7	8	27.8–1921
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	6.552 \pm 0.4	5	6.07–6.91	88.888 \pm 121.6	5	20.34–304
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	6.283 \pm 0.2	6	5.97–6.62	49.918 \pm 80.6	6	12.09–214.4
04. Wetland Complex 2	6.877 \pm 0	2	6.86–6.9	17.23 \pm 1.6	2	16.07–18.39
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	5.479 \pm 0.6	5	4.69–6.14	47.496 \pm 63.5	5	10.27–159.3
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	5.245 \pm 0.1	7	5.06–5.39	46.5 \pm 85	7	8.48–239
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	5.13 \pm 0.4	6	4.78–5.75	38.602 \pm 74.2	6	7.38–190
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	5.323 \pm 0.5	6	4.65–5.79	38.825 \pm 63	6	10.48–167.3
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	7.172 \pm 0.5	4	6.53–7.63	466.325 \pm 666.9	4	102.8–1466
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	6.129 \pm 0.2	3	5.88–6.25	378.367 \pm 551.6	3	42.3–1015
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	7.141 \pm 0.3	3	6.9–7.45	605.7 \pm 745.2	3	160.7–1466
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	7.287 \pm 0.2	4	7.08–7.45	1278.675 \pm 2227.4	4	125.5–4619
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	7.126 \pm 0.1	2	7.08–7.17	55.35 \pm 6.9	2	50.5–60.2

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	5.792 \pm NA	1	5.79–5.79	41.1 \pm NA	1	41.1–41.1
16. Maumee River	7.604 \pm NA	1	7.6–7.6	196.1 \pm NA	1	196.1–196.1
17. Stream 1	7.386 \pm 0.4	4	6.8–7.67	138.05 \pm 63	4	101.4–232
18. Stream 2	7.448 \pm 0.4	2	7.17–7.72	64.15 \pm 37.3	2	37.8–90.5

Table A3.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	6.405 \pm 1	45	4.65–7.72	57.909 \pm 59	45	7.38–232
Summer	6.267 \pm 0.9	24	4.69–7.45	588.465 \pm 1025.8	24	8.48–4619

Table A3.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	30.083 \pm 24.4	10	5.06–94.73	538.211 \pm 355.7	10	149.1–1425.29	731.06 \pm 168.6	10	357.88–929.7	87.029 \pm 40.7	10	0–153
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	16.448 \pm 10.2	7	1.52–34.5	312.885 \pm 132.8	7	131.6–519.81	827.912 \pm 228.6	7	503.4–1084.68	95.949 \pm 35.1	7	31–131
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	10.833 \pm 10.2	8	1.38–33.3	464.029 \pm 444.3	8	111.23–1431.02	788.696 \pm 160.1	8	609.11–1008.19	105.395 \pm 41.5	8	56–181
04. Wetland Complex 2	5.351 \pm 2.8	3	3.14–8.5	169.553 \pm 35	3	132.8–202.46	755.113 \pm 125.6	3	640.06–889.18	90.558 \pm 17	3	78.67–110
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	8.653 \pm 4.7	7	0.96–16.8	562.023 \pm 791.7	7	122.5–2340.93	994.714 \pm 143.6	7	850.7–1262.8	136.766 \pm 62.2	7	94–274
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	12.158 \pm 7.3	9	1.49–23.42	656.03 \pm 384	9	225.51–1301.65	1177.537 \pm 143.1	9	946.51–1379.52	159.375 \pm 36.3	9	101.57–216
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	8.541 \pm 4.5	8	1.7–16.85	621.601 \pm 884.8	8	98.7–2759.08	998.054 \pm 337.3	8	460.61–1321.25	140.407 \pm 72	8	61.92–284
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	13.836 \pm 13.2	8	4.77–40.2	847.397 \pm 983.6	8	104.29–2903.71	1093.681 \pm 393.3	8	333.12–1457.83	158.765 \pm 81.9	8	46.38–321.41

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	10.354 \pm 7.1	8	1.69–22.02	456.992 \pm 463.9	8	46.7–1088.45	446.825 \pm 384	8	23.66–996.37	66.525 \pm 61.3	8	0–152.64
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	21.915 \pm 7.6	7	9.4–34.37	758.698 \pm 493.5	7	69.1–1247.6	714.479 \pm 227.1	7	466.8–1100.84	102.178 \pm 39.6	7	48–160.63
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	13.907 \pm 6.7	7	4.18–24.2	1028.637 \pm 854.7	7	146–2442.52	614.558 \pm 334.2	7	0.18–979.95	113.555 \pm 80.9	7	21.43–240.72
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	17.87 \pm 7.6	7	8.3–28.07	995.493 \pm 924.3	7	159.3–2532.63	755.492 \pm 366.9	7	397.9–1355.05	124.029 \pm 90.2	7	38.95–274.2
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	10.248 \pm 5.7	5	4.9–16.79	133.979 \pm 55	5	85.7–227.1	627.943 \pm 279.5	5	339.3–1069.4	69.386 \pm 33.6	5	37.62–124
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	19.058 \pm 9.8	5	11.4–35.2	677.645 \pm 542.4	5	149.9–1391.8	808.75 \pm 187.6	5	516.05–985.5	111.364 \pm 40.4	5	73.82–159
15. SW Tile Outlet	44 \pm NA	1	44–44	413.3 \pm NA	1	413.3–413.3	325 \pm NA	1	325–325	16 \pm NA	1	16–16
16. Maumee River	23.63 \pm 18.9	4	3.3–47.7	337.982 \pm 369.6	4	133.5–891.4	76.94 \pm 68.1	3	21.5–153	8.333 \pm 13.6	3	0–24
17. Stream 1	22.956 \pm 22.6	7	1.12–72	391.509 \pm 183.7	7	213.93–654.84	166.476 \pm 147	7	21.5–394	22.652 \pm 19.1	7	0–43
18. Stream 2	11.025 \pm 14.2	2	0.95–21.1	162.091 \pm 7.4	2	156.88–167.3	365.224 \pm 515.9	2	0.42–730.03	39.88 \pm 45.4	2	7.78–71.98

Table A3.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	11.532 \pm 14.5	45	0.95–94.73	484.296 \pm 561	45	46.7–2759.08	698.408 \pm 420.3	45	0.18–1328.62	96.226 \pm 69	45	0–284
Summer	17.055 \pm 8.2	36	2.34–35.2	826.962 \pm 720.8	36	74.9–2903.71	872.506 \pm 332.8	36	59.6–1457.83	129.009 \pm 69.7	36	0–321.41
Fall	20.663 \pm 15.3	32	3.3–72	432.609 \pm 417.3	32	69.1–1357.2	675.432 \pm 310.2	31	21.5–1255.5	82.613 \pm 43.5	31	0–170

Figure A3.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A3.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	1.154 \pm 1.4	10	0–4.38	5.428 \pm 3.9	10	0–12.06	0.594 \pm 0.7	10	0–1.57	1023.193 \pm 295.8	10	356–1446	427.441 \pm 94.6	10	183–540
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	0.557 \pm 0.7	7	0–1.93	3.268 \pm 4.7	7	0–12.32	0.838 \pm 1.1	7	0–2.37	1045.421 \pm 428.9	7	405–1664	460.546 \pm 150	7	179–595.21
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	0.242 \pm 0.5	8	0–1.13	2.229 \pm 2.2	8	0–4.91	0.546 \pm 1	8	0–2.92	751.943 \pm 268.1	8	430.85–1223	376.781 \pm 123.8	8	272–640
04. Wetland Complex 2	0.21 \pm 0.4	3	0–0.63	4.069 \pm 3.3	3	1.27–7.75	1.39 \pm 2	3	0–3.64	916.333 \pm 29.6	3	884–942	287.667 \pm 59	3	241–354
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	0.093 \pm 0.2	7	0–0.65	2.725 \pm 2.6	7	0–7.32	1.755 \pm 2	7	0–5.46	744.122 \pm 499.6	7	125.71–1658	343.012 \pm 84.3	7	218.44–451
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	0.804 \pm 1	9	0–3.1	4.409 \pm 3	9	0–11.12	2.237 \pm 3.5	9	0–9.17	980.391 \pm 338.1	9	241–1340	393.514 \pm 95.7	9	216–512
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	0.158 \pm 0.3	8	0–0.9	3.643 \pm 3	8	0–9.02	4.786 \pm 11.8	8	0–34	768.415 \pm 211	8	420–984.44	408.483 \pm 57.3	8	308–488.11
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	0.871 \pm 1.9	8	0–5.44	4.672 \pm 5.7	8	0–17.84	3.805 \pm 5.2	8	0–15.62	548.66 \pm 139.5	8	342–704.72	370.35 \pm 54.4	8	288–445

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	1.378 ± 0.8	6	0.44–2.58	7.127 ± 4.2	6	2.93–14.21	5.346 ± 8.4	6	0–20.71	1142.028 ± 413.1	8	409–1739.9	440.733 ± 127.1	8	190–608.18
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	0.882 ± 0.6	5	0–1.73	7.841 ± 8.7	5	1.29–22.82	5.553 ± 9.2	5	0–21.86	1198.56 ± 331.4	7	545.81–1540	402.554 ± 102.3	7	187.81–479
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	0.334 ± 0.3	5	0–0.67	5.413 ± 3.4	5	1.75–10.39	16.503 ± 14.2	5	0–32.8	1151.603 ± 195	7	939.47–1499.75	371.984 ± 47.3	7	311–434
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	0.71 ± 0.8	5	0–1.8	17.872 ± 22.2	5	5.56–57.56	33.92 ± 70.9	5	0–160.61	1207.71 ± 774.8	7	141.04–2650.93	409.388 ± 99.8	7	314.21–553.51
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	2.686 ± 3.3	4	0–7.4	6.194 ± 3.3	4	1.45–9.02	0.457 ± 0.3	4	0–0.68	1265.4 ± 1457.5	5	455–3844	433.4 ± 281.4	5	160–864
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	0.437 ± 0.8	3	0–1.31	10.063 ± 4.5	3	5.31–14.16	7.308 ± 7	3	0–13.91	1274.4 ± 777.3	5	425–2317	526 ± 171.4	5	306–784
15. SW Tile Outlet	7.757 ± NA	1	7.76–7.76	14.272 ± NA	1	14.27–14.27	0 ± NA	1	0–0	2335 ± NA	1	2335–2335	835 ± NA	1	835–835
16. Maumee River	3.395 ± 2.5	4	0.67–6.12	6.807 ± 4.6	4	3.33–13.19	2.377 ± 4.8	4	0–9.51	1259 ± 1033.4	4	159–2655	534 ± 266.4	4	153–753
17. Stream 1	0.986 ± 1.3	6	0–3.47	6.465 ± 3.6	6	3.29–12.96	2.609 ± 6.4	6	0–15.66	1305.143 ± 349.4	7	974–1879	558.429 ± 265.7	7	399–1151
18. Stream 2	3.094 ± 3.6	2	0.54–5.65	0 ± 0	2	0–0	0.63 ± 0.9	2	0–1.26	642.5 ± 589	2	226–1059	259.5 ± 109.6	2	182–337

Table A3.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)		TP (mg P/kg)			
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	0.896 \pm 1.4	45	0–5.65	5.427 \pm 4.6	45	0–22.82	2.656 \pm 6	45	0–34	907.111 \pm 558.4	45	226–3844	412.4 \pm 130.1	45	179–864
Summer	0.524 \pm 0.4	24	0–1.29	7.774 \pm 11.3	24	0–57.56	10.796 \pm 33	24	0–160.61	1087.52 \pm 479.9	36	125.71–2650.93	415.367 \pm 118.5	36	187.81–784
Fall	1.393 \pm 2.2	32	0–7.76	4.229 \pm 4.3	32	0–17.84	3.282 \pm 6.5	32	0–25.75	1107.656 \pm 594.5	32	159–2655	438.969 \pm 197.4	32	153–1151

Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)
Sampling Locations

Table A4.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project.

Location Code	Location Description
MAGM_01	Creek WCS1
MAGM_02	Wetland WCS1
MAGM_03	Creek Half
MAGM_04	Wetland Half
MAGM_05	Wetland Center
MAGM_06	Creek WCS2
MAGM_07	Wetland WCS2
MAGM_08	Wetland Pump

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Creek WCS1
 - 02. Wetland WCS1
 - 03. Creek Half
 - 04. Wetland Half
 - 05. Wetland Center
 - 06. Creek WCS2
 - 07. Wetland WCS2
 - 08. Wetland Pump

Figure A4.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A4.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Creek WCS1	37 \pm 10	26	25–63
02. Wetland WCS1	46 \pm 17	32	15–90
03. Creek Half	39 \pm 11	23	15–72
04. Wetland Half	23 \pm 6	29	15–37
05. Wetland Center	68 \pm 18	4	57–94
06. Creek WCS2	43 \pm 21	25	18–92
07. Wetland WCS2	44 \pm 16	41	20–81
08. Wetland Pump	65 \pm 30	14	30–128

Figure A4.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A4.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	73 \pm 15	3	60–90
Spring	40 \pm 21	37	17–127
Summer	41 \pm 18	86	18–128
Fall	41 \pm 19	68	15–90

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A4.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Creek WCS1	0.041 \pm 0	25 (0)	0–0.12	0.16 \pm 0.1	25 (0)	0.03–0.28
02. Wetland WCS1	0.031 \pm 0	26 (0)	0–0.09	0.115 \pm 0.1	26 (0)	0–0.25
03. Creek Half	0.027 \pm 0	23 (0)	0–0.09	0.118 \pm 0.1	23 (0)	0.04–0.27
04. Wetland Half	0.011 \pm 0	21 (0)	0–0.04	0.13 \pm 0.1	21 (0)	0–0.63
05. Wetland Center	0.003 \pm 0	5 (0)	0–0.01	0.055 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.02–0.14
06. Creek WCS2	0.012 \pm 0	23 (0)	0–0.05	0.08 \pm 0	23 (0)	0–0.14
07. Wetland WCS2	0.015 \pm 0	31 (0)	0–0.07	0.095 \pm 0.1	31 (0)	0–0.24
08. Wetland Pump	0.018 \pm 0	15 (0)	0–0.06	0.106 \pm 0	15 (0)	0.04–0.19

Table A4.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.009 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.02	0.119 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.04–0.18
Spring	0.016 \pm 0	45 (0)	0–0.08	0.099 \pm 0.1	45 (0)	0–0.29
Summer	0.032 \pm 0	79 (0)	0–0.12	0.144 \pm 0.1	79 (0)	0–0.63
Fall	0.012 \pm 0	42 (0)	0–0.07	0.07 \pm 0	42 (0)	0.02–0.16

Figure A4.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A4.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Creek WCS1	0.913 \pm 1.5	25 (0)	0.02–6.15	0.101 \pm 0.1	25 (0)	0.02–0.25	1.988 \pm 1.8	25 (0)	0.56–8.21
02. Wetland WCS1	0.2 \pm 0.8	26 (0)	0–4.12	0.08 \pm 0.1	26 (0)	0.01–0.27	1.231 \pm 0.9	26 (0)	0–5.43
03. Creek Half	0.827 \pm 1.5	23 (0)	0.01–6.32	0.09 \pm 0.1	23 (0)	0.02–0.22	1.769 \pm 1.9	23 (0)	0.57–9.04
04. Wetland Half	0.033 \pm 0	21 (0)	0–0.1	0.04 \pm 0	21 (0)	0.02–0.14	1.325 \pm 0.7	21 (0)	0–3.37
05. Wetland Center	0.043 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.07	0.03 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.02–0.05	1.133 \pm 0.4	5 (0)	0.8–1.9
06. Creek WCS2	0.65 \pm 1	23 (0)	0.02–4.04	0.084 \pm 0.1	23 (0)	0.03–0.21	1.293 \pm 1.2	23 (0)	0–5.44
07. Wetland WCS2	0.374 \pm 0.8	31 (0)	0–3.23	0.114 \pm 0.1	31 (0)	0.02–0.36	1.171 \pm 0.9	31 (0)	0–4.18
08. Wetland Pump	0.092 \pm 0.2	15 (0)	0–0.77	0.075 \pm 0.1	15 (0)	0.01–0.18	1.081 \pm 0.5	15 (0)	0.51–2.45

Table A4.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.076 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0–0.17	0.043 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.09	1.69 \pm 0.9	3 (0)	0.72–2.45
Spring	0.61 \pm 0.8	45 (0)	0–3.2	0.069 \pm 0.1	45 (0)	0.01–0.21	1.549 \pm 0.9	45 (0)	0–3.8
Summer	0.576 \pm 1.4	79 (0)	0–6.32	0.1 \pm 0.1	79 (0)	0.02–0.27	1.637 \pm 1.6	79 (0)	0–9.04
Fall	0.063 \pm 0.1	42 (0)	0–0.36	0.074 \pm 0.1	42 (0)	0.01–0.36	0.812 \pm 0.2	42 (0)	0.49–1.24

Soil Characteristics

Table A4.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Wetland WCS1	7.25 \pm 0.4	4	6.7–7.7	40831 \pm NA	1	40831–40831	3066 \pm 2291.5	3	1248–5640
04. Wetland Half	7.45 \pm 0.2	4	7.3–7.8	44796 \pm NA	1	44796–44796	3875.75 \pm 2704.3	4	1853–7750
07. Wetland WCS2	7.4 \pm 0.3	4	7–7.7	68752 \pm NA	1	68752–68752	2256.5 \pm 1954.2	4	1082–5180

Table A4.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	7.217 \pm 0.3	6	6.7–7.5	51459.667 \pm 15106.3	3	40831–68752	4734.8 \pm 2359.8	5	1404–7750
Summer	7.3 \pm 0.1	3	7.2–7.4	NA	NA	NA	1841 \pm 475.1	3	1360–2310
Fall	7.733 \pm 0.1	3	7.7–7.8	NA	NA	NA	1510 \pm 603.3	3	1082–2200

Table A4.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Wetland WCS1	26.475 \pm 23.9	4	3–55.5	1274.25 \pm 1169.3	4	228–2376	76 \pm 51.5	3	21–123	63 \pm 51.2	3	4–95
04. Wetland Half	9.725 \pm 6.8	4	1.7–18.3	800.25 \pm 345	4	370–1127	23.667 \pm 12.7	3	10–35	42.667 \pm 10.7	3	31–52
07. Wetland WCS2	23.475 \pm 23.3	4	7.1–57.3	851.25 \pm 740.6	4	317–1894	197 \pm 218.4	4	21–516	46.25 \pm 33.7	4	11–86

Table A4.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	25.483 \pm 18.2	6	9.3–57.3	1222 \pm 715.2	6	228–2193	130.333 \pm 193.2	6	10–516	57.167 \pm 32.5	6	4–95
Summer	24.667 \pm 26.7	3	8.9–55.5	1124 \pm 1099.3	3	317–2376	56.667 \pm 57.5	3	21–123	44 \pm 41.1	3	11–90
Fall	3.933 \pm 2.8	3	1.7–7.1	333 \pm 35.2	3	300–370	135 \pm NA	1	135–135	27 \pm NA	1	27–27

Figure A4.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A4.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Wetland WCS1	2.153 \pm 2.5	4	0–5.74	11.124 \pm 10.1	4	1.87–23.45	6.077 \pm 8.5	4	0.72–18.78	1746.5 \pm 1111.1	4	653–3279	482.5 \pm 106.5	4	363–622
04. Wetland Half	0.71 \pm 1.1	4	0–2.29	5.426 \pm 5	4	2.29–12.75	4.524 \pm 3.3	4	1.05–7.5	1361.25 \pm 966.9	4	203–2224	517.5 \pm 48.9	4	466–565
07. Wetland WCS2	0.806 \pm 1.3	4	0–2.75	4.287 \pm 3.4	4	1.17–8.98	7.658 \pm 6.8	4	3.23–17.77	1754.25 \pm 1975.7	4	633–4712	530.75 \pm 180.2	4	395–796

Table A4.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	1.036 \pm 2.3	6	0–5.74	10.704 \pm 8.4	6	1.17–23.45	4.848 \pm 6.4	6	0.72–17.77	2490.167 \pm 1329.3	6	932–4712	576 \pm 125	6	454–796
Summer	2.305 \pm 0.4	3	1.87–2.75	2.305 \pm 0.4	3	1.87–2.75	9.84 \pm 8	3	3.23–18.78	1006 \pm 312.4	3	740–1350	435.667 \pm 63.2	3	363–478
Fall	0.516 \pm 0.5	3	0–1	4.071 \pm 0.2	3	3.81–4.24	4.811 \pm 2.8	3	1.67–7.08	496.333 \pm 254.2	3	203–653	453.333 \pm 50.6	3	395–486

Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East (OAKE)
Sampling Locations

Table A5.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project.

Location Code	Location Description
OAKE_01	Wetland Pool 20
OAKE_02	Wetland Pool 21
OAKE_03	Wetland Pool 22
OAKE_04	Wetland Pool 23
OAKE_05	Wetland Pool 24
OAKE_06	Wetland Pool 25
OAKE_07	Wetland Pool 26
OAKE_08	Wetland Pool 27
OAKE_09	Wetland Pool 28
OAKE_10	Wetland Pool 29
OAKE_11	Wetland Pool 30
OAKE_12	Wetland Pool 31
OAKE_13	Wetland Pool 32
OAKE_14	Wetland Pool 33
OAKE_15	Wetland Pool 34
OAKE_16	Wetland Pool 35
OAKE_17	Wetland Pool 36
OAKE_18	Wetland Pool 37
OAKE_19	Wetland Pool 38
OAKE_20	Wetland Pool 39
OAKE_21	Wetland Pool 40
OAKE_22	Wetland Pool 41
OAKE_23	Wetland Pool 42
OAKE_24	Wetland Pool 43

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 20
- 02. Wetland Pool 21
- 03. Wetland Pool 22
- 04. Wetland Pool 23
- 05. Wetland Pool 24
- 06. Wetland Pool 25
- 07. Wetland Pool 26
- 08. Wetland Pool 27
- 09. Wetland Pool 28
- 10. Wetland Pool 29
- 11. Wetland Pool 30
- 12. Wetland Pool 31
- 13. Wetland Pool 32
- 14. Wetland Pool 33
- 15. Wetland Pool 34
- 16. Wetland Pool 35
- 17. Wetland Pool 36
- 18. Wetland Pool 37
- 19. Wetland Pool 38
- 20. Wetland Pool 39
- 21. Wetland Pool 40
- 22. Wetland Pool 41
- 23. Wetland Pool 42
- 24. Wetland Pool 43

Figure A5.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A5.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	1 \pm 3	20	0–15
02. Wetland Pool 21	8 \pm 11	13	0–30
03. Wetland Pool 22	8 \pm 17	15	0–60
04. Wetland Pool 23	1 \pm 4	13	0–15
05. Wetland Pool 24	5 \pm 11	13	0–35
06. Wetland Pool 25	14 \pm 15	20	0–47
07. Wetland Pool 26	28 \pm 16	22	0–60
08. Wetland Pool 27	7 \pm 11	11	0–30
09. Wetland Pool 28	7 \pm 12	11	0–35
10. Wetland Pool 29	14 \pm 16	13	0–50
11. Wetland Pool 30	24 \pm 21	25	0–62
12. Wetland Pool 31	11 \pm 12	17	0–40
13. Wetland Pool 32	2 \pm 4	15	0–16
14. Wetland Pool 33	10 \pm 14	14	0–40
15. Wetland Pool 34	21 \pm 15	16	0–50
16. Wetland Pool 35	15 \pm 14	14	0–35
17. Wetland Pool 36	5 \pm 11	18	0–40
18. Wetland Pool 37	6 \pm 9	16	0–30
19. Wetland Pool 38	6 \pm 11	14	0–30
20. Wetland Pool 39	19 \pm 14	23	0–60
21. Wetland Pool 40	40 \pm 21	40	0–70
22. Wetland Pool 41	9 \pm 15	12	0–50

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
23. Wetland Pool 42	28 \pm 24	24	0–62
24. Wetland Pool 43	15 \pm 20	15	0–60

Figure A5.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A5.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	29 \pm 17	15	10–60
Spring	23 \pm 21	87	0–62
Summer	18 \pm 20	156	0–70
Fall	7 \pm 11	156	0–40

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A5.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	0.023 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.02–0.02	0.329 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.33–0.33
02. Wetland Pool 21	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.085 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.06–0.13
03. Wetland Pool 22	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.253 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.05–0.46
05. Wetland Pool 24	0.011 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.162 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.16–0.16
06. Wetland Pool 25	0.004 \pm 0	5 (3)	0–0.01	0.122 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.06–0.26
07. Wetland Pool 26	0.001 \pm 0	9 (8)	0–0.01	0.131 \pm 0.1	11 (0)	0.04–0.26
08. Wetland Pool 27	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.293 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.26–0.33
09. Wetland Pool 28	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.342 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0.2–0.49
10. Wetland Pool 29	0.007 \pm 0	5 (3)	0–0.02	0.767 \pm 0.6	5 (0)	0.25–1.55
11. Wetland Pool 30	0.014 \pm 0	11 (9)	0–0.12	0.189 \pm 0.2	11 (0)	0.03–0.85
12. Wetland Pool 31	0.016 \pm 0	6 (3)	0–0.05	0.262 \pm 0.2	6 (0)	0.03–0.48
13. Wetland Pool 32	0.013 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.03	0.055 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.03–0.08

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 33	0.005 ± 0	4 (3)	0–0.02	0.387 ± 0.3	4 (0)	0.1–0.83
15. Wetland Pool 34	0 ± 0	9 (9)	0–0	0.146 ± 0	9 (0)	0.09–0.23
16. Wetland Pool 35	0 ± 0	7 (7)	0–0	0.144 ± 0.1	7 (0)	0.05–0.28
17. Wetland Pool 36	0.084 ± 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.18	0.216 ± 0.1	4 (0)	0.02–0.36
18. Wetland Pool 37	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.11 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.02–0.27
19. Wetland Pool 38	0.026 ± 0.1	4 (3)	0–0.11	0.206 ± 0.1	4 (0)	0.04–0.28
20. Wetland Pool 39	0.004 ± 0	8 (6)	0–0.02	0.128 ± 0.1	8 (0)	0.03–0.32
21. Wetland Pool 40	0.015 ± 0.1	31 (27)	0–0.3	0.128 ± 0.1	32 (0)	0.02–0.48
22. Wetland Pool 41	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.697 ± 0.5	3 (0)	0.14–1
23. Wetland Pool 42	0.018 ± 0	11 (9)	0–0.1	0.366 ± 0.4	11 (0)	0.05–1.66
24. Wetland Pool 43	0 ± 0	5 (5)	0–0	0.151 ± 0.2	5 (0)	0.04–0.44

Table A5.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.093 \pm 0	6 (0)	0.04–0.16	0.3 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.2–0.4
Spring	0.01 \pm 0	38 (31)	0–0.18	0.1 \pm 0.1	38 (0)	0.02–0.36
Summer	0.001 \pm 0	49 (44)	0–0.02	0.237 \pm 0.3	52 (0)	0.02–1.66
Fall	0.011 \pm 0	47 (40)	0–0.3	0.262 \pm 0.3	48 (0)	0.03–1.55

Figure A5.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A5.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	0.042 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	1.665 \pm NA	1 (0)	1.67–1.67
02. Wetland Pool 21	0.026 \pm 0	4 (2)	0–0.06	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	1.614 \pm 0.7	4 (0)	0.73–2.38
03. Wetland Pool 22	0.199 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.04–0.5	0.015 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	2.624 \pm 2.3	3 (0)	0.73–5.18
05. Wetland Pool 24	0.058 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.06–0.06	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	4.193 \pm NA	1 (0)	4.19–4.19
06. Wetland Pool 25	0.042 \pm 0.1	5 (3)	0–0.13	0.025 \pm 0	6 (3)	0–0.11	1.473 \pm 0.8	6 (0)	0.68–2.5
07. Wetland Pool 26	0.05 \pm 0.1	9 (6)	0–0.28	0.011 \pm 0	10 (8)	0–0.06	1.776 \pm 0.8	11 (0)	0.72–3.65
08. Wetland Pool 27	0.032 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.032 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	5.866 \pm 1.3	2 (0)	4.97–6.76
09. Wetland Pool 28	0.025 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.05	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	5.86 \pm 1.1	2 (0)	5.05–6.67
10. Wetland Pool 29	0.014 \pm 0	5 (4)	0–0.07	0.051 \pm 0.1	5 (4)	0–0.25	6.951 \pm 3.8	5 (0)	3.12–11.1
11. Wetland Pool 30	0.133 \pm 0.2	11 (4)	0–0.8	0.081 \pm 0.3	11 (9)	0–0.87	2.381 \pm 2.2	11 (0)	0.54–8.23
12. Wetland Pool 31	0.09 \pm 0.1	6 (1)	0–0.15	0.04 \pm 0.1	6 (3)	0–0.17	3.007 \pm 2.8	6 (0)	0.84–6.76
13. Wetland Pool 32	0.631 \pm 0.7	2 (0)	0.13–1.14	0.154 \pm 0.2	2 (1)	0–0.31	1.795 \pm 1.3	2 (0)	0.87–2.72

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 33	0.04 ± 0	4 (2)	0–0.1	0 ± 0	4 (4)	0–0	4.191 ± 2.6	4 (0)	1.14–7.08
15. Wetland Pool 34	0.044 ± 0.1	9 (5)	0–0.16	0.042 ± 0.1	9 (6)	0–0.2	2.522 ± 0.9	9 (0)	0.9–3.94
16. Wetland Pool 35	0.033 ± 0	7 (4)	0–0.12	0.025 ± 0.1	7 (6)	0–0.17	2.085 ± 0.9	7 (0)	0.93–3.1
17. Wetland Pool 36	0.262 ± 0.2	4 (0)	0.05–0.57	0.485 ± 1	4 (3)	0–1.94	1.973 ± 2.2	4 (0)	0.67–5.31
18. Wetland Pool 37	0.077 ± 0	3 (0)	0.04–0.12	0.059 ± 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.18	2.465 ± 3.2	3 (0)	0.63–6.12
19. Wetland Pool 38	0.059 ± 0.1	4 (1)	0–0.13	0.037 ± 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.14	3.014 ± 2	4 (0)	0.69–4.97
20. Wetland Pool 39	0.019 ± 0	8 (6)	0–0.12	0.002 ± 0	8 (7)	0–0.01	1.794 ± 0.9	8 (0)	0.51–2.8
21. Wetland Pool 40	0.049 ± 0.1	31 (12)	0–0.26	0.008 ± 0	32 (26)	0–0.06	1.364 ± 0.5	32 (0)	0.73–2.72
22. Wetland Pool 41	0.028 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.08	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	7.288 ± 3.2	3 (0)	4.12–10.54
23. Wetland Pool 42	0.057 ± 0.1	11 (5)	0–0.15	0.014 ± 0	11 (7)	0–0.09	3.546 ± 3.5	11 (0)	0.83–13.3
24. Wetland Pool 43	2.164 ± 4.6	5 (1)	0–10.47	0.152 ± 0.3	5 (3)	0–0.69	4.836 ± 4.9	5 (0)	0.82–13.07

Table A5.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.261 \pm 0.3	6 (0)	0.11–0.8	0.007 \pm 0	6 (4)	0–0.02	1.258 \pm 0.4	6 (0)	0.71–1.78
Spring	0.138 \pm 0.2	38 (3)	0–1.14	0.074 \pm 0.3	38 (26)	0–1.94	1.197 \pm 0.8	38 (0)	0.51–5.31
Summer	0.04 \pm 0.1	49 (25)	0–0.28	0.017 \pm 0	52 (39)	0–0.17	3.579 \pm 2.3	52 (0)	0.88–13.3
Fall	0.248 \pm 1.5	47 (32)	0–10.47	0.049 \pm 0.2	47 (39)	0–0.87	2.915 \pm 2.9	48 (0)	0.73–13.07

Soil Characteristics

Table A5.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	6.529 \pm 0.5	6	6.16–7.63	95.162 \pm 100.5	6	13.34–226
02. Wetland Pool 21	6.217 \pm 0.2	4	5.93–6.53	102.012 \pm 94.5	4	12.75–200.5
03. Wetland Pool 22	6.432 \pm 0.3	5	6.25–6.92	135.358 \pm 136	5	18–296
04. Wetland Pool 23	6.738 \pm 0.5	5	6.17–7.45	121.74 \pm 139.3	5	33.8–360
05. Wetland Pool 24	6.745 \pm 0.1	5	6.62–6.87	125.54 \pm 123	5	27.1–299
06. Wetland Pool 25	6.987 \pm 0.8	8	6.18–8.83	132.887 \pm 128.9	8	45.8–343
07. Wetland Pool 26	6.45 \pm 0.3	8	6.07–6.8	39.276 \pm 16	8	20.91–67.7
08. Wetland Pool 27	6.691 \pm 0.7	3	5.98–7.4	28.433 \pm 10.4	3	21.2–40.4
09. Wetland Pool 28	6.476 \pm 0	3	6.44–6.51	129.667 \pm 160.8	3	26.9–315
10. Wetland Pool 29	6.634 \pm 0.3	4	6.3–6.99	190.575 \pm 297	4	36–636
11. Wetland Pool 30	7.178 \pm 0.5	5	6.44–7.63	466.32 \pm 623.2	5	50.1–1503
12. Wetland Pool 31	7.111 \pm 0.3	5	6.8–7.61	404.4 \pm 332.4	5	29.3–730
13. Wetland Pool 32	7.279 \pm 0.5	5	6.71–8.04	70.9 \pm 26.1	5	46.1–113.4

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 33	7.388 \pm 0.3	4	7.09–7.7	92.725 \pm 37.5	4	40.2–126.6
15. Wetland Pool 34	7.45 \pm 0.1	4	7.26–7.55	97.075 \pm 34.8	4	60.3–143.3
16. Wetland Pool 35	6.981 \pm 0.4	5	6.62–7.55	64.7 \pm 40.1	5	22.5–127.9
17. Wetland Pool 36	6.925 \pm 0.5	5	6.25–7.5	37.2 \pm 10	5	29.1–53.7
18. Wetland Pool 37	7.06 \pm 0.3	5	6.6–7.41	46.4 \pm 20.8	5	22.3–67
19. Wetland Pool 38	7.335 \pm 0.3	4	6.95–7.6	88.45 \pm 45.2	4	34.4–127.6
20. Wetland Pool 39	6.428 \pm 0.3	7	5.98–6.8	94.413 \pm 83.7	7	14.05–227
21. Wetland Pool 40	6.794 \pm 0.4	14	6.19–7.73	54.293 \pm 25.8	14	29.7–104.8
22. Wetland Pool 41	7.292 \pm 0.3	4	6.9–7.64	315.675 \pm 258.7	4	88.2–628
23. Wetland Pool 42	7.181 \pm 0.4	4	6.62–7.51	98.325 \pm 63.1	4	38.8–158.1
24. Wetland Pool 43	7.354 \pm 0.2	4	7.18–7.69	69.925 \pm 28.5	4	38.3–106.6

Table A5.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	6.852 \pm 0.5	44	5.98–8.83	250.089 \pm 275.7	44	21.2–1503
Summer	6.76 \pm 0.4	45	6.07–7.64	46.029 \pm 25.2	45	12.75–118.5
Fall	7.033 \pm 0.5	37	5.93–8.04	63.519 \pm 34.6	37	13.34–158.1

Table A5.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	14.517 \pm 2.6	6	10.5–17.4	391.933 \pm 310.7	6	94.1–943.6	729.017 \pm 186.4	6	523.6–913.2	90.833 \pm 33.3	6	52–139
02. Wetland Pool 21	32.4 \pm 34.6	4	12.8–84.2	632.125 \pm 155.4	4	408.8–747.6	828.2 \pm 270.4	4	539.6–1144.5	97.75 \pm 42.3	4	47–150
03. Wetland Pool 22	24.18 \pm 15.7	5	11.4–47.9	359.08 \pm 89.7	5	270.4–487.8	768.76 \pm 185	5	480.3–942.1	84 \pm 21.2	5	59–113
04. Wetland Pool 23	9.44 \pm 3.1	5	5.1–12.9	248.06 \pm 142.9	5	126.6–482.5	760.22 \pm 202.6	5	523.7–931.4	91.8 \pm 26.7	5	62–121
05. Wetland Pool 24	27.66 \pm 21.3	5	15.6–65.7	458.92 \pm 211	5	148.7–704.6	822.84 \pm 154.3	5	569.3–951.8	92.4 \pm 26.7	5	65–126
06. Wetland Pool 25	31.619 \pm 9.8	8	19.1–44.9	607.514 \pm 287	8	174.2–865.36	958.727 \pm 328.3	8	507.4–1397.17	112.041 \pm 51.8	8	29–177.71
07. Wetland Pool 26	28.407 \pm 12.5	8	8.3–50.08	717.25 \pm 319.3	8	226.9–1172.37	845.534 \pm 215.1	8	568.1–1216.52	108.346 \pm 28.2	8	72–154.5
08. Wetland Pool 27	10.733 \pm 7	3	6.4–18.8	454.633 \pm 127.1	3	374.5–601.2	701.4 \pm 176.9	3	568.7–902.3	95 \pm 21.2	3	79–119
09. Wetland Pool 28	12.6 \pm 1.6	3	11.4–14.4	422.533 \pm 96.4	3	312.1–489.9	605.133 \pm 127.1	3	508.1–749	80.333 \pm 19.6	3	64–102
10. Wetland Pool 29	16.975 \pm 7.4	4	8.4–24.6	524.15 \pm 157.2	4	337.2–668.8	777.375 \pm 135.5	4	646.6–935.7	101.25 \pm 25.9	4	68–131

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
11. Wetland Pool 30	7.48 ± 4.9	5	1.5–13.7	322.52 ± 197.4	5	104.5–531.3	423.82 ± 301.8	5	80.9–782.2	59 ± 34.8	5	31–105
12. Wetland Pool 31	10.66 ± 3.1	5	7.3–15.1	497.54 ± 194.4	5	202.1–671.1	840.08 ± 243.9	5	511.7–1126.2	113.2 ± 29.5	5	75–151
13. Wetland Pool 32	18.28 ± 13.9	5	6.3–37.2	334.26 ± 102.5	5	253.4–509.2	677.54 ± 233.4	5	450.3–1017	77.8 ± 29.4	5	46–116
14. Wetland Pool 33	12.15 ± 4.1	4	6.7–16	418.325 ± 77.2	4	340.3–498.7	572 ± 182.6	4	380.9–807.4	76.75 ± 23.2	4	54–105
15. Wetland Pool 34	12.325 ± 5.8	4	5.1–17.2	401.6 ± 235.5	4	145–636.4	481.675 ± 90.5	4	363.5–575.5	65.5 ± 17.1	4	40–76
16. Wetland Pool 35	12.36 ± 2.2	5	9.5–15	387.44 ± 257.9	5	172.3–771.6	589.56 ± 167.9	5	391.5–766.2	76.6 ± 10.6	5	64–87
17. Wetland Pool 36	13.12 ± 16.9	5	1.7–42.5	162.68 ± 81.3	5	74.1–293.4	545.56 ± 152.4	5	378.9–794.9	58.6 ± 7.8	5	46–65
18. Wetland Pool 37	11.5 ± 5.1	5	5.5–18.1	325.94 ± 216.8	5	103.7–604.2	551.26 ± 82.7	5	415.3–633.6	69.8 ± 9.6	5	57–79
19. Wetland Pool 38	14.5 ± 10.2	4	2.2–24.9	337.825 ± 258.7	4	89.5–697.6	415.25 ± 272.9	4	17.5–624.7	51.75 ± 30.2	4	13–79
20. Wetland Pool 39	14.519 ± 5.1	7	8.3–20.88	751.12 ± 371	7	149.1–1263.29	886.373 ± 317.7	7	323.6–1391.26	128.92 ± 48.2	7	58–208.91
21. Wetland Pool 40	20.681 ± 8.8	14	10.1–46.1	772.957 ± 394.5	14	163.9–1372.2	892.886 ± 236.3	14	429.6–1397.22	124.692 ± 39.4	14	65–205.85
22. Wetland Pool 41	11.6 ± 7.2	4	4.9–21.6	582.375 ± 320.3	4	198.6–980.1	724.05 ± 175.7	4	522–940.6	103.75 ± 26	4	85–141

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
23. Wetland Pool 42	11.2 ± 2.9	4	8.6–15.3	481.825 ± 211.7	4	218.2–718	579.275 ± 337.6	4	109.6–882.9	82 ± 26.1	4	44–100
24. Wetland Pool 43	5.6 ± 6.2	4	0.8–14.6	136.25 ± 117.2	4	40.7–297.7	559.55 ± 157.4	4	377.1–698.2	66.25 ± 17.4	4	47–82

Table A5.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	16.975 \pm 15.9	44	1.7–84.2	356.839 \pm 177.4	44	59.3–980.1	800.241 \pm 195.1	44	80.9–1144.5	94.705 \pm 27.1	44	31–151
Summer	19.444 \pm 10.7	45	4–50.08	647.512 \pm 349.4	45	89.5–1372.2	799.676 \pm 303.3	45	297.1–1397.22	108.227 \pm 44.7	45	37–208.91
Fall	14.784 \pm 9.9	37	0.8–44.9	442.205 \pm 259.9	37	40.7–1016	537.419 \pm 159	37	17.5–767.3	71.378 \pm 23	37	13–121

Figure A5.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A5.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	0.843 \pm 0.8	6	0–2.38	4.859 \pm 4.4	6	0–11.38	0.637 \pm 1.2	6	0–3.05	1686.667 \pm 715.4	6	449–2619	584.833 \pm 219.8	6	184–796
02. Wetland Pool 21	1.273 \pm 1.1	4	0.31–2.35	6.348 \pm 5	4	0–11.99	0.131 \pm 0.3	4	0–0.52	1766 \pm 158.5	4	1589–1951	649.5 \pm 48.8	4	608–705
03. Wetland Pool 22	0.574 \pm 0.3	5	0.27–1	4.362 \pm 4.2	5	0–10.47	0 \pm 0	5	0–0	1329.8 \pm 432.4	5	622–1639	610.8 \pm 83.6	5	538–754
04. Wetland Pool 23	1.323 \pm 1.1	5	0.49–3.12	5.47 \pm 3.5	5	2.7–11.17	0.148 \pm 0.3	5	0–0.74	1907.4 \pm 363.4	5	1517–2404	675.6 \pm 102.9	5	573–815
05. Wetland Pool 24	1.268 \pm 1.7	5	0–4.04	7.954 \pm 2.9	5	3.24–11.11	0 \pm 0	5	0–0	2246.4 \pm 666.6	5	1714–3398	786.2 \pm 274.2	5	631–1270
06. Wetland Pool 25	0.789 \pm 0.9	8	0–2.09	5.759 \pm 2.6	8	2.52–10.05	1.854 \pm 2.7	8	0–8.21	1424.15 \pm 572.7	8	287–1966.76	559.344 \pm 247	8	103–881
07. Wetland Pool 26	0.716 \pm 1.3	8	0–3.78	4.465 \pm 2	8	2.64–7.16	3.093 \pm 2.2	8	0–5.4	1648.978 \pm 332.3	8	1145–2082.25	644.557 \pm 113.8	8	517–830.34
08. Wetland Pool 27	0.595 \pm 0.6	3	0–1.15	10.216 \pm 6.6	3	4.95–17.66	0.229 \pm 0.4	3	0–0.69	1451 \pm 134.1	3	1310–1577	630.333 \pm 117.6	3	539–763
09. Wetland Pool 28	0.472 \pm 0.4	3	0–0.87	2.946 \pm 2.8	3	0–5.56	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	999.333 \pm 497.7	3	553–1536	422 \pm 105.5	3	349–543
10. Wetland Pool 29	1.448 \pm 1.5	4	0–3.53	5.295 \pm 4.1	4	2.25–11.18	0 \pm 0	4	0–0	1290.5 \pm 785.8	4	653–2283	574.25 \pm 124.9	4	408–698
11. Wetland Pool 30	0.561 \pm 0.5	5	0–1.23	6.809 \pm 3.2	5	3.43–11.67	0 \pm 0	5	0–0	888 \pm 619	5	365–1852	466 \pm 136.4	5	323–677

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Wetland Pool 31	0.349 ± 0.4	5	0–0.78	13.355 ± 13.6	5	2.17–37.15	0 ± 0	5	0–0	1323.6 ± 403.7	5	775–1859	558 ± 170.1	5	357–817
13. Wetland Pool 32	1.095 ± 0.9	5	0–2.14	5.912 ± 2.5	5	2.07–8.75	0.46 ± 0.5	5	0–1.07	1653.6 ± 435.6	5	1197–2169	656.6 ± 150.8	5	463–817
14. Wetland Pool 33	1.108 ± 1.1	4	0–2.64	14.868 ± 15.1	4	1.77–32.52	0.338 ± 0.4	4	0–0.7	1220 ± 64.4	4	1130–1283	681.75 ± 139.1	4	566–870
15. Wetland Pool 34	1.449 ± 1.3	4	0–2.92	4.53 ± 1.6	4	2.57–6.32	2.29 ± 3.5	4	0–7.53	963.667 ± 129.8	3	878–1113	565 ± 32.1	3	530–593
16. Wetland Pool 35	1.327 ± 1.3	5	0–3.33	7.976 ± 3.7	5	5.59–14.53	0.34 ± 0.8	5	0–1.7	1474.6 ± 301.9	5	1091–1762	640.6 ± 125.9	5	535–830
17. Wetland Pool 36	1.554 ± 1	5	0–2.77	3.612 ± 0.8	5	2.64–4.51	0.32 ± 0.4	5	0–0.9	1472 ± 600.6	5	758–2363	593 ± 178.5	5	399–869
18. Wetland Pool 37	1.217 ± 1.1	5	0–2.75	4.426 ± 1.7	5	1.7–6.5	0.186 ± 0.4	5	0–0.93	1619.2 ± 504.6	5	958–2359	662.8 ± 148.5	5	558–899
19. Wetland Pool 38	0.365 ± 0.5	4	0–1.06	3.522 ± 3.2	4	1.27–8.24	0.782 ± 1.6	4	0–3.13	979.5 ± 312.1	4	525–1237	584 ± 175.1	4	356–779
20. Wetland Pool 39	0.188 ± 0.4	7	0–0.91	4.286 ± 2.5	7	0–7.79	0.888 ± 0.8	7	0–1.97	1287.184 ± 602.1	7	356.46–2133	461.849 ± 212.3	7	146.31–752
21. Wetland Pool 40	0.512 ± 0.8	14	0–2.87	3.906 ± 2.2	14	0–8.53	2.034 ± 2.4	14	0–8.21	1449.99 ± 410.1	14	568.36–2086	579.92 ± 117.4	14	301.49–856
22. Wetland Pool 41	0.385 ± 0.3	4	0–0.58	9.738 ± 4.1	4	4.23–14.01	0 ± 0	4	0–0	1111.5 ± 208.7	4	804–1263	535.5 ± 120.5	4	412–694
23. Wetland Pool 42	0.589 ± 0.7	4	0–1.46	5.102 ± 2.4	4	1.88–7.59	0 ± 0	4	0–0	1646.25 ± 682.7	4	785–2196	715 ± 171.8	4	460–830

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
24. Wetland Pool 43	1.381 ± 1.3	4	0–3.16	6.25 ± 4.4	4	2.19–12.02	0.561 ± 0.7	4	0–1.48	796.25 ± 850.9	4	333–2072	495.75 ± 141.3	4	366–694

Table A5.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	1.484 \pm 1.1	44	0–4.04	7.382 \pm 5.6	44	1.27–37.15	0.293 \pm 0.6	44	0–3.13	1555 \pm 532.8	43	385–2619	629 \pm 145.7	43	357–899
Summer	0.289 \pm 0.5	45	0–2.07	3.923 \pm 2.4	45	0–11.11	0.756 \pm 1.2	45	0–4.91	1298.826 \pm 595.9	45	287–3398	582.023 \pm 209.2	45	103–1270
Fall	0.779 \pm 0.8	37	0–3.53	6.913 \pm 6.3	37	0–32.52	1.502 \pm 2.5	37	0–8.21	1452.919 \pm 490	37	333–2404	575.595 \pm 114	37	356–881

Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West (OAKW)
Sampling Locations

Table A6.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project.

Location Code	Location Description
OAKW_01	Wetland Pool 1
OAKW_02	Wetland Pool 2
OAKW_03	Wetland Pool 3
OAKW_04	Wetland Pool 4
OAKW_05	Wetland Pool 5
OAKW_06	Wetland Pool 6
OAKW_07	Wetland Pool 7
OAKW_08	Wetland Pool 8
OAKW_09	Wetland Pool 9
OAKW_10	Wetland Pool 10
OAKW_11	Wetland Pool 11
OAKW_12	Wetland Pool 12
OAKW_13	Wetland Pool 13
OAKW_14	Wetland Pool 14
OAKW_15	Wetland Pool 15
OAKW_16	Wetland Pool 16
OAKW_17	Wetland Pool 17
OAKW_18	Wetland Pool 18
OAKW_19	Wetland Pool 19
OAKW_20	Aurand Run downstream
OAKW_21	Aurand Run conn. to P1
OAKW_22	Aurand Run upstream

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Wetland Pool 4
- 05. Wetland Pool 5
- 06. Wetland Pool 6
- 07. Wetland Pool 7
- 08. Wetland Pool 8
- 09. Wetland Pool 9
- 10. Wetland Pool 10
- 11. Wetland Pool 11
- 12. Wetland Pool 12
- 13. Wetland Pool 13
- 14. Wetland Pool 14
- 15. Wetland Pool 15
- 16. Wetland Pool 16
- 17. Wetland Pool 17
- 18. Wetland Pool 18
- 19. Wetland Pool 19
- 20. Aurand Run downstream
- 21. Aurand Run connection to P1
- 22. Aurand Run upstream

Figure A6.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A6.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	39 \pm 79	39	0–350
02. Wetland Pool 2	3 \pm 6	13	0–15
03. Wetland Pool 3	1 \pm 4	14	0–15
04. Wetland Pool 4	24 \pm 18	19	0–70
05. Wetland Pool 5	4 \pm 7	13	0–20
06. Wetland Pool 6	8 \pm 12	16	0–40
07. Wetland Pool 7	2 \pm 6	12	0–15
08. Wetland Pool 8	12 \pm 16	14	0–40
09. Wetland Pool 9	25 \pm 17	17	0–56
10. Wetland Pool 10	1 \pm 3	15	0–10
11. Wetland Pool 11	4 \pm 7	16	0–25
12. Wetland Pool 12	10 \pm 13	16	0–42
13. Wetland Pool 13	8 \pm 15	12	0–50
14. Wetland Pool 14	3 \pm 6	14	0–20
15. Wetland Pool 15	2 \pm 4	13	0–15
16. Wetland Pool 16	2 \pm 5	15	0–20
17. Wetland Pool 17	0 \pm 1	12	0–4
18. Wetland Pool 18	31 \pm 18	18	0–63
19. Wetland Pool 19	13 \pm 14	16	0–40
20. Aurand Run downstream	13 \pm 9	15	0–29
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	22 \pm 18	12	0–68
22. Aurand Run upstream	24 \pm 15	15	0–50

Figure A6.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A6.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	9 \pm 17	43	0–68
Spring	18 \pm 25	49	0–105
Summer	17 \pm 43	148	0–350
Fall	10 \pm 13	106	0–50

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A6.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.015 \pm 0	31 (19)	0–0.11	0.206 \pm 0.2	31 (0)	0.03–0.79
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.005 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.02	0.429 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.06–0.69
03. Wetland Pool 3	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.046 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.008 \pm 0	13 (9)	0–0.04	0.181 \pm 0.1	13 (0)	0.05–0.44
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.006 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.02	0.32 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.06–0.63
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.01 \pm 0	5 (3)	0–0.04	0.316 \pm 0.3	5 (0)	0.09–0.91
07. Wetland Pool 7	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.091 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.03–0.15
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.046 \pm 0.1	6 (3)	0–0.18	0.327 \pm 0.4	6 (0)	0.06–1.16
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.005 \pm 0	12 (10)	0–0.04	0.424 \pm 0.6	12 (0)	0.11–2.35
10. Wetland Pool 10	0.087 \pm 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.17	0.252 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	0.04–0.46
11. Wetland Pool 11	0.014 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	0.119 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.09–0.14
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.007 \pm 0	9 (6)	0–0.03	0.366 \pm 0.5	9 (0)	0.05–1.5

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.009 ± 0	5 (4)	0–0.04	0.146 ± 0.1	5 (0)	0.04–0.39
14. Wetland Pool 14	0.02 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.03	0.485 ± 0.6	2 (0)	0.09–0.88
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.008 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.02	0.159 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.03–0.29
16. Wetland Pool 16	0.212 ± 0.4	3 (2)	0–0.64	0.568 ± 0.8	3 (0)	0.04–1.5
17. Wetland Pool 17	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.073 ± NA	1 (0)	0.07–0.07
18. Wetland Pool 18	0.006 ± 0	14 (11)	0–0.05	0.141 ± 0.2	14 (0)	0.04–0.63
19. Wetland Pool 19	0.01 ± 0	10 (8)	0–0.08	0.229 ± 0.3	10 (0)	0.02–0.7
20. Aurand Run downstream	0.002 ± 0	11 (9)	0–0.01	0.018 ± 0	11 (7)	0–0.12
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	0.023 ± 0.1	10 (7)	0–0.16	0.058 ± 0.1	10 (6)	0–0.45
22. Aurand Run upstream	0.002 ± 0	11 (10)	0–0.02	0.016 ± 0	11 (6)	0–0.1

Table A6.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.12 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.08–0.16	0.425 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.4–0.45
Spring	0.007 \pm 0	42 (36)	0–0.17	0.095 \pm 0.1	42 (3)	0–0.46
Summer	0.022 \pm 0.1	74 (47)	0–0.64	0.276 \pm 0.4	74 (7)	0–2.35
Fall	0.007 \pm 0	42 (31)	0–0.11	0.189 \pm 0.3	42 (9)	0–1.5

Figure A6.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A6.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.388 \pm 1.4	31 (8)	0–8.06	0.076 \pm 0.4	31 (28)	0–2.27	2.332 \pm 2.6	31 (0)	0.63–11.94
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.113 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.06–0.16	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	4.097 \pm 3	3 (0)	0.69–6.27
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.125 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.12–0.12	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.564 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.56–0.56
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.086 \pm 0.1	13 (6)	0–0.27	0.035 \pm 0.1	13 (8)	0–0.2	1.959 \pm 1	13 (0)	0.42–4.47
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.056 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.05–0.07	0.085 \pm 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.26	3.705 \pm 2.6	3 (0)	0.76–5.2
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.111 \pm 0.1	5 (2)	0–0.24	0.012 \pm 0	5 (4)	0–0.06	2.656 \pm 2	5 (0)	0.82–5.86
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.086 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.05–0.12	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.39 \pm 1.1	2 (0)	0.65–2.13
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.077 \pm 0.1	6 (2)	0–0.18	0.244 \pm 0.5	6 (4)	0–1.22	2.857 \pm 2.2	6 (0)	0.5–6.46
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.079 \pm 0.1	12 (5)	0–0.24	0.046 \pm 0.1	12 (10)	0–0.3	2.867 \pm 2.2	12 (0)	0.7–9.26
10. Wetland Pool 10	0.094 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.04–0.14	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.098 \pm 0.6	2 (0)	0.67–1.53
11. Wetland Pool 11	0.091 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.14	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.515 \pm 1.3	3 (0)	0.74–2.96

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.084 ± 0.1	9 (2)	0–0.19	0.133 ± 0.4	9 (7)	0–1.19	3.308 ± 3.9	9 (0)	0.56–12.95
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.086 ± 0.1	5 (1)	0–0.2	0.011 ± 0	5 (3)	0–0.03	1.657 ± 1.1	5 (0)	0.46–2.85
14. Wetland Pool 14	0.08 ± 0	2 (0)	0.07–0.09	0.025 ± 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.03	3.633 ± 4	2 (0)	0.78–6.49
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.062 ± 0	3 (0)	0.06–0.06	0.022 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.07	2.129 ± 1.3	3 (0)	0.59–3.08
16. Wetland Pool 16	0.233 ± 0.3	3 (0)	0.03–0.62	0.014 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	3.17 ± 3.2	3 (0)	0.81–6.84
17. Wetland Pool 17	0.052 ± NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	0.011 ± NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.691 ± NA	1 (0)	0.69–0.69
18. Wetland Pool 18	0.08 ± 0.1	14 (6)	0–0.25	0.036 ± 0.1	14 (10)	0–0.39	1.562 ± 0.7	14 (0)	0.48–3.02
19. Wetland Pool 19	0.069 ± 0.1	10 (4)	0–0.21	0.067 ± 0.2	10 (9)	0–0.67	8.555 ± 20.6	10 (0)	0.12–67.12
20. Aurand Run downstream	1.419 ± 2.1	11 (0)	0.09–6.42	0.036 ± 0	11 (5)	0–0.11	1.732 ± 2.2	11 (0)	0.22–7.27
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	2.315 ± 3.2	10 (0)	0.11–9.37	0.052 ± 0.1	10 (3)	0–0.26	2.908 ± 3.8	10 (0)	0.21–11.79
22. Aurand Run upstream	2.096 ± 4.4	11 (2)	0–13.95	0.076 ± 0.1	11 (2)	0–0.23	2.591 ± 4.8	11 (0)	0.21–15.57

Table A6.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	4.903 \pm 6.3	2 (0)	0.44–9.37	0.049 \pm 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.1	6.64 \pm 7.3	2 (0)	1.49–11.79
Spring	0.662 \pm 1.7	42 (2)	0–6.83	0.015 \pm 0	42 (32)	0–0.25	1.328 \pm 1.7	42 (0)	0.42–7.74
Summer	0.44 \pm 1.7	74 (23)	0–13.95	0.054 \pm 0.2	74 (52)	0–1.22	3.818 \pm 7.9	74 (0)	0.12–67.12
Fall	0.288 \pm 1.2	42 (14)	0–8.06	0.113 \pm 0.4	42 (25)	0–2.27	2.153 \pm 2.7	42 (0)	0.21–12.95

Soil Characteristics

Table A6.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	6.926 \pm 0.2	11	6.52–7.28	49.426 \pm 43.9	11	16.89–176.7
02. Wetland Pool 2	6.12 \pm 0.1	3	6.02–6.25	23.813 \pm 3	3	21.74–27.2
03. Wetland Pool 3	6.802 \pm 0.2	5	6.57–6.99	46.798 \pm 28.4	5	20.49–91.2
04. Wetland Pool 4	6.099 \pm 0.3	6	5.7–6.38	29.383 \pm 12.5	6	13.6–50.9
05. Wetland Pool 5	5.769 \pm 0.3	4	5.33–6.02	48.675 \pm 39.6	4	19–107
06. Wetland Pool 6	6.015 \pm 0.2	4	5.87–6.25	54.925 \pm 26.9	4	26–80.3
07. Wetland Pool 7	6.102 \pm 0.2	3	5.94–6.34	51.333 \pm 37.5	3	26.2–94.4
08. Wetland Pool 8	5.826 \pm 0.1	3	5.7–5.98	98.7 \pm 81.8	3	34.1–190.7
09. Wetland Pool 9	6.372 \pm 0.6	4	5.96–7.28	38.33 \pm 18.7	4	20.02–61.4
10. Wetland Pool 10	5.719 \pm 0.7	4	4.96–6.56	26.41 \pm 12.1	4	14.24–39.7
11. Wetland Pool 11	6.001 \pm 0.2	3	5.79–6.25	15.163 \pm 4.3	3	12.15–20.03
12. Wetland Pool 12	6.144 \pm 0.1	4	6.02–6.25	53.248 \pm 45.8	4	18.19–120.2
13. Wetland Pool 13	6.433 \pm 0.9	3	5.77–7.45	34.1 \pm 12.4	3	25.1–48.3

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 14	5.854 \pm 0.2	4	5.61–6.02	13.9 \pm 3.8	4	9.83–18.67
15. Wetland Pool 15	5.971 \pm 0.3	4	5.68–6.44	36.25 \pm 18.2	4	20.1–57.8
16. Wetland Pool 16	5.981 \pm 0.2	5	5.74–6.22	22.322 \pm 5	5	15.4–27.2
17. Wetland Pool 17	6.758 \pm 0.7	3	6.02–7.45	11.49 \pm 1.2	3	10.07–12.21
18. Wetland Pool 18	6.578 \pm 1.3	5	5.79–8.83	16.776 \pm 4.9	5	10.26–21.99
19. Wetland Pool 19	6.171 \pm 0.7	5	5.33–6.88	19.624 \pm 7.3	5	13.47–32
20. Aurand Run downstream	7.437 \pm 0.1	5	7.36–7.56	550.58 \pm 694	5	65.6–1614
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	7.434 \pm 0.3	4	7.17–7.78	357.95 \pm 427.2	4	46.2–959
22. Aurand Run upstream	7.496 \pm 0	4	7.43–7.54	474.35 \pm 514	4	82.7–1183

Table A6.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	6.471 \pm 0.8	34	4.96–8.83	36.194 \pm 23	34	12.15–91.2
Summer	6.311 \pm 0.6	33	5.61–7.56	126.752 \pm 323	33	12.15–1614
Fall	6.489 \pm 0.6	29	5.79–7.78	127.829 \pm 266.3	29	9.83–1183

Table A6.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	30.955 \pm 12.4	11	7.8–46.2	479.991 \pm 381.6	11	64.3–1269.4	642.093 \pm 230.6	11	163.7–846.94	69.455 \pm 35.4	11	15–136
02. Wetland Pool 2	31.933 \pm 6.9	3	24.3–37.8	513.367 \pm 62.5	3	441.8–557.4	726.3 \pm 190.3	3	577.3–940.7	79.667 \pm 25.4	3	59–108
03. Wetland Pool 3	30.36 \pm 6.8	5	20.5–37.5	351.36 \pm 66.6	5	278.2–428.5	723.58 \pm 96.1	5	633.3–830.7	72.2 \pm 9.5	5	60–86
04. Wetland Pool 4	47.283 \pm 10	6	32.2–56.6	803.633 \pm 428.8	6	210.8–1399	858.1 \pm 393.8	6	557–1636.2	95.833 \pm 45.6	6	33–159
05. Wetland Pool 5	47.95 \pm 18.2	4	23.2–61.7	890.05 \pm 448.2	4	335.7–1371	658.475 \pm 142	4	463.7–787.7	77 \pm 33.4	4	47–112
06. Wetland Pool 6	32.8 \pm 14.4	4	20.6–51.3	668.45 \pm 273.2	4	352.2–984.9	769.7 \pm 143	4	578.5–919.3	92.5 \pm 23.6	4	62–116
07. Wetland Pool 7	25.7 \pm 10.1	3	14.5–34	448.933 \pm 180.5	3	244–584.2	782.033 \pm 175.8	3	625–971.9	89 \pm 19.3	3	72–110
08. Wetland Pool 8	39.2 \pm 20.1	3	25.4–62.3	723.033 \pm 139.4	3	631.3–883.5	936.6 \pm 94.8	3	827.2–995.2	108.333 \pm 26.5	3	87–138
09. Wetland Pool 9	30.8 \pm 20.7	4	6.9–57	694.875 \pm 460.9	4	211.3–1221.9	577.1 \pm 310.4	4	188.4–892.9	73.75 \pm 39	4	26–120
10. Wetland Pool 10	50.075 \pm 16.9	4	34.5–70.1	660.975 \pm 306.4	4	453.7–1114.3	821.175 \pm 154.1	4	617.5–973.7	80.75 \pm 16.9	4	62–103

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max
11. Wetland Pool 11	30.067 ± 4.6	3	25–34.1	563.033 ± 290.1	3	280.7–860.4	801.433 ± 99.8	3	708.9–907.1	93.333 ± 11.8	3	86–107
12. Wetland Pool 12	25.175 ± 9.2	4	19.3–38.8	540.175 ± 263.6	4	253.5–865.8	796.95 ± 130.9	4	635.1–927.7	96 ± 8.2	4	87–107
13. Wetland Pool 13	13.6 ± 10.3	3	1.8–20.6	521.967 ± 406.8	3	58.4–819.3	621.833 ± 186.1	3	426.6–797.1	86.333 ± 33.5	3	50–116
14. Wetland Pool 14	20.125 ± 3.9	4	14.4–22.7	606.55 ± 335.5	4	152.2–884.5	801.7 ± 265.4	4	528.6–1158.1	105.75 ± 43.8	4	55–158
15. Wetland Pool 15	26.475 ± 12.5	4	15.8–43	663.3 ± 468.1	4	199–1314.6	774.2 ± 179	4	593.4–979.5	99 ± 28.2	4	67–126
16. Wetland Pool 16	27.24 ± 11.4	5	17.7–45.5	476.02 ± 206.5	5	198.1–762.3	781.8 ± 179.8	5	491.2–973.7	89 ± 27.3	5	62–125
17. Wetland Pool 17	12.4 ± 1.2	3	11–13.4	320.533 ± 64	3	252.6–379.8	747.667 ± 146.6	3	591.8–882.7	91.333 ± 20.7	3	69–110
18. Wetland Pool 18	13.34 ± 4.1	5	9.3–19	522.56 ± 229.3	5	236.6–860.7	547.72 ± 276.9	5	262.8–917.9	78.2 ± 22.1	5	48–100
19. Wetland Pool 19	7.64 ± 5.2	5	2.9–15.2	286.08 ± 143.1	5	161.2–515	631.34 ± 281.1	5	188–870.5	80.8 ± 27.3	5	36–110
20. Aurand Run downstream	18.48 ± 10.9	5	2.9–33.1	917.92 ± 597.8	5	146.1–1607.5	426.9 ± 401.2	5	24.2–985.9	81.4 ± 24.2	5	44–106
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	22.75 ± 5	4	19.3–29.9	720.65 ± 416.5	4	158.9–1058.8	274.8 ± 198.9	4	68.3–448.3	48.75 ± 25.9	4	30–87
22. Aurand Run upstream	25.45 ± 25.3	4	3.1–58.9	1334.35 ± 836.6	4	174.7–2173.1	152.725 ± 156.1	4	10.9–341	66 ± 39.8	4	28–115

Table A6.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	28.779 \pm 17.2	34	1.8–70.1	539.215 \pm 435.6	34	58.4–2173.1	787.926 \pm 293.1	34	67.5–1636.2	91.471 \pm 28.9	34	37–159
Summer	31.518 \pm 15.2	33	4–61.7	672.439 \pm 383.2	33	64.3–1490.2	676.207 \pm 222.9	33	38.8–995.2	83.394 \pm 30.1	33	15–138
Fall	23.31 \pm 13.3	29	2.9–57	646.128 \pm 378.9	29	152.2–1499.4	517.893 \pm 234.4	29	10.9–827.2	71.966 \pm 27	29	26–136

Figure A6.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A6.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	1.183 \pm 2	11	0–6.83	7.092 \pm 3.8	11	1.33–12.03	1.042 \pm 2.1	11	0–7.28	1631.818 \pm 620.9	11	359–2382	860.636 \pm 245.2	11	469–1282
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.92 \pm 1.1	3	0.15–2.15	5.786 \pm 3	3	2.41–8.31	1.692 \pm 1.3	3	0.65–3.2	1518.667 \pm 597.3	3	832–1918	783 \pm 119.2	3	660–898
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.779 \pm 0.8	5	0–1.86	5.063 \pm 2.4	5	2.48–8.39	1.232 \pm 1.6	5	0–3.84	1909.2 \pm 331.7	5	1492–2227	774.8 \pm 275.9	5	520–1233
04. Wetland Pool 4	1.08 \pm 1.5	6	0–3.92	3.093 \pm 2.4	6	0–7.42	6.269 \pm 7.6	6	0–17.3	2237.333 \pm 723.2	6	1128–3104	1073.333 \pm 390.6	6	634–1757
05. Wetland Pool 5	1.885 \pm 2	4	0.27–4.67	13.072 \pm 16.4	4	2.1–37.3	3.956 \pm 4.6	4	0–8.55	1529 \pm 455.5	4	1084–2084	855.75 \pm 146.5	4	659–1001
06. Wetland Pool 6	1.304 \pm 1.6	4	0–3.34	7.289 \pm 2.7	4	3.8–10.19	3.637 \pm 5.1	4	0–10.89	1759.25 \pm 753.6	4	1096–2843	736.5 \pm 166	4	599–977
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.779 \pm 1.1	3	0–2	4.383 \pm 0.8	3	3.68–5.28	1.257 \pm 0.3	3	0.88–1.49	1849.667 \pm 474.5	3	1420–2359	667.333 \pm 198.8	3	535–896
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.703 \pm 1.2	3	0–2.11	8.514 \pm 9.3	3	1.85–19.17	11.459 \pm 13.3	3	0–26.02	2407 \pm 622.2	3	1957–3117	975.333 \pm 105.9	3	857–1061
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.415 \pm 0.4	4	0–0.95	1.68 \pm 1.2	4	0–2.54	5.968 \pm 5.2	4	0–12.05	902.75 \pm 693.5	4	168–1810	548.5 \pm 368.9	4	66–963
10. Wetland Pool 10	2.03 \pm 1.7	4	0.2–3.51	7.96 \pm 2	4	5.49–10.12	1.752 \pm 1.7	4	0.58–4.18	2008 \pm 307.3	4	1803–2458	1004.5 \pm 162.4	4	830–1222
11. Wetland Pool 11	0.825 \pm 0.8	3	0–1.67	2.754 \pm 0.8	3	1.91–3.51	0.908 \pm 1.6	3	0–2.72	2056.667 \pm 580.5	3	1535–2682	742.333 \pm 99.4	3	656–851

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min-Max
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.583 ± 0.7	4	0–1.48	6.836 ± 5.4	4	2.82–14.64	1.467 ± 2.5	4	0–5.22	1910.5 ± 673	4	1403–2902	786.75 ± 76.3	4	681–860
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.341 ± 0.6	3	0–1.02	5.629 ± 7.3	3	0–13.84	3.705 ± 3.3	3	0–6.25	728.667 ± 949.2	3	43–1812	393.667 ± 358.4	3	0–701
14. Wetland Pool 14	0.32 ± 0.1	4	0.22–0.44	2.796 ± 3.1	4	0–7.3	1.051 ± 0.7	4	0–1.54	1604.5 ± 185.8	4	1370–1820	661.25 ± 93.4	4	592–799
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.277 ± 0.4	4	0–0.78	4.581 ± 4.5	4	0–9.55	0.657 ± 1	4	0–2.05	989 ± 686.8	4	110–1641	541.25 ± 309.9	4	79–726
16. Wetland Pool 16	0.519 ± 0.4	5	0–0.98	4.083 ± 2.6	5	1.97–8.24	0.493 ± 0.7	5	0–1.55	1605.4 ± 297.3	5	1088–1794	650.4 ± 126.4	5	547–846
17. Wetland Pool 17	0.428 ± 0.5	3	0–1.05	2.893 ± 2.5	3	0–4.37	0.678 ± 1.2	3	0–2.03	1139.667 ± 610.3	3	548–1767	511 ± 51.2	3	479–570
18. Wetland Pool 18	1.192 ± 2	5	0–4.54	2.791 ± 3.1	5	0–6.53	2.289 ± 1.2	5	0.8–4.12	1197.2 ± 372.4	5	645–1486	561.2 ± 134.8	5	352–694
19. Wetland Pool 19	1.172 ± 2.3	5	0–5.23	2.188 ± 3.6	5	0–8.26	1.437 ± 0.8	5	0.57–2.34	1203.8 ± 435.8	5	681–1765	539.4 ± 175.2	5	318–721
20. Aurand Run downstream	0.211 ± 0.5	5	0–1.06	4.475 ± 3.7	5	0–8.11	0.347 ± 0.5	5	0–1.08	2236.2 ± 1031.3	5	1279–3811	563.4 ± 227.1	5	324–829
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	1.714 ± 2.7	4	0–5.69	7.171 ± 9.3	4	0–19.44	1.587 ± 1.3	4	0–3	1726.75 ± 1355.9	4	430–3456	517.25 ± 234.9	4	236–811
22. Aurand Run upstream	0 ± 0	4	0–0	6.98 ± 2.8	4	3.35–10.27	1.321 ± 1.8	4	0–3.78	2144 ± 590.6	4	1319–2634	581.75 ± 194.4	4	458–867

Table A6.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	2.031 \pm 1.7	34	0–6.83	6.613 \pm 3.6	34	0–19.44	0.853 \pm 1.7	34	0–8.55	1590.382 \pm 676	34	331–3456	799.735 \pm 268.2	34	381–1757
Summer	0.198 \pm 0.4	33	0–1.54	4.02 \pm 3.7	33	0–12.03	2.503 \pm 3.2	33	0–12.05	1791.636 \pm 930	33	43–3811	650.909 \pm 287.8	33	0–1282
Fall	0.323 \pm 0.4	29	0–1.84	5.358 \pm 7.6	29	0–37.3	3.833 \pm 5.9	29	0–26.02	1597.655 \pm 447.9	29	430–2498	683.931 \pm 220.2	29	236–1244

Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Sampling Locations

Table A7.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
REDB_01	Pond 1 A
REDB_02	Pond 1 B
REDB_03	Pond 2
REDB_04	Pond 3 A
REDB_05	Pond 3 B
REDB_06	Pond 4
REDB_07	Pond 5
REDB_08	Pond 6
REDB_09	Sandusky River
REDB_10	Ditch 2 S
REDB_11	Ditch 2 N
REDB_12	Spring
REDB_13	Pond A
REDB_14	Pond B
REDB_15	Pond C
REDB_16	Pond D
REDB_17	Pond E
REDB_18	Pond F
REDB_19	Pond G

Sampling Locations

- 01. Pond 1 A
- 02. Pond 1 B
- 03. Pond 2
- 04. Pond 3 A
- 05. Pond 3 B
- 06. Pond 4
- 07. Pond 5
- 08. Pond 6
- 09. Sandusky River
- 10. Ditch 2 S
- 11. Ditch 2 N
- 12. Spring
- 13. Pond A
- 14. Pond B
- 15. Pond C
- 16. Pond D
- 17. Pond E
- 18. Pond F
- 19. Pond G

Figure A7.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A7.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1 A	28 \pm 10	31	0–45
02. Pond 1 B	18 \pm 9	21	0–35
03. Pond 2	26 \pm 14	28	0–52
04. Pond 3 A	39 \pm 8	27	23–65
05. Pond 3 B	31 \pm 13	20	8–58
06. Pond 4	27 \pm 10	37	0–44
07. Pond 5	19 \pm 9	18	0–41
08. Pond 6	18 \pm 11	14	0–35
09. Sandusky River	53 \pm 22	26	13–96
10. Ditch 2 S	24 \pm 23	8	0–60
11. Ditch 2 N	25 \pm 21	17	0–77
12. Spring	35 \pm 25	14	7–69
13. Pond A	19 \pm 10	18	0–35
14. Pond B	23 \pm 10	12	3–38
15. Pond C	20 \pm 10	8	6–36
16. Pond D	20 \pm 7	7	8–28

Figure A7.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A7.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	34 \pm 18	69	6–96
Spring	31 \pm 16	86	5–89
Summer	25 \pm 14	92	0–68
Fall	23 \pm 17	59	0–62

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A7.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pond 1 A	0.01 \pm 0	26 (11)	0–0.1	0.077 \pm 0.1	22 (0)	0–0.29
02. Pond 1 B	0.027 \pm 0	12 (1)	0–0.12	0.295 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.05–0.78
03. Pond 2	0.007 \pm 0	21 (8)	0–0.06	0.096 \pm 0.1	21 (0)	0.02–0.29
04. Pond 3 A	0.037 \pm 0.1	23 (3)	0–0.31	0.188 \pm 0.2	19 (0)	0.02–0.83
05. Pond 3 B	0.029 \pm 0	13 (0)	0–0.13	0.17 \pm 0.1	9 (0)	0.07–0.26
06. Pond 4	0.013 \pm 0	26 (3)	0–0.12	0.125 \pm 0.1	18 (0)	0.02–0.61
07. Pond 5	0.031 \pm 0.1	17 (4)	0–0.26	0.105 \pm 0.1	17 (0)	0.01–0.41
08. Pond 6	0.079 \pm 0.1	10 (1)	0–0.36	0.198 \pm 0.2	10 (0)	0.06–0.56
09. Sandusky River	0.068 \pm 0.1	28 (2)	0–0.18	0.293 \pm 0.2	28 (0)	0.03–0.83
10. Ditch 2 S	0.104 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0–0.24	0.301 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.11–0.44
11. Ditch 2 N	0.037 \pm 0	13 (3)	0–0.09	0.206 \pm 0.2	13 (0)	0.05–0.75
12. Spring	0.02 \pm 0	7 (1)	0–0.08	0.072 \pm 0.1	7 (1)	0–0.22

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Pond A	0.009 ± 0	15 (3)	0–0.03	0.148 ± 0.1	15 (0)	0.04–0.44
14. Pond B	0.007 ± 0	11 (4)	0–0.03	0.163 ± 0.1	11 (0)	0–0.43
15. Pond C	0.014 ± 0	7 (1)	0–0.05	0.204 ± 0.1	7 (0)	0.1–0.34
16. Pond D	0.039 ± 0.1	5 (0)	0–0.19	0.18 ± 0.2	5 (0)	0.08–0.48

Table A7.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.05 \pm 0.1	63 (2)	0–0.29	0.242 \pm 0.2	63 (0)	0.04–0.83
Spring	0.018 \pm 0	69 (20)	0–0.19	0.131 \pm 0.1	69 (0)	0–0.63
Summer	0.038 \pm 0.1	63 (7)	0–0.36	0.216 \pm 0.2	39 (0)	0.04–0.78
Fall	0.009 \pm 0	45 (16)	0–0.1	0.089 \pm 0.1	45 (1)	0–0.52

Figure A7.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A7.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0.087 \pm 0.2	26 (2)	0–0.43	0.018 \pm 0	26 (4)	0–0.05	0.838 \pm 0.5	22 (0)	0.03–2.05
02. Pond 1B	0.295 \pm 0.4	12 (3)	0–1.48	0.033 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.01–0.08	1.631 \pm 1	8 (0)	0.38–2.95
03. Pond 2	0.1 \pm 0.1	21 (0)	0–0.49	0.021 \pm 0	20 (3)	0–0.11	1.078 \pm 0.6	21 (0)	0.23–2.32
04. Pond 3A	0.322 \pm 0.9	21 (2)	0–3.88	0.043 \pm 0.1	23 (2)	0–0.38	2.12 \pm 3.2	19 (0)	0.51–14.27
05. Pond 3B	0.114 \pm 0.2	12 (3)	0–0.83	0.099 \pm 0.3	13 (1)	0–1.11	1.573 \pm 0.8	9 (0)	0.28–2.98
06. Pond 4	0.086 \pm 0.1	22 (4)	0–0.51	0.014 \pm 0	26 (2)	0–0.04	1.266 \pm 1	18 (0)	0.17–3.88
07. Pond 5	0.981 \pm 3	17 (0)	0–12.44	0.026 \pm 0	17 (3)	0–0.08	2.054 \pm 3.2	17 (0)	0.33–14.02
08. Pond 6	0.148 \pm 0.4	10 (0)	0–1.14	0.019 \pm 0	10 (1)	0–0.06	0.979 \pm 0.5	10 (0)	0.44–2.29
09. Sandusky River	2.842 \pm 2.7	28 (0)	0–12	0.059 \pm 0.1	28 (1)	0–0.36	4.138 \pm 3.2	28 (0)	0.42–14.56
10. Ditch 2S	0.274 \pm 0.3	6 (0)	0–0.77	0.116 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0–0.31	1.339 \pm 0.9	6 (0)	0.16–2.3
11. Ditch 2N	1.013 \pm 1.8	13 (0)	0–6.11	0.139 \pm 0.3	13 (3)	0–0.83	2.144 \pm 2.3	13 (0)	0.27–7.88
12. Spring	0.12 \pm 0.3	7 (0)	0–0.84	0.018 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0.04	0.366 \pm 0.4	7 (1)	0–1.03

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Pond A	0.357 ± 0.6	15 (0)	0–1.95	0.016 ± 0	15 (4)	0–0.06	1.487 ± 0.8	15 (0)	0.47–3.65
14. Pond B	0.297 ± 0.6	11 (0)	0–2	0.005 ± 0	11 (1)	0–0.02	1.229 ± 1.1	11 (0)	0.11–3.74
15. Pond C	0.212 ± 0.4	7 (0)	0–1.13	0.005 ± 0	7 (1)	0–0.02	1.236 ± 0.8	7 (0)	0.39–2.65
16. Pond D	0.018 ± 0	5 (0)	0–0.09	0.002 ± 0	5 (1)	0–0	1.076 ± 0.7	5 (0)	0.4–2.16

Table A7.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.608 \pm 1.3	63 (0)	0–5.3	0.023 \pm 0.1	63 (4)	0–0.38	1.548 \pm 1.8	63 (1)	0–7.39
Spring	0.636 \pm 1.8	69 (0)	0–12	0.027 \pm 0.1	69 (22)	0–0.36	1.617 \pm 2.1	69 (0)	0.11–14.56
Summer	0.624 \pm 1.3	56 (14)	0–6.33	0.044 \pm 0.1	62 (0)	0–0.67	2.331 \pm 1.7	39 (0)	0.2–8.15
Fall	0.541 \pm 2	45 (0)	0–12.44	0.07 \pm 0.2	45 (1)	0–1.11	1.783 \pm 2.9	45 (0)	0.02–14.27

Soil Characteristics

Table A7.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1 A	7.626 \pm 0.2	3	7.45–7.82	834.733 \pm 1064.7	3	158.2–2062
02. Pond 1 B	7.72 \pm 0.1	5	7.63–7.82	1493.62 \pm 1236.7	5	101.1–2750
03. Pond 2	7.425 \pm 0.1	2	7.36–7.48	100.8 \pm 0.6	2	100.4–101.2
04. Pond 3 A	7.08 \pm 0.1	4	6.99–7.26	645.375 \pm 629.1	4	103.5–1353
05. Pond 3 B	7.508 \pm 0.1	6	7.36–7.63	594.283 \pm 702	6	124.4–1872
06. Pond 4	7.557 \pm 0.1	9	7.45–7.63	717.767 \pm 668.5	9	146.3–1877
07. Pond 5	7.421 \pm 0.1	2	7.36–7.48	133.75 \pm 3.6	2	131.2–136.3

Table A7.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	7.548 \pm 0.2	12	6.99–7.82	1653.75 \pm 595.4	12	965–2750
Summer	7.473 \pm 0.2	19	6.99–7.82	168.605 \pm 65.3	19	100.4–300

Table A7.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1 A	5.584 \pm 0.4	3	5.26–6.1	1292.588 \pm 1054.6	3	230.99–2340.05	281.037 \pm 206.3	3	141.63–518	98.237 \pm 37.9	3	67–140.41
02. Pond 1 B	25.334 \pm 14.1	5	9.78–39.03	957.896 \pm 654.3	5	214.43–2008.88	419.146 \pm 167.6	5	246.32–687.63	75.817 \pm 36.5	5	30.16–124.41
03. Pond 2	20.071 \pm 13.9	2	10.22–29.92	355.641 \pm 262.1	2	170.28–541	520.89 \pm 79	2	464.99–576.79	59.422 \pm 8.5	2	53.41–65.43
04. Pond 3 A	13.394 \pm 2.8	4	9.36–15.33	1567.663 \pm 1225.7	4	526.86–3263.79	824.414 \pm 121.8	4	666.2–962	168.042 \pm 83.3	4	90.64–281.77
05. Pond 3 B	39.648 \pm 27.1	6	10.63–72.39	1404.702 \pm 639	6	654.74–2253.69	706.285 \pm 174.2	6	470.3–948.3	119.205 \pm 75.8	6	20.61–198.85
06. Pond 4	10.295 \pm 11.9	9	2.21–38.32	713.357 \pm 350.3	9	250.3–1325.38	684.067 \pm 151.1	9	453.87–933.48	107.735 \pm 39.2	9	47.17–176.37
07. Pond 5	19.381 \pm 22.8	2	3.22–35.54	672.339 \pm 760.7	2	134.47–1210.2	534.382 \pm 117.7	2	451.15–617.61	79.193 \pm 32.8	2	56.02–102.37

Table A7.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	16.795 \pm 13.8	12	2.91–38.32	1273.413 \pm 858.4	12	253.42–3263.79	604.192 \pm 214	12	183.49–962	123.068 \pm 60.2	12	74.58–281.77
Summer	21.311 \pm 21.3	19	2.21–72.39	871.649 \pm 628.9	19	134.47–2340.05	604.792 \pm 225.4	19	141.63–948.3	96.38 \pm 54.3	19	20.61–190.96

Figure A7.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A7.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1 A	0.101 \pm 0.2	3	0–0.3	2.252 \pm 2.2	3	0–4.31	0.735 \pm 1.3	3	0–2.2	688.985 \pm 616.2	3	0–1187.29	449.419 \pm 415.5	3	0–819.71
02. Pond 1 B	0.663 \pm 0.6	5	0–1.34	4.897 \pm 3.9	5	0–9.33	4.975 \pm 9.6	5	0–22.21	1082.992 \pm 725.4	5	0–1806.74	542.147 \pm 328.5	5	0–782.22
03. Pond 2	0.509 \pm 0.7	2	0–1.02	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	0.185 \pm 0.1	2	0.12–0.25	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	0 \pm 0	2	0–0
04. Pond 3 A	0.146 \pm 0.3	4	0–0.58	1.595 \pm 1.1	4	0–2.36	5.348 \pm 6.7	4	0–14.84	1555.911 \pm 154.2	4	1415.37–1763.99	743.061 \pm 93	4	690.75–881.99
05. Pond 3 B	0.846 \pm 0.7	6	0–1.83	3.975 \pm 3.5	6	0–8.14	2.743 \pm 3.1	6	0–6.62	1171.606 \pm 936.9	6	0–1989.87	598.518 \pm 478.6	6	0–1110.12
06. Pond 4	0.411 \pm 0.5	9	0–1.5	1.85 \pm 2.4	9	0–6.86	1.736 \pm 2.4	9	0–6.23	716.595 \pm 509.8	9	0–1564.32	352.919 \pm 244.7	9	0–794.32
07. Pond 5	0.317 \pm 0.4	2	0–0.63	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	0.2 \pm 0.3	2	0–0.4	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	0 \pm 0	2	0–0

Table A7.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	0.553 \pm 0.5	12	0–1.5	4.521 \pm 2.8	12	1.5–9.33	6.122 \pm 6.3	12	0.88–22.21	1329.505 \pm 431.3	12	768.65–1989.87	681.989 \pm 214.5	12	416.9–1110.12
Summer	0.42 \pm 0.6	19	0–1.83	1.256 \pm 2.2	19	0–8.14	0.414 \pm 1.2	19	0–5.01	591.078 \pm 720.2	19	0–1957.09	295.513 \pm 352.4	19	0–902.14

St. Joseph's River Restoration (SJRE)

Sampling Locations

Table A8.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
SJRE_01	North Tile
SJRE_02	Northwest Tile
SJRE_03	Northeast Tile
SJRE_04	Wetland Pool A
SJRE_05	Wetland Pool B
SJRE_06	Wetland Pool C
SJRE_07	Wetland Pool D
SJRE_08	Wetland Pool E
SJRE_09	Wetland Pool F
SJRE_10	Wetland Pool G
SJRE_11	Reach b/w NoT & WA
SJRE_12	Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet
SJRE_13	Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC
SJRE_14	Reach b/w WC & WG
SJRE_15	Reach b/w WG & East Ditch
SJRE_16	Swale connecting WB tile to WB
SJRE_17	East Ditch
SJRE_18	Ditch Extension
SJRE_19	St. Joseph River
SJRE_20	Reach b/w NWT & Int. w/ RANWT
SJRE_21	Reach b/w NET & Int. w/ RANWT
SJRE_22	Existing Wetland

Sampling Locations

- 01. North Tile
- 02. Northwest Tile
- 03. Northeast Tile
- 04. Wetland Pool A
- 05. Wetland Pool B
- 06. Wetland Pool C
- 07. Wetland Pool D
- 08. Wetland Pool E
- 09. Wetland Pool F
- 10. Wetland Pool G
- 11. Reach between NoT & WA
- 12. Reach between WA & Intersection with NWT outlet
- 13. Reach between NW tile junction & WC
- 14. Reach between WC & WG
- 15. Reach between WG & East Ditch
- 16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB
- 17. East Ditch
- 18. Ditch Extension
- 19. St. Joe River
- 20. Reach between NWT & Intersection with RANWT
- 21. Reach between NET & Intersection with RANWT
- 22. Existing Wetland

Figure A8.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table A8.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. North Tile	5 \pm 12	32	0–50
02. Northwest Tile	18 \pm 14	24	0–55
03. Northeast Tile	14 \pm 10	22	0–30
04. Wetland Pool A	3 \pm 7	28	0–35
05. Wetland Pool B	22 \pm 20	62	0–70
06. Wetland Pool C	11 \pm 17	42	0–50
07. Wetland Pool D	2 \pm 3	19	0–10
08. Wetland Pool E	3 \pm 8	21	0–34
09. Wetland Pool F	2 \pm 6	18	0–24
10. Wetland Pool G	8 \pm 16	23	0–65
11. Reach b/w NoT & WA	6 \pm 8	4	0–17
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	3 \pm 6	9	0–15
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	10 \pm 12	17	0–30
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	1 \pm 2	18	0–7
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	15 \pm 19	21	0–70
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	18 \pm 15	23	0–75
17. East Ditch	40 \pm 75	27	0–400
18. Ditch Extension	4 \pm 8	4	0–15
19. St. Joseph River	42 \pm 15	15	0–55
20. Reach b/w NWT & Int. w/ RANWT	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
21. Reach b/w NET & Int. w/ RANWT	0 \pm NA	1	0–0

Figure A8.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table A8.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	32 \pm 68	33	0–400
Spring	13 \pm 18	107	0–60
Summer	13 \pm 17	150	0–70
Fall	9 \pm 15	141	0–60

Surface Water Chemistry

Table A8.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. North Tile	0.025 \pm 0	13 (4)	0–0.07	0.074 \pm 0.1	13 (3)	0–0.22
02. Northwest Tile	0.429 \pm 0.5	21 (0)	0.03–1.4	0.628 \pm 0.7	20 (0)	0.03–2.69
03. Northeast Tile	0.324 \pm 0.6	18 (0)	0.02–2.15	0.419 \pm 0.6	18 (0)	0.04–2.24
04. Wetland Pool A	0.013 \pm 0	11 (7)	0–0.05	0.098 \pm 0.1	11 (1)	0–0.26
05. Wetland Pool B	0.029 \pm 0.1	60 (29)	0–0.33	0.209 \pm 0.3	58 (2)	0–2.39
06. Wetland Pool C	0.085 \pm 0.1	17 (4)	0–0.31	0.221 \pm 0.1	17 (0)	0.06–0.49
07. Wetland Pool D	0.015 \pm 0	4 (2)	0–0.05	0.209 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.12–0.31
08. Wetland Pool E	0.079 \pm 0.1	9 (3)	0–0.18	0.255 \pm 0.1	9 (0)	0.07–0.42
09. Wetland Pool F	0.018 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.02	0.164 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.14–0.19
10. Wetland Pool G	0.04 \pm 0.1	7 (4)	0–0.11	0.177 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.04–0.38
11. Reach b/w NoT & WA	0.019 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.04	0.04 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.03–0.05
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	0.037 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.06	0.188 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.1–0.28

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	0.061 ± 0.1	14 (4)	0–0.22	0.115 ± 0.1	14 (0)	0.02–0.27
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.04 ± NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	0.019 ± 0	12 (6)	0–0.09	0.171 ± 0.2	11 (0)	0.02–0.57
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	0.081 ± 0.1	18 (1)	0–0.33	0.218 ± 0.4	18 (1)	0–1.61
17. East Ditch	0.058 ± 0.2	25 (14)	0–0.9	0.12 ± 0.2	25 (3)	0–1.05
18. Ditch Extension	0.259 ± NA	1 (0)	0.26–0.26	0.53 ± NA	1 (0)	0.53–0.53
19. St. Joseph River	0.013 ± 0	12 (4)	0–0.04	0.135 ± 0.1	11 (0)	0.02–0.48
22. Existing Wetland	0.287 ± 0.4	2 (1)	0–0.57	0.486 ± 0.4	2 (0)	0.23–0.74

Table A8.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.049 \pm 0	44 (7)	0–0.18	0.176 \pm 0.1	44 (0)	0.03–0.39
Spring	0.055 \pm 0.1	43 (17)	0–0.33	0.24 \pm 0.4	44 (0)	0.02–2.39
Summer	0.113 \pm 0.3	71 (24)	0–1.4	0.283 \pm 0.4	71 (7)	0–2.18
Fall	0.129 \pm 0.3	94 (37)	0–2.15	0.208 \pm 0.4	88 (3)	0–2.69

Figure A8.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table A8.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. North Tile	3.329 \pm 2.6	13 (1)	0–8.88	0.015 \pm 0	13 (9)	0–0.07	4.213 \pm 3.1	13 (3)	0–9.58
02. Northwest Tile	3.812 \pm 2.2	21 (0)	0.44–8.57	2.792 \pm 3.7	21 (1)	0–10.17	8.74 \pm 4.7	20 (0)	3.87–21.79
03. Northeast Tile	3.379 \pm 2.3	18 (0)	0.59–10.35	0.759 \pm 1.6	18 (5)	0–6.28	5.398 \pm 3.4	18 (0)	2.03–15.63
04. Wetland Pool A	1.127 \pm 2.4	11 (5)	0–7.07	0.006 \pm 0	11 (8)	0–0.03	2.324 \pm 2.6	11 (1)	0–8.66
05. Wetland Pool B	0.42 \pm 0.7	60 (28)	0–2.59	0.037 \pm 0.1	60 (38)	0–0.64	1.925 \pm 1.9	58 (0)	0.47–13.97
06. Wetland Pool C	1.729 \pm 2.3	17 (3)	0–7.33	0.038 \pm 0	17 (8)	0–0.1	3.604 \pm 2.1	17 (0)	0.94–7.19
07. Wetland Pool D	0.155 \pm 0.2	4 (1)	0–0.4	0.08 \pm 0.2	4 (3)	0–0.32	0.752 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.64–0.9
08. Wetland Pool E	0.126 \pm 0.2	9 (3)	0–0.44	0.01 \pm 0	9 (6)	0–0.04	1.315 \pm 0.5	9 (0)	0.87–2.53
09. Wetland Pool F	0.29 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	0.05–0.53	0.009 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.02	0.974 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0.83–1.12
10. Wetland Pool G	1.154 \pm 1.5	7 (2)	0–3.48	0.05 \pm 0.1	7 (3)	0–0.18	1.992 \pm 1.5	7 (0)	0.55–4.47

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
11. Reach b/w NoT & WA	4.718 ± 4.5	3 (1)	0–8.88	0.038 ± 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.05	7.056 ± 5.9	3 (0)	0.38–11.42
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	0.457 ± 0.6	2 (1)	0–0.91	0.15 ± 0.2	2 (1)	0–0.3	1.289 ± 0.8	2 (0)	0.73–1.85
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	3.078 ± 2.7	14 (0)	0.05–9.08	0.35 ± 1	14 (7)	0–3.83	4.399 ± 2.8	14 (0)	0.7–9.13
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	0.098 ± NA	1 (0)	0.1–0.1	0.077 ± NA	1 (0)	0.08–0.08	0.59 ± NA	1 (0)	0.59–0.59
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	0.461 ± 0.8	12 (6)	0–2.17	0.048 ± 0.1	12 (8)	0–0.36	1.462 ± 1.2	11 (0)	0.24–3.39
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	1.512 ± 1.4	18 (2)	0–4.54	0.038 ± 0.1	18 (12)	0–0.34	2.303 ± 1.5	18 (1)	0–5.48
17. East Ditch	0.601 ± 1	25 (8)	0–3.3	0.123 ± 0.1	25 (5)	0–0.55	1.289 ± 1.4	25 (0)	0.25–4.81
18. Ditch Extension	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	2.132 ± NA	1 (0)	2.13–2.13
19. St. Joseph River	0.632 ± 0.7	12 (1)	0–2.13	0.04 ± 0.1	12 (8)	0–0.34	1.385 ± 1	11 (0)	0.35–3.29
22. Existing Wetland	0.029 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.017 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.03	1.563 ± 0	2 (0)	1.54–1.59

Table A8.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	2.812 \pm 2.1	44 (1)	0–9.08	0.05 \pm 0.1	44 (27)	0–0.35	3.543 \pm 2.1	44 (0)	0.33–9.13
Spring	1.499 \pm 1.8	43 (10)	0–5.79	0.084 \pm 0.2	43 (13)	0–0.96	3.518 \pm 3	44 (0)	0.59–13.97
Summer	0.924 \pm 1.4	71 (23)	0–5.78	0.623 \pm 2.1	71 (39)	0–10.17	3.029 \pm 3.5	71 (5)	0–16.78
Fall	1.292 \pm 2.4	94 (30)	0–10.35	0.387 \pm 1.3	94 (46)	0–8	2.573 \pm 3.5	88 (0)	0.24–21.79

Soil Characteristics

Table A8.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. North Tile	7.144 \pm 0.5	5	6.44–7.55	NA	NA	NA	504.2 \pm 607.7	4	83.2–1404
02. Northwest Tile	7.382 \pm 0.4	5	6.75–7.91	NA	NA	NA	764.35 \pm 1085	4	45.4–2380
03. Northeast Tile	7.383 \pm 0.3	4	6.92–7.62	NA	NA	NA	1248 \pm 961.8	3	578–2350
04. Wetland Pool A	6.737 \pm 0.7	7	5.34–7.48	NA	NA	NA	162 \pm 145.1	5	26.9–349
05. Wetland Pool B	6.976 \pm 0.5	19	6.03–7.68	5804.5 \pm 3445.7	2	3368–8241	1060.757 \pm 2847.8	15	20.35–11160
06. Wetland Pool C	6.518 \pm 0.7	16	4.5–7.47	12204 \pm 813.2	2	11629–12779	106.955 \pm 172.6	11	16.01–609
07. Wetland Pool D	5.88 \pm 0.9	5	4.65–7.08	NA	NA	NA	275.72 \pm 246.2	3	14.16–503
08. Wetland Pool E	6.693 \pm 0.4	5	6.04–7.21	7119 \pm NA	1	7119–7119	246.333 \pm 190.4	3	49–429
09. Wetland Pool F	6.169 \pm 0.7	4	5.53–6.9	NA	NA	NA	308.5 \pm 81.3	2	251–366
10. Wetland Pool G	6.73 \pm 0.6	6	5.9–7.5	7116 \pm NA	1	7116–7116	289.2 \pm 205.9	3	69.6–478

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (µS/cm)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	7.08 ± NA	1	7.08–7.08	NA	NA	NA	304 ± NA	1	304–304
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	7.2 ± 0.4	5	6.77–7.61	NA	NA	NA	550.425 ± 679.3	4	31.4–1542
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	6.437 ± 0.9	6	5.43–7.72	NA	NA	NA	592 ± 70.7	2	542–642
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	7.132 ± 0.4	6	6.6–7.45	4953.5 ± 4060.9	2	2082–7825	606.25 ± 665.5	4	27–1526
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	7.132 ± 0.3	6	6.78–7.55	NA	NA	NA	1480.65 ± 2148.9	4	50.6–4680
17. East Ditch	7.056 ± 0.5	8	6.32–7.91	5793 ± 1352	2	4837–6749	501.8 ± 222.6	5	238–739
18. Ditch Extension	6.993 ± 0.7	3	6.24–7.48	3300 ± NA	1	3300–3300	440.8 ± 512.2	2	78.6–803
19. St. Joseph River	7.512 ± 0.1	3	7.45–7.55	NA	NA	NA	877.333 ± 671.4	3	241–1579

Table A8.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	7.057 \pm 0.5	52	5.61–7.91	NA	NA	NA	835.459 \pm 1675.6	52	16.01–11160
Summer	6.214 \pm 0.6	36	4.5–6.92	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fall	7.333 \pm 0.3	26	5.91–7.68	6822.273 \pm 3354.6	11	2082–12779	168.572 \pm 157.2	26	14.16–578

Table A8.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. North Tile	12.14 \pm 9.4	5	1.5–21.3	182.46 \pm 214.6	5	30–560	509.88 \pm 218	5	177.7–750.8	56.4 \pm 21.3	5	21–79
02. Northwest Tile	43.86 \pm 18.2	5	27.9–72.5	406.04 \pm 265.3	5	125.2–756.4	386.4 \pm 271.1	5	22.9–658	25.4 \pm 23.5	5	0–47
03. Northeast Tile	30.275 \pm 16.2	4	14.6–51.6	743.8 \pm 646	4	163.1–1639.1	347.35 \pm 241.5	4	41.3–579	51 \pm 27.8	4	19–81
04. Wetland Pool A	33.112 \pm 25	8	5.8–77.8	179.713 \pm 81.2	8	29.4–318.9	546.325 \pm 204.3	8	112.8–767.5	40.875 \pm 28	8	0–75
05. Wetland Pool B	52.737 \pm 36	16	10–128.6	731.038 \pm 507.3	16	221.9–1821.5	583.438 \pm 120.6	16	316.6–753.1	57.188 \pm 41.5	16	0–143
06. Wetland Pool C	42.578 \pm 21.5	16	11.8–80	212.159 \pm 139.7	16	88–529.3	585.908 \pm 140.7	16	173.82–827	36.312 \pm 23.7	16	3–71
07. Wetland Pool D	20.933 \pm 5.7	3	17.2–27.5	124.5 \pm 9.2	3	113.9–129.9	820.933 \pm 128.3	3	684.6–939.2	80.667 \pm 10.2	3	69–88
08. Wetland Pool E	19.975 \pm 6.8	4	11.9–25.8	270.225 \pm 124	4	91–375.2	568.475 \pm 116.4	4	423.9–706.8	60.25 \pm 11.1	4	50–76
09. Wetland Pool F	12.55 \pm 4.6	2	9.3–15.8	128.35 \pm 12.4	2	119.6–137.1	756.5 \pm 15.1	2	745.8–767.2	81 \pm 7.1	2	76–86
10. Wetland Pool G	16.68 \pm 14.8	5	4.9–41.5	161.52 \pm 42.8	5	128–226.1	530.28 \pm 118.4	5	412.3–695	53.2 \pm 17.3	5	29–74

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	22.4 ± NA	1	22.4–22.4	144.1 ± NA	1	144.1–144.1	700.8 ± NA	1	700.8–700.8	66 ± NA	1	66–66
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	36.42 ± 19.3	5	15.5–59.6	404.4 ± 222	5	158.7–759.7	748.38 ± 228	5	509–1119.9	72 ± 37.4	5	29–126
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	12.9 ± 12.4	2	4.1–21.7	127.35 ± 84.1	2	67.9–186.8	510.1 ± 265.9	2	322.1–698.1	53 ± 22.6	2	37–69
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	24.65 ± 13.4	4	6.3–36.2	377.075 ± 216.6	4	115–634	514.975 ± 178.4	4	247.6–613.3	55.25 ± 28.1	4	16–81
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	58.925 ± 40.1	4	21.7–108.9	1055.1 ± 949.4	4	213.7–2041.5	400.05 ± 377.4	4	47–732	48.5 ± 44.2	4	0–93
17. East Ditch	32.76 ± 39.7	5	4.1–95.3	780.5 ± 782.9	5	103.4–1675.4	452 ± 100.4	5	296.7–541.2	62.4 ± 7.2	5	53–73
18. Ditch Extension	10.1 ± 4.8	2	6.7–13.5	263.95 ± 151.1	2	157.1–370.8	678.35 ± 106.3	2	603.2–753.5	82 ± 25.5	2	64–100
19. St. Joseph River	34.7 ± 14.9	3	17.7–45.4	568.633 ± 119.9	3	440.3–677.8	108.6 ± 81.3	3	39–197.9	10 ± 12.5	3	0–24

Table A8.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	36.062 \pm 28.2	52	1.5–128.6	419.798 \pm 433.5	52	29.4–2041.5	560.846 \pm 209.3	52	88.9–1119.9	52.769 \pm 34.3	52	0–143
Summer	32.616 \pm 21.4	16	3.2–77.8	201.084 \pm 133.4	16	75–541	534.426 \pm 137.3	16	173.82–827	40.562 \pm 20	16	0–71
Fall	34.535 \pm 27.6	26	5.8–114.4	546.315 \pm 543.5	26	115–1694.1	507.796 \pm 247.1	26	22.9–939.2	54.115 \pm 27.3	26	0–112

Figure A8.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table A8.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. North Tile	0.28 \pm 0.3	4	0–0.63	1.703 \pm 2.2	4	0–4.62	1.634 \pm 2.4	4	0–5.07	715 \pm 449	4	165–1194	466.5 \pm 188.7	4	194–609
02. Northwest Tile	1.958 \pm 1.6	4	0.57–4.08	5.409 \pm 7.4	4	0–16.24	0.494 \pm 0.7	4	0–1.39	1168.5 \pm 570.5	4	720–1959	440.75 \pm 110.8	4	289–537
03. Northeast Tile	0.855 \pm 0.8	3	0–1.55	16.3 \pm 7.2	3	8.3–22.2	2.899 \pm 5	3	0–8.7	1020.333 \pm 396.3	3	567–1301	621.667 \pm 31.2	3	595–656
04. Wetland Pool A	2.136 \pm 3	5	0–7.46	3.885 \pm 3.4	5	0–7.87	0.629 \pm 0.9	5	0–1.71	780.125 \pm 369.6	8	251–1433	469.375 \pm 214.4	8	159–885
05. Wetland Pool B	1.548 \pm 3.2	15	0–12.38	40.018 \pm 91.5	15	3.29–368.1	9.84 \pm 21	15	0–81.33	1509.438 \pm 611.7	16	434–2486	673.812 \pm 272.7	16	249–1086
06. Wetland Pool C	0.762 \pm 1	11	0–2.79	9.542 \pm 4.7	11	5.86–20.18	0 \pm 0	11	0–0	867 \pm 333.2	20	214–1465	424 \pm 139.7	20	224–876
07. Wetland Pool D	0.117 \pm 0.2	3	0–0.35	7.418 \pm 4.6	3	3.68–12.51	4.803 \pm 7.3	3	0–13.23	829.333 \pm 178.3	3	689–1030	389 \pm 30.4	3	362–422
08. Wetland Pool E	2.024 \pm 1.4	3	0.59–3.28	11.584 \pm 3	3	9.64–15.07	0.794 \pm 1	3	0–1.85	1602.5 \pm 1239.4	4	664–3426	612.5 \pm 354.1	4	379–1140
09. Wetland Pool F	0.509 \pm 0.3	2	0.29–0.73	11.367 \pm 5.3	2	7.65–15.08	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	1365 \pm 42.4	2	1335–1395	503.5 \pm 12	2	495–512
10. Wetland Pool G	0.617 \pm 0.6	3	0–1.08	8.358 \pm 2.4	3	5.55–9.87	0.759 \pm 0.7	3	0–1.17	1186.333 \pm 681.4	6	411–2454	513.5 \pm 146.7	6	299–699

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	3.338 ± NA	1	3.34–3.34	4.849 ± NA	1	4.85–4.85	0 ± NA	1	0–0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	3.29 ± 1.4	4	1.55–5.01	16.707 ± 18.8	4	0–43.31	0 ± 0	4	0–0	597.75 ± 424.9	4	233–1204	351.25 ± 35.5	4	321–392
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	0.499 ± 0.1	2	0.44–0.56	7.162 ± 5.6	2	3.22–11.1	0.448 ± 0.6	2	0–0.9	840 ± 831.6	4	108–1730	351.5 ± 306.2	4	87–643
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	1.266 ± 1.3	4	0–2.9	11.56 ± 7.6	4	2.23–20.75	0 ± 0	4	0–0	1519.75 ± 1041.2	4	560–2936	665.75 ± 387.2	4	376–1230
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	3.474 ± 4.7	4	0–10.21	22.547 ± 13.3	4	6.89–35.58	2.851 ± 5.7	4	0–11.4	1084.25 ± 681.2	4	457–1980	550.75 ± 250.6	4	280–876
17. East Ditch	0.484 ± 0.5	5	0–1.3	19.713 ± 29.1	5	0–71.11	7.182 ± 16.1	5	0–35.91	1873.6 ± 1196.6	5	662–3717	687.2 ± 408.6	5	358–1265
18. Ditch Extension	0.402 ± 0.6	2	0–0.8	7.367 ± 0.9	2	6.75–7.98	0 ± 0	2	0–0	2314 ± 717	2	1807–2821	599 ± 70.7	2	549–649
19. St. Joseph River	2.103 ± 1.8	3	0–3.45	9.334 ± 8	3	4.64–18.6	0.759 ± 0.2	3	0.62–0.96	350 ± NA	1	350–350	334 ± NA	1	334–334

Table A8.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	1.659 \pm 2.4	52	0–12.38	18.21 \pm 50.1	52	0–368.1	2.685 \pm 11.7	52	0–81.33	1057 \pm 486.6	16	434–1865	481.625 \pm 239	16	224–973
Summer	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1098.731 \pm 664.2	52	108–3426	501.731 \pm 207.9	52	87–1140
Fall	0.877 \pm 1.3	26	0–5.01	12.447 \pm 16.8	26	0–71.11	3.764 \pm 7.9	26	0–35.91	1290 \pm 875.7	26	251–3717	579.385 \pm 288.5	26	159–1265

Appendix B

Non-focal Projects

Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection (DARR)

Sampling Locations

Table B1.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project.

Location Code	Location Description
DARR_01	Creek Outlet
DARR_02	Pool 1 WCS1
DARR_03	Creek WCS1
DARR_04	Pool 1 Center
DARR_05	Pool 1 WCS2
DARR_06	Ditch WCS2
DARR_07	Pool 4 WCS3
DARR_08	Ditch WCS3
DARR_09	Pool 4 Center

Sampling Locations

- 01. Creek Outlet
- 02. Pool 1 WCS1
- 03. Creek WCS1
- 04. Pool 1 Center
- 05. Pool 1 WCS2
- 06. Ditch WCS2
- 07. Pool 4 WCS3
- 08. Ditch WCS3
- 09. Pool 4 Center

Figure B1.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B1.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Creek Outlet	29 \pm 5	14	20–36
02. Pool 1 WCS1	36 \pm 18	20	15–104
03. Creek WCS1	29 \pm 11	16	15–62
04. Pool 1 Center	26 \pm 37	2	0–52
05. Pool 1 WCS2	36 \pm 19	18	3–92
06. Ditch WCS2	40 \pm 12	10	29–69
07. Pool 4 WCS3	36 \pm 16	20	15–81
08. Ditch WCS3	27 \pm 8	12	16–40
09. Pool 4 Center	52 \pm NA	1	52–52

Figure B1.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B1.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	49 \pm 33	4	3–81
Spring	30 \pm 10	29	15–52
Summer	37 \pm 15	57	15–104
Fall	26 \pm 11	23	0–55

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B1.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Creek Outlet	0.008 \pm 0	13 (0)	0–0.02	0.064 \pm 0	13 (0)	0.02–0.14
02. Pool 1 WCS1	0.025 \pm 0	16 (0)	0–0.13	0.111 \pm 0.1	16 (0)	0.04–0.26
03. Creek WCS1	0.009 \pm 0	14 (0)	0–0.02	0.085 \pm 0	14 (0)	0.04–0.15
04. Pool 1 Center	0.012 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.02	0.102 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.06–0.17
05. Pool 1 WCS2	0.055 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0–0.25	0.126 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0.04–0.35
06. Ditch WCS2	0.023 \pm 0	12 (1)	0–0.11	0.118 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0.02–0.52
07. Pool 4 WCS3	0.022 \pm 0	17 (0)	0–0.16	0.105 \pm 0.1	17 (0)	0–0.4
08. Ditch WCS3	0.048 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0–0.36	0.17 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0.02–0.45
09. Pool 4 Center	0.004 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.01	0.053 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.04–0.07

Table B1.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.042 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.01–0.2	0.15 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.07–0.3
Spring	0.029 \pm 0.1	33 (1)	0–0.25	0.088 \pm 0.1	33 (0)	0.04–0.35
Summer	0.024 \pm 0	43 (0)	0–0.11	0.133 \pm 0.1	43 (0)	0.03–0.52
Fall	0.022 \pm 0.1	22 (0)	0–0.36	0.079 \pm 0.1	22 (0)	0–0.45

Figure B1.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B1.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Creek Outlet	0.458 \pm 0.6	13 (0)	0.03–2.2	0.097 \pm 0.1	13 (0)	0.01–0.26	1.012 \pm 0.5	13 (0)	0.3–2.09
02. Pool 1 WCS1	0.04 \pm 0	16 (0)	0–0.09	0.046 \pm 0	16 (0)	0.02–0.1	1.124 \pm 0.5	16 (0)	0.42–1.85
03. Creek WCS1	0.383 \pm 0.4	14 (0)	0.01–1.58	0.079 \pm 0	14 (0)	0–0.13	1.146 \pm 0.4	14 (0)	0.57–2.01
04. Pool 1 Center	0.056 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.1	0.029 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.04	1.365 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	1.04–1.71
05. Pool 1 WCS2	0.037 \pm 0	14 (0)	0–0.1	0.072 \pm 0.1	14 (1)	0–0.46	0.932 \pm 0.3	14 (0)	0.48–1.27
06. Ditch WCS2	0.056 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0–0.26	0.085 \pm 0.2	12 (0)	0.02–0.63	0.936 \pm 0.4	12 (0)	0.4–2.04
07. Pool 4 WCS3	0.051 \pm 0.1	17 (0)	0–0.31	0.039 \pm 0	17 (0)	0.02–0.11	1.182 \pm 0.9	17 (0)	0–3.62
08. Ditch WCS3	0.048 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0–0.22	0.047 \pm 0.1	14 (1)	0–0.24	1.318 \pm 0.6	14 (0)	0.52–2.69
09. Pool 4 Center	0.033 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.05	0.019 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	0.747 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.65–0.83

Table B1.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.154 \pm 0.3	8 (0)	0.05–0.78	0.016 \pm 0	8 (2)	0–0.04	1.165 \pm 0.4	8 (0)	0.68–1.71
Spring	0.274 \pm 0.5	33 (0)	0–2.2	0.042 \pm 0	33 (0)	0.01–0.13	1.111 \pm 0.4	33 (0)	0.64–2.09
Summer	0.095 \pm 0.1	43 (0)	0–0.59	0.077 \pm 0.1	43 (0)	0.03–0.63	1.238 \pm 0.7	43 (0)	0.42–3.62
Fall	0.026 \pm 0	22 (0)	0–0.07	0.08 \pm 0.1	22 (0)	0.01–0.46	0.779 \pm 0.4	22 (0)	0–1.47

Soil Characteristics

Table B1.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Pool 1 WCS1	7.55 \pm 0.3	4	7.3–7.8	39554 \pm NA	1	39554–39554	3236.25 \pm 1750.8	4	1949–5690
03. Creek WCS1	7.6 \pm 0.2	4	7.4–7.8	44516 \pm NA	1	44516–44516	1930.667 \pm 467.3	3	1647–2470
05. Pool 1 WCS2	7.45 \pm 0.5	4	6.7–7.8	22079 \pm NA	1	22079–22079	1868 \pm 613.1	4	1335–2730
07. Pool 4 WCS3	7.425 \pm 0.3	4	7–7.8	38924 \pm NA	1	38924–38924	1916.333 \pm 862.2	3	999–2710

Table B1.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	7.425 \pm 0.1	4	7.3–7.6	36268.25 \pm 9784.5	4	22079–44516	2425.5 \pm 1236.7	2	1551–3300
Spring	7.7 \pm 0.1	4	7.5–7.8	NA	NA	NA	1962.75 \pm 468.8	4	1335–2470
Summer	7.1 \pm 0.3	4	6.7–7.4	NA	NA	NA	2259 \pm 546.5	4	1647–2730
Fall	7.8 \pm 0	4	7.8–7.8	NA	NA	NA	2555 \pm 2122.3	4	999–5690

Table B1.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Pool 1 WCS1	2.825 \pm 3.9	4	0.2–8.6	453 \pm 138.9	4	261–560	6 \pm 10.7	4	0–22	23 \pm 6.4	4	14–29
03. Creek WCS1	7.15 \pm 7.7	4	1.3–18.5	474 \pm 226.4	4	169–705	11 \pm 11	4	0–24	20.25 \pm 12.6	4	8–37
05. Pool 1 WCS2	21.375 \pm 32.8	4	3–70.4	1231.5 \pm 1534.6	4	255–3501	206.25 \pm 355.4	4	10–739	70.25 \pm 92.6	4	12–208
07. Pool 4 WCS3	9.125 \pm 7.4	4	1.8–19	666.75 \pm 722.3	4	113–1678	30.25 \pm 20.8	4	15–61	31.25 \pm 35.1	4	6–81

Table B1.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	6.9 \pm 8.1	4	0.2–18.5	379.25 \pm 160.2	4	182–559	19.75 \pm 15.8	4	1–39	16.25 \pm 7.4	4	7–24
Spring	3.65 \pm 4.3	4	0.4–9.9	344.75 \pm 236.6	4	169–694	8 \pm 10.5	4	0–22	16.25 \pm 10.1	4	8–31
Summer	25.7 \pm 30.4	4	4.8–70.4	1611 \pm 1354.3	4	560–3501	211.5 \pm 352.1	4	22–739	87.75 \pm 83.7	4	25–208
Fall	4.225 \pm 3.3	4	1.8–9	490.25 \pm 297.5	4	113–835	14.25 \pm 16.3	4	1–37	24.5 \pm 14.6	4	6–41

Figure B1.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B1.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)		TP (mg P/kg)			
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. Pool 1 WCS1	0.414 \pm 0.8	4	0–1.66	3.942 \pm 2.5	4	1.66–7.44	4.983 \pm 1.5	4	4.15–7.19	1003 \pm 480.5	4	442–1492	379.25 \pm 64.7	4	317–469
03. Creek WCS1	0.299 \pm 0.3	4	0–0.77	6.074 \pm 7.5	4	0–16.96	7.742 \pm 4.8	4	1.24–12.37	661.5 \pm 142.4	4	509–843	378.75 \pm 48.5	4	324–422
05. Pool 1 WCS2	0.858 \pm 1.4	4	0–2.86	4.854 \pm 3.7	4	0–8.1	10.503 \pm 14.8	4	1.23–32.23	933.75 \pm 422.2	4	544–1508	367.5 \pm 101.5	4	221–454
07. Pool 4 WCS3	1.168 \pm 0.1	4	1.04–1.29	5.419 \pm 4.9	4	0–11.18	6.4 \pm 8.9	4	0–19.36	1024.25 \pm 601.1	4	202–1643	462.5 \pm 14.4	4	442–475

Table B1.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	1.052 \pm 1.3	4	0–2.86	5.318 \pm 2.5	4	2.95–7.5	3.9 \pm 4.6	4	0–10.22	835.5 \pm 251	4	509–1079	409.75 \pm 51.6	4	354–475
Spring	0.261 \pm 0.5	4	0–1.04	10.92 \pm 4.3	4	7.44–16.96	2.03 \pm 1.4	4	1.24–4.17	1082.5 \pm 486.1	4	544–1643	396.75 \pm 73.4	4	317–464
Summer	1.07 \pm 0.5	4	0.57–1.66	0.414 \pm 0.8	4	0–1.66	17.789 \pm 10.8	4	7.19–32.23	1193.5 \pm 424.1	4	601–1508	370.75 \pm 121	4	221–469
Fall	0.356 \pm 0.5	4	0–1.07	3.638 \pm 0.6	4	3–4.38	5.908 \pm 1.5	4	4.42–7.3	511 \pm 239.3	4	202–707	410.75 \pm 26.9	4	377–442

Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve (FRUW)

Sampling Locations

Table B2.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project.

Location Code	Location Description
FRUW_01	Pond 1A
FRUW_02	Pond 1B
FRUW_03	Pond 1C
FRUW_04	Pond 1D
FRUW_05	Pond 2
FRUW_06	Pond 3A
FRUW_07	Pond 3B
FRUW_08	Pond 4
FRUW_09	Vernal Pool A
FRUW_10	Wooded Swale Inflow
FRUW_11	Wooded Swale Outflow

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Pond 1 A
 - 02. Pond 1 B
 - 03. Pond 1 C
 - 04. Pond 1 D
 - 05. Pond 2
 - 06. Pond 3 A
 - 07. Pond 3 B
 - 08. Pond 4
 - 09. Vernal Pool A
 - 10. Wooded Swale Inflow
 - 11. Wooded Swale Outflow

Figure B2.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B2.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	21 \pm 13	9	0–48
02. Pond 1B	33 \pm 15	8	7–47
03. Pond 1C	38 \pm 10	7	26–57
04. Pond 1D	39 \pm 9	3	31–48
05. Pond 2	26 \pm 15	16	0–62
06. Pond 3A	24 \pm 12	12	0–46
07. Pond 3B	26 \pm 29	4	0–66
08. Pond 4	33 \pm 17	15	0–61
09. Vernal Pool A	22 \pm NA	1	22–22
10. Wooded Swale Inflow	0 \pm NA	1	0–0

Figure B2.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B2.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	38 \pm 16	14	12–66
Spring	28 \pm 17	27	0–62
Summer	21 \pm 17	14	0–52
Fall	26 \pm 9	21	9–48

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B2.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0.001 \pm 0	7 (2)	0–0	0.096 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.03–0.15
02. Pond 1B	0.002 \pm 0	7 (3)	0–0.01	0.072 \pm 0	7 (0)	0.03–0.12
03. Pond 1C	0.001 \pm 0	7 (4)	0–0	0.054 \pm 0	7 (0)	0.03–0.09
04. Pond 1D	0.002 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0	0.05 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.03–0.08
05. Pond 2	0.004 \pm 0	12 (3)	0–0.02	0.075 \pm 0	12 (1)	0–0.15
06. Pond 3A	0.009 \pm 0	9 (0)	0–0.05	0.107 \pm 0.1	9 (0)	0.05–0.2
07. Pond 3B	0.013 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.03	0.15 \pm 0.2	3 (1)	0–0.36
08. Pond 4	0.005 \pm 0	12 (2)	0–0.02	0.043 \pm 0	12 (2)	0–0.11
09. Vernal Pool A	0.026 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03	0.203 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.2–0.2

Table B2.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.007 \pm 0	14 (1)	0–0.05	0.103 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0.04–0.2
Spring	0.007 \pm 0	17 (6)	0–0.03	0.043 \pm 0	17 (4)	0–0.15
Summer	0.004 \pm 0	10 (0)	0–0.02	0.13 \pm 0.1	10 (0)	0.03–0.36
Fall	0.001 \pm 0	20 (8)	0–0.01	0.063 \pm 0	20 (0)	0.02–0.15

Figure B2.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B2.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0.026 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0–0.18	0.066 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.01–0.17	1.133 \pm 0.7	7 (0)	0.27–2.1
02. Pond 1B	0 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0	0.029 \pm 0	7 (1)	0–0.09	1.076 \pm 0.6	7 (0)	0.57–2.25
03. Pond 1C	0.019 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0.13	0.024 \pm 0	7 (1)	0–0.06	0.846 \pm 0.4	7 (0)	0.49–1.39
04. Pond 1D	0 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0	0.02 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.03	0.637 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.37–0.79
05. Pond 2	0 \pm 0	12 (0)	0–0	0.035 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.01–0.11	1.161 \pm 0.7	12 (1)	0–2.91
06. Pond 3A	0 \pm 0	9 (0)	0–0	0.026 \pm 0	9 (0)	0.01–0.05	1.286 \pm 0.4	9 (0)	0.78–2.08
07. Pond 3B	0 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0	0.096 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.01–0.16	0.333 \pm 0.4	3 (1)	0–0.74
08. Pond 4	0.021 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0–0.16	0.024 \pm 0	12 (1)	0–0.07	0.777 \pm 0.5	12 (2)	0–1.57
09. Vernal Pool A	1 \pm NA	1 (0)	1–1	0.046 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	2.23 \pm NA	1 (0)	2.23–2.23

Table B2.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.071 \pm 0.3	14 (0)	0–1	0.042 \pm 0	14 (2)	0–0.14	0.877 \pm 0.5	14 (0)	0.27–2.23
Spring	0.013 \pm 0	17 (0)	0–0.13	0.03 \pm 0	17 (1)	0–0.09	0.866 \pm 0.7	17 (4)	0–2.25
Summer	0.018 \pm 0.1	10 (0)	0–0.18	0.049 \pm 0	10 (0)	0.01–0.16	1.536 \pm 0.7	10 (0)	0.26–2.91
Fall	0.008 \pm 0	20 (0)	0–0.16	0.029 \pm 0	20 (0)	0.01–0.17	0.949 \pm 0.4	20 (0)	0.37–1.8

Soil Characteristics

Table B2.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	7.752 \pm NA	1	7.75–7.75	76.7 \pm NA	1	76.7–76.7
02. Pond 1B	6.252 \pm NA	1	6.25–6.25	38.9 \pm NA	1	38.9–38.9
03. Pond 1C	7.384 \pm NA	1	7.38–7.38	141.4 \pm NA	1	141.4–141.4
05. Pond 2	6.896 \pm 0.1	2	6.83–6.96	30.18 \pm 13.6	2	20.56–39.8
07. Pond 3B	6.329 \pm 0.2	3	6.22–6.53	23.683 \pm 4.6	3	20.05–28.8
08. Pond 4	7.224 \pm 0.1	3	7.14–7.39	39.3 \pm 9.1	3	30.9–49

Table B2.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	6.894 \pm 0.5	11	6.22–7.75	46.028 \pm 35.5	11	20.05–141.4

Table B2.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0.915 \pm NA	1	0.92–0.92	39.676 \pm NA	1	39.68–39.68	27.764 \pm NA	1	27.76–27.76	4.469 \pm NA	1	4.47–4.47
02. Pond 1B	18.602 \pm NA	1	18.6–18.6	487.033 \pm NA	1	487.03–487.03	665.604 \pm NA	1	665.6–665.6	84.78 \pm NA	1	84.78–84.78
03. Pond 1C	13.629 \pm NA	1	13.63–13.63	1690.52 \pm NA	1	1690.52–1690.52	783.345 \pm NA	1	783.34–783.34	169.893 \pm NA	1	169.89–169.89
05. Pond 2	3.273 \pm 0.1	2	3.19–3.35	175.441 \pm 43.6	2	144.58–206.3	360.759 \pm 8.9	2	354.47–367.05	47.859 \pm 3.3	2	45.51–50.21
07. Pond 3B	8.397 \pm 2.1	3	6.9–10.77	345.851 \pm 192.9	3	232.18–568.59	516.403 \pm 177.7	3	393.96–720.18	70.04 \pm 28.9	3	51.44–103.39
08. Pond 4	1.154 \pm 0.2	3	0.94–1.32	105.746 \pm 98	3	43.67–218.68	604.029 \pm 192.2	3	382.26–722.5	74.051 \pm 16.8	3	54.68–84.16

Table B2.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	6.213 \pm 5.9	11	0.92–18.6	356.627 \pm 474	11	39.68–1690.52	505.412 \pm 232.3	11	27.76–783.34	71.558 \pm 42.1	11	4.47–169.89

Figure B2.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B2.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
02. Pond 1B	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0.574 \pm NA	1	0.57–0.57	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
03. Pond 1C	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
05. Pond 2	1.056 \pm 0	2	1.04–1.07	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	969.56 \pm 444.3	2	655.41–1283.71	649.867 \pm 142.2	2	549.35–750.38
07. Pond 3B	0.874 \pm 0.1	3	0.74–0.96	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	0.316 \pm 0.5	3	0–0.95	1683.697 \pm 1095.5	3	781.37–2902.57	715.17 \pm 227.7	3	496.84–951.24
08. Pond 4	0.377 \pm 0.1	3	0.32–0.47	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	899.273 \pm 113.9	3	775.22–999.08	692.663 \pm 233.3	3	453.8–920.06

Table B2.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.533 \pm 0.4	11	0–1.07	0 \pm 0	11	0–0	0.138 \pm 0.3	11	0–0.95	880.73 \pm 830.8	11	0–2902.57	502.112 \pm 357.5	11	0–951.24

Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration (MERW)

Sampling Locations

Table B3.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
MERW_01	Lake Inflow Phase 1
MERW_02	Post Field Phase 1
MERW_03	Pool 1 Outflow
MERW_04	Pool 2 Outflow
MERW_05	Pool 3 Outflow
MERW_06	Lake Inflow Phase 2
MERW_07	Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2
MERW_08	Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2
MERW_09	Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Lake Inflow Phase 1
 - 02. Post Field Phase 1
 - 03. Pool 1 Outflow
 - 04. Pool 2 Outflow
 - 05. Pool 3 Outflow
 - 06. Lake Inflow Phase 2
 - 07. Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2
 - 08. Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2
 - 09. Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2

Figure B3.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B3.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Lake Inflow Phase 1	37 \pm 13	10	15–56
02. Post Field Phase 1	8 \pm 12	9	0–30
03. Pool 1 Outflow	7 \pm 6	9	0–15
04. Pool 2 Outflow	14 \pm 6	9	8–25
05. Pool 3 Outflow	19 \pm 6	9	12–29
06. Lake Inflow Phase 2	47 \pm 8	3	40–56
07. Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2	12 \pm 2	4	10–15
08. Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2	37 \pm 34	5	10–74
09. Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2	38 \pm 4	2	35–40

Figure B3.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B3.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	26 \pm 17	9	10–46
Spring	14 \pm 15	10	0–50
Summer	18 \pm 12	16	0–36
Fall	24 \pm 22	25	0–74

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B3.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Lake Inflow Phase 1	0.056 \pm 0.1	9 (2)	0–0.23	0.329 \pm 0.1	9 (0)	0.15–0.56
02. Post Field Phase 1	0.094 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0–0.24	0.345 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.11–0.57
03. Pool 1 Outflow	0.001 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0	0.098 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.05–0.14
04. Pool 2 Outflow	0.007 \pm 0	7 (5)	0–0.05	0.148 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.04–0.33
05. Pool 3 Outflow	0.003 \pm 0	7 (4)	0–0.01	0.229 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.09–0.32
06. Lake Inflow Phase 2	0.052 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.08	0.317 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.28–0.39
07. Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2	NA	NA	NA	0.139 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.03–0.23
08. Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2	0.101 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.05–0.15	0.705 \pm 0.9	4 (0)	0.06–2.04
09. Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2	NA	NA	NA	0.039 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04

Table B3.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.041 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04	0.248 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.25–0.25
Spring	0 \pm 0	8 (8)	0–0	0.146 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.04–0.27
Summer	0.059 \pm 0.1	12 (4)	0–0.24	0.329 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0.11–0.57
Fall	0.04 \pm 0	14 (1)	0–0.15	0.285 \pm 0.4	22 (0)	0.03–2.04

Figure B3.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B3.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Lake Inflow Phase 1	0.695 \pm 1.2	9 (4)	0–3.24	0.331 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.23–0.45	4.177 \pm 0.6	9 (0)	3.51–5.09
02. Post Field Phase 1	0.069 \pm 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.21	NA	NA	NA	3.686 \pm 1.5	3 (0)	2.06–4.94
03. Pool 1 Outflow	0.339 \pm 0.7	4 (1)	0–1.33	0.048 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.06	2.234 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	2.07–2.39
04. Pool 2 Outflow	0.688 \pm 1.4	8 (3)	0–3.99	0.082 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.04–0.12	2.745 \pm 0.9	8 (0)	1.69–4.53
05. Pool 3 Outflow	0.003 \pm 0	8 (6)	0–0.01	0.022 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.03	2.736 \pm 1	8 (0)	1.43–4.44
06. Lake Inflow Phase 2	0.022 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.03	NA	NA	NA	3.52 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	3.39–3.74
07. Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2	0.5 \pm 0.4	3 (0)	0.02–0.78	NA	NA	NA	2.682 \pm 0.8	3 (0)	1.82–3.39
08. Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2	0.014 \pm 0	4 (1)	0–0.02	NA	NA	NA	2.956 \pm 1.9	4 (0)	0.77–4.92
09. Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2	0.857 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.86–0.86	NA	NA	NA	2.116 \pm NA	1 (0)	2.12–2.12

Table B3.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	3.244 \pm NA	1 (0)	3.24–3.24	0.313 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.31–0.31	4.613 \pm NA	1 (0)	4.61–4.61
Spring	1.034 \pm 1.4	8 (4)	0–3.99	0.123 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.01–0.45	3.124 \pm 1.2	8 (0)	1.43–4.87
Summer	0.141 \pm 0.3	12 (9)	0–0.91	NA	NA	NA	3.514 \pm 0.9	12 (0)	2.06–5.09
Fall	0.12 \pm 0.3	22 (4)	0–0.86	NA	NA	NA	2.828 \pm 1.1	22 (0)	0.77–4.92

North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration (NORR)
Sampling Locations

Table B4.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
NORR_01	Ditch Pump
NORR_02	WCS
NORR_03	Packer Creek
NORR_04	West Pool
NORR_05	North Dike
NORR_06	East Pool
NORR_07	North Ditch
NORR_08	East Ditch
NORR_09	Center

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Ditch Pump
 - 02. WCS
 - 03. Packer Creek
 - 04. West Pool
 - 05. North Dike
 - 06. East Pool
 - 07. North Ditch
 - 08. East Ditch
 - 09. Center

Figure B4.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at North Ridge Hunt Club Wetlands Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B4.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	33 \pm 16	21	3–67
02. WCS	42 \pm 21	21	3–82
03. Packer Creek	44 \pm 13	13	20–70
04. West Pool	33 \pm 13	22	15–57
05. North Dike	27 \pm 20	19	0–55
06. East Pool	57 \pm NA	1	57–57
07. North Ditch	116 \pm 166	15	18–500
08. East Ditch	41 \pm 27	14	18–100
09. Center	79 \pm 20	16	43–105

Figure B4.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B4.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	60 \pm 107	38	15–500
Summer	46 \pm 36	61	0–200
Fall	46 \pm 26	43	3–105

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B4.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	0.076 \pm 0.1	14 (0)	0–0.49	0.228 \pm 0.3	14 (0)	0–0.86
02. WCS	0.077 \pm 0.1	15 (0)	0–0.52	0.196 \pm 0.1	15 (0)	0.03–0.56
03. Packer Creek	0.047 \pm 0	15 (0)	0.01–0.12	0.154 \pm 0.1	15 (0)	0.05–0.29
04. West Pool	0.005 \pm 0	16 (0)	0–0.02	0.03 \pm 0	16 (0)	0.02–0.07
05. North Dike	0.026 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.13	0.115 \pm 0.1	11 (0)	0.03–0.31
06. East Pool	0.013 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.034 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03
07. North Ditch	0.073 \pm 0.2	16 (0)	0–0.49	0.163 \pm 0.2	16 (0)	0.03–0.93
08. East Ditch	0.081 \pm 0.2	13 (0)	0–0.51	0.199 \pm 0.3	13 (0)	0.05–1.05
09. Center	0.002 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0	0.027 \pm 0	11 (0)	0.02–0.04

Table B4.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.056 \pm 0.1	42 (0)	0–0.49	0.142 \pm 0.2	42 (0)	0.02–0.86
Summer	0.039 \pm 0.1	47 (0)	0–0.52	0.127 \pm 0.1	47 (0)	0–0.58
Fall	0.06 \pm 0.1	23 (0)	0–0.51	0.165 \pm 0.3	23 (0)	0.02–1.05

Figure B4.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B4.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	3.732 \pm 11.9	14 (0)	0–44.78	0.19 \pm 0.4	14 (0)	0.02–1.64	5.125 \pm 12.4	14 (0)	0–47.83
02. WCS	0.756 \pm 2.4	15 (0)	0–9.24	0.105 \pm 0.1	15 (0)	0.02–0.52	2.278 \pm 2.3	15 (0)	0.83–10.4
03. Packer Creek	1.816 \pm 2.8	15 (0)	0–10.74	0.227 \pm 0.3	15 (0)	0.01–1.4	3.026 \pm 2.9	15 (0)	0.92–12.69
04. West Pool	0.038 \pm 0	16 (0)	0–0.1	0.039 \pm 0	16 (0)	0.01–0.08	0.814 \pm 0.1	16 (0)	0.52–0.95
05. North Dike	0.038 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.15	0.046 \pm 0	11 (0)	0.02–0.1	1.294 \pm 0.4	11 (0)	0.9–1.98
06. East Pool	0.093 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09	0.08 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.08–0.08	0.7 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.7–0.7
07. North Ditch	4.053 \pm 13.5	16 (0)	0–54.46	0.134 \pm 0.3	16 (0)	0.02–1.21	5.161 \pm 13.4	16 (0)	0.73–55.33
08. East Ditch	4.671 \pm 12.7	13 (0)	0.04–46.54	0.21 \pm 0.4	13 (0)	0.03–1.54	5.597 \pm 12.4	13 (0)	0.87–46.52
09. Center	0.036 \pm 0	11 (0)	0.02–0.06	0.04 \pm 0	11 (0)	0.03–0.06	0.798 \pm 0.1	11 (0)	0.56–0.93

Table B4.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	4.444 \pm 12.6	42 (0)	0–54.46	0.2 \pm 0.4	42 (0)	0.02–1.64	5.537 \pm 12.7	42 (0)	0.52–55.33
Summer	0.506 \pm 1.3	47 (0)	0–5.69	0.083 \pm 0.1	47 (0)	0.02–0.52	1.645 \pm 1.4	47 (0)	0–6.87
Fall	0.326 \pm 0.7	23 (0)	0–2.34	0.081 \pm 0.1	23 (0)	0.01–0.44	1.457 \pm 1.3	23 (0)	0.63–5.87

Soil Characteristics

Table B4.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	7.2 \pm 0.4	4	6.8–7.6	8230 \pm NA	1	8230–8230	1255.75 \pm 580.9	4	698–2072
02. WCS	7.125 \pm 0.5	4	6.7–7.7	21561 \pm NA	1	21561–21561	1553.25 \pm 501.5	4	959–2170
04. West Pool	7.3 \pm 0.4	4	6.8–7.7	NA	NA	NA	1341 \pm 678.9	4	529–2143
05. North Dike	6.5 \pm NA	1	6.5–6.5	NA	NA	NA	1026 \pm NA	1	1026–1026

Table B4.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	7.28 \pm 0.4	5	6.8–7.7	14895.5 \pm 9426.4	2	8230–21561	1690.6 \pm 419.2	5	1154–2143
Summer	6.767 \pm 0.1	3	6.7–6.8	NA	NA	NA	1132.333 \pm 902.6	3	529–2170
Fall	7.26 \pm 0.5	5	6.5–7.7	NA	NA	NA	1155.2 \pm 229.8	5	959–1546

Table B4.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	4.2 \pm 2	5	1.6–6.5	405.5 \pm 332.5	5	126–968	606.24 \pm 182.6	5	335.2–807	87.8 \pm 34.1	5	46–140
02. WCS	29.34 \pm 19.8	5	12–57	773.4 \pm 532	5	282–1636	465.6 \pm 317.6	5	107–898	67 \pm 46.3	5	16–137
04. West Pool	2.15 \pm 0.9	4	0.8–3	271.25 \pm 178.2	4	79–503	566.5 \pm 183.2	4	402–795	78 \pm 29.9	4	54–117
05. North Dike	37.2 \pm 49.2	2	2.4–72	615 \pm 656.2	2	151–1079	661.5 \pm 159.1	2	549–774	73 \pm 5.7	2	69–77

Table B4.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	9.48 \pm 8.1	5	3–22.3	414.6 \pm 117.5	5	295–585	524.4 \pm 180.7	5	210–636	73.6 \pm 21.2	5	37–90
Summer	21.433 \pm 30.9	3	0.8–57	894.333 \pm 781.1	3	79–1636	713.667 \pm 244.7	3	436–898	110.333 \pm 48.8	3	54–140
Fall	17.375 \pm 26.1	8	1.6–72	431.688 \pm 366.1	8	126–1079	523.15 \pm 239.1	8	107–795	66.625 \pm 29.8	8	16–117

Figure B4.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B4.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	2.393 \pm 2.3	4	0–5.32	11.889 \pm 10	4	0–24.36	2.46 \pm 1.2	4	1.56–4.08	584.2 \pm 190.4	5	266–722	251 \pm 67	5	181–338
02. WCS	0.962 \pm 0.9	4	0–2	8.647 \pm 4.4	4	2–11.23	10.365 \pm 13.9	4	0.76–30.85	1476.2 \pm 622	5	640–2125	553.8 \pm 125.1	5	399–687
04. West Pool	1.764 \pm 1.3	4	0.49–3.22	5.559 \pm 4.5	4	0–11	1.524 \pm 1.7	4	0–3.93	342.5 \pm 84.6	4	257–459	217.5 \pm 149	4	60–387
05. North Dike	0.939 \pm NA	1	0.94–0.94	5.776 \pm NA	1	5.78–5.78	5.264 \pm NA	1	5.26–5.26	1416.5 \pm 1249.5	2	533–2300	702 \pm 476.6	2	365–1039

Table B4.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	1.59 \pm 2.1	5	0–5.32	12.906 \pm 6.8	5	6.24–24.36	1.32 \pm 1	5	0–2.59	938.6 \pm 707.3	5	334–2125	366.8 \pm 149.4	5	205–550
Summer	1.266 \pm 0.8	3	0.49–2	0.668 \pm 1.2	3	0–2	11.856 \pm 16.5	3	0.64–30.85	782.667 \pm 902.7	3	257–1825	303 \pm 321.8	3	60–668
Fall	1.933 \pm 1.4	5	0–3.22	8.723 \pm 3.1	5	5–11.34	4.098 \pm 2.3	5	1.52–7.27	933 \pm 709.4	8	320–2300	444.375 \pm 286.2	8	131–1039

Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration (OOPR)
Sampling Locations

Table B5.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
OOPR_01	Wetland Pool 1
OOPR_02	Wetland Pool 2
OOPR_03	Wetland Pool 3
OOPR_04	Wetland Pool 4
OOPR_05	Wetland Pool 5
OOPR_06	Wetland Pool 6
OOPR_07	Wetland Pool 7
OOPR_08	Wetland Pool 8
OOPR_09	Wetland Pool 9
OOPR_10	Wetland Pool 10
OOPR_11	Wetland Pool 11
OOPR_12	Wetland Pool 12
OOPR_13	Wetland Pool 13
OOPR_14	Wetland Pool 14
OOPR_15	Wetland Pool 15

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Wetland Pool 4
- 05. Wetland Pool 5
- 06. Wetland Pool 6
- 07. Wetland Pool 7
- 08. Wetland Pool 8
- 09. Wetland Pool 9
- 10. Wetland Pool 10
- 11. Wetland Pool 11
- 12. Wetland Pool 12
- 13. Wetland Pool 13
- 14. Wetland Pool 14
- 15. Wetland Pool 15

Figure B5.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B5.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0 \pm 1	14	0–3
02. Wetland Pool 2	2 \pm 5	10	0–12
03. Wetland Pool 3	11 \pm 14	12	0–40
04. Wetland Pool 4	1 \pm 2	9	0–7
05. Wetland Pool 5	4 \pm 7	9	0–20
06. Wetland Pool 6	1 \pm 3	11	0–8
07. Wetland Pool 7	4 \pm 6	12	0–20
08. Wetland Pool 8	3 \pm 7	9	0–20
09. Wetland Pool 9	3 \pm 7	10	0–21
10. Wetland Pool 10	7 \pm 13	10	0–40
11. Wetland Pool 11	0 \pm 0	10	0–0
12. Wetland Pool 12	23 \pm 15	14	0–45
13. Wetland Pool 13	14 \pm 12	13	0–40
14. Wetland Pool 14	8 \pm 15	14	0–40
15. Wetland Pool 15	1 \pm 4	21	0–17

Figure B5.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B5.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	13 \pm 14	20	0–45
Spring	14 \pm 11	15	0–35
Summer	4 \pm 11	91	0–40
Fall	4 \pm 7	52	0–25

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B5.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.189 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.12–0.26	0.34 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.32–0.36
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.009 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.02	0.479 \pm 0.8	3 (0)	0.04–1.36
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.03 \pm 0	5 (3)	0–0.1	0.073 \pm 0.1	4 (1)	0–0.14
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.058 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.01–0.11	0.511 \pm 0.5	2 (0)	0.16–0.86
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.096 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.16	0.548 \pm 0.7	3 (0)	0.03–1.4
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.011 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.02	0.395 \pm 0.6	3 (0)	0.02–1.13
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.032 \pm 0	5 (2)	0–0.1	0.261 \pm 0.5	5 (2)	0–1.14
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.034 \pm 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.1	0.135 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.04–0.28
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.063 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.01–0.12	0.438 \pm 0.5	3 (0)	0.11–1.04
10. Wetland Pool 10	0.027 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.05	0.316 \pm 0.4	3 (0)	0.04–0.79
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.087 \pm 0.1	12 (2)	0–0.24	0.354 \pm 0.5	11 (1)	0–1.73
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.014 \pm 0	9 (7)	0–0.1	0.158 \pm 0.3	8 (1)	0–0.77

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 14	0.027 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.08	0.107 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.02–0.26
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.091 ± 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.18	0.15 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.07–0.23

Table B5.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.096 \pm 0.1	16 (2)	0–0.26	0.149 \pm 0.1	16 (0)	0.02–0.36
Spring	0.007 \pm 0	12 (10)	0–0.07	0.052 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.02–0.11
Summer	0.033 \pm 0	8 (4)	0–0.11	0.186 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.03–0.59
Fall	0.048 \pm 0.1	22 (7)	0–0.24	0.605 \pm 0.6	19 (5)	0–1.73

Figure B5.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B5.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.16 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.12–0.2	0.805 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	0.56–1.05
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.163 \pm 0.2	3 (1)	0–0.42	0.099 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.23	1.734 \pm 2.3	3 (0)	0.2–4.42
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.146 \pm 0.2	5 (1)	0–0.48	0.05 \pm 0.1	5 (3)	0–0.2	0.656 \pm 0.6	4 (0)	0.3–1.51
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.298 \pm 0.4	2 (1)	0–0.6	0.138 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0–0.28	2.442 \pm 2.6	2 (0)	0.6–4.28
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.409 \pm 0.7	3 (1)	0–1.17	0.11 \pm 0.2	3 (1)	0–0.29	3.519 \pm 3.8	3 (0)	0.67–7.86
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.606 \pm 1	3 (1)	0–1.75	0.107 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.25	2.483 \pm 3.6	3 (0)	0.29–6.63
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.549 \pm 0.7	5 (1)	0–1.72	0.048 \pm 0	5 (1)	0–0.09	4.68 \pm 9.3	5 (0)	0.37–21.3
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.054 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.09	0.099 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.26	0.789 \pm 0.7	3 (0)	0.18–1.58
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.435 \pm 0.7	3 (1)	0–1.24	0.112 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.27	3.132 \pm 4.5	3 (0)	0.41–8.3
10. Wetland Pool 10	0.212 \pm 0.3	3 (1)	0–0.57	0.378 \pm 0.5	3 (0)	0.04–0.97	11.534 \pm 18.5	3 (0)	0.49–32.92
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.229 \pm 0.2	12 (2)	0–0.58	0.052 \pm 0.1	12 (6)	0–0.36	7.07 \pm 19.3	11 (0)	0.28–65.28
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.186 \pm 0.2	9 (1)	0–0.5	0.09 \pm 0.2	9 (5)	0–0.63	0.595 \pm 0.5	8 (0)	0.2–1.51

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 14	3.153 ± 5.3	3 (0)	0.06–9.28	0.088 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.03–0.13	3.737 ± 6	3 (0)	0.22–10.63
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.03 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.054 ± 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.07	0.585 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.53–0.64

Table B5.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.587 \pm 2.3	16 (14)	0–9.28	0.155 \pm 0.1	16 (1)	0–0.29	1.197 \pm 2.6	16 (0)	0.18–10.63
Spring	0.065 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.05–0.09	0.045 \pm 0	12 (1)	0–0.07	0.535 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0.3–0.77
Summer	0.108 \pm 0	8 (0)	0.05–0.15	0.126 \pm 0.2	8 (5)	0–0.63	1.492 \pm 1	8 (0)	0.32–3.74
Fall	0.573 \pm 0.5	22 (1)	0–1.75	0.071 \pm 0.2	22 (13)	0–0.97	8.394 \pm 16.1	19 (0)	0.23–65.28

Soil Characteristics

Table B5.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	6.804 \pm NA	1	6.8–6.8	NA	NA	NA	202.8 \pm NA	1	202.8–202.8
02. Wetland Pool 2	6.252 \pm 0.5	2	5.88–6.62	NA	NA	NA	178.75 \pm 22.6	2	162.8–194.7
03. Wetland Pool 3	7.356 \pm 0.3	2	7.17–7.54	NA	NA	NA	950.5 \pm 234.1	2	785–1116
04. Wetland Pool 4	6.528 \pm NA	1	6.53–6.53	NA	NA	NA	108.4 \pm NA	1	108.4–108.4
05. Wetland Pool 5	7.126 \pm 0.8	2	6.53–7.72	NA	NA	NA	599.35 \pm 549.6	2	210.7–988
06. Wetland Pool 6	6.16 \pm 0.5	2	5.79–6.53	NA	NA	NA	195.55 \pm 1.3	2	194.6–196.5
07. Wetland Pool 7	6.528 \pm NA	1	6.53–6.53	NA	NA	NA	173.6 \pm NA	1	173.6–173.6
08. Wetland Pool 8	6.988 \pm 0	2	6.99–6.99	NA	NA	NA	165.7 \pm 57.8	2	124.8–206.6
09. Wetland Pool 9	6.344 \pm NA	1	6.34–6.34	NA	NA	NA	225 \pm NA	1	225–225
10. Wetland Pool 10	6.344 \pm NA	1	6.34–6.34	NA	NA	NA	184.7 \pm NA	1	184.7–184.7
11. Wetland Pool 11	6.252 \pm 0.1	2	6.16–6.34	9925 \pm NA	1	9925–9925	179.05 \pm 54.8	2	140.3–217.8
12. Wetland Pool 12	6.252 \pm NA	1	6.25–6.25	8123.5 \pm 2233.8	2	6544–9703	182.7 \pm NA	1	182.7–182.7
13. Wetland Pool 13	6.482 \pm 0.2	2	6.34–6.62	2444 \pm NA	1	2444–2444	115.5 \pm 43	2	85.1–145.9

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 14	6.082 \pm 0.6	5	5.55–7.17	7388 \pm NA	1	7388–7388	158.88 \pm 163.5	5	28.6–378
15. Wetland Pool 15	6.089 \pm 0.6	6	5.45–6.99	NA	NA	NA	85.853 \pm 88.1	6	12.66–220

Table B5.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	6.419 \pm 0.6	31	5.45–7.72	7200.8 \pm 3032.2	5	2444–9925	230.823 \pm 260.9	31	12.66–1116

Table B5.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	29.2 \pm NA	1	29.2–29.2	301.6 \pm NA	1	301.6–301.6	1360.7 \pm NA	1	1360.7–1360.7	144 \pm NA	1	144–144
02. Wetland Pool 2	165.193 \pm 101.4	3	92.8–281.03	350.167 \pm 221.9	3	129.8–573.6	1224.082 \pm 274	3	949.91–1497.9	31 \pm 47.8	3	0–86
03. Wetland Pool 3	174.25 \pm 12	2	165.8–182.7	509.1 \pm 172.4	2	387.2–631	1556.45 \pm 703.6	2	1058.9–2054	52.5 \pm 74.2	2	0–105
04. Wetland Pool 4	168.53 \pm 111.7	2	89.56–247.5	286.05 \pm 187	2	153.8–418.3	1025.423 \pm 130.4	2	933.2–1117.65	23.5 \pm 33.2	2	0–47
05. Wetland Pool 5	95.507 \pm 76.2	3	14.13–165.07	147.233 \pm 74.6	3	61.1–191.5	1232.48 \pm 427.8	3	754.73–1580.28	54.333 \pm 45.5	3	2–85
06. Wetland Pool 6	37.17 \pm 7	3	31.85–45.06	148.7 \pm 32.7	3	112.7–176.6	1148.609 \pm 389.8	3	698.96–1391.47	102.667 \pm 39.6	3	57–127
07. Wetland Pool 7	66.018 \pm 52.9	5	27.23–150.6	195.28 \pm 111.4	5	82.8–349.4	1139.946 \pm 125.7	5	959.3–1234.17	75.6 \pm 47.8	5	8–124
08. Wetland Pool 8	140.33 \pm 12.4	2	131.53–149.13	480.75 \pm 185	2	349.9–611.6	1247.249 \pm 273.2	2	1054.08–1440.42	29.5 \pm 29	2	9–50
09. Wetland Pool 9	152.637 \pm 57.5	3	100.01–214	253.733 \pm 148.5	3	99.4–395.6	1448.173 \pm 37.2	3	1405.82–1475.3	35.333 \pm 33.7	3	0–67
10. Wetland Pool 10	146.23 \pm 52.9	6	78.91–221.68	237.817 \pm 141.5	6	38.4–405.8	1057.16 \pm 546.7	6	95.16–1709.31	23.833 \pm 27.4	6	0–59

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
11. Wetland Pool 11	80.987 ± 72.4	3	20.46–161.2	224.567 ± 116.4	3	120.1–350	1184.751 ± 479.5	3	644.48–1559.9	67.333 ± 58.3	3	13–129
12. Wetland Pool 12	110.833 ± 16.7	4	92–131.71	264.8 ± 46.9	4	197.8–306.8	1096.158 ± 138	4	913.6–1246.62	29.75 ± 6	4	24–38
13. Wetland Pool 13	19.85 ± NA	1	19.85–19.85	101.7 ± NA	1	101.7–101.7	608.792 ± NA	1	608.79–608.79	56 ± NA	1	56–56
14. Wetland Pool 14	101.334 ± 75	6	18.13–189.7	710.843 ± 1348.2	6	65.8–3458.26	1079.11 ± 405.8	6	516.65–1473.1	64.833 ± 80.7	6	0–217
15. Wetland Pool 15	107.586 ± 93.3	7	12.04–243.78	468.58 ± 741.9	7	60.3–2126.66	1364.303 ± 448.1	7	632.3–1819.1	82.714 ± 65	7	0–178

Table B5.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	111.83 \pm 67.8	23	17.7–247.5	242.922 \pm 144.3	23	60.3–631	1328.187 \pm 297	23	846.5–2054	62.652 \pm 50.3	23	0–144
Fall	108.913 \pm 74.7	28	12.04–281.03	419.597 \pm 708.5	28	38.4–3458.26	1080.208 \pm 391.9	28	95.16–1709.31	51.786 \pm 54.4	28	0–217

Figure B5.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B5.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.324 \pm NA	1	0.32–0.32	1.095 \pm NA	1	1.09–1.09	392.5 \pm 207.2	2	246–539	350.5 \pm 94	2	284–417
02. Wetland Pool 2	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	2.289 \pm 1.8	2	1.03–3.55	625.2 \pm 754.8	5	138–1957	479 \pm 435.5	5	169–1240
03. Wetland Pool 3	2.425 \pm 2.8	2	0.47–4.38	1.868 \pm 0.4	2	1.6–2.14	712.5 \pm 441.4	4	241–1298	494.25 \pm 272.7	4	199–838
04. Wetland Pool 4	1.194 \pm NA	1	1.19–1.19	1.524 \pm NA	1	1.52–1.52	517.667 \pm 355.8	3	107–732	512 \pm 179.3	3	313–661
05. Wetland Pool 5	3.525 \pm 1.9	2	2.16–4.89	1.078 \pm 0	2	1.07–1.09	331.4 \pm 271	5	11–684	350.6 \pm 139.8	5	219–583
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.129 \pm 0.2	2	0–0.26	1.459 \pm 0.1	2	1.39–1.53	235.4 \pm 147.9	5	50–446	214.6 \pm 55.5	5	172–312
07. Wetland Pool 7	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	1.73 \pm NA	1	1.73–1.73	314.667 \pm 300.3	6	86–789	345 \pm 186.7	6	175–598
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.842 \pm 0.8	2	0.27–1.42	1.372 \pm 0.3	2	1.16–1.59	418 \pm 314.1	4	0–736	414.25 \pm 155.9	4	182–509
09. Wetland Pool 9	4.846 \pm NA	1	4.85–4.85	2.042 \pm NA	1	2.04–2.04	537.25 \pm 433.9	4	0–959	509.75 \pm 91.9	4	401–613
10. Wetland Pool 10	1.484 \pm NA	1	1.48–1.48	0.953 \pm NA	1	0.95–0.95	786.714 \pm 370.6	7	217–1239	522.286 \pm 288.3	7	352–1166
11. Wetland Pool 11	1.289 \pm 0.8	2	0.7–1.88	2.087 \pm 1.7	2	0.86–3.31	516.6 \pm 203.1	5	156–640	416.6 \pm 102.8	5	236–495

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Wetland Pool 12	0 ± NA	1	0–0	1.688 ± NA	1	1.69–1.69	176.8 ± 144.3	5	35–386	315.4 ± 114.4	5	160–425
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.467 ± 0.7	2	0–0.93	1.816 ± 1.2	2	0.99–2.64	179.25 ± 271.1	4	0–573	302 ± 221.8	4	114–621
14. Wetland Pool 14	1.807 ± 1.3	5	0–3.36	0.429 ± 0.6	5	0–1.43	528.556 ± 479.7	9	54–1586	439.556 ± 155.6	9	211–667
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.493 ± 0.7	6	0–1.56	0.557 ± 1.4	6	0–3.34	503.333 ± 482.7	9	13–1648	366.111 ± 170	9	138–578

Table B5.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	1.2 \pm 1.5	31	0–4.89	1.241 \pm 1	31	0–3.55	401.408 \pm 331.2	49	0–1298	376.041 \pm 196.7	49	114–1166
Fall	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	577.357 \pm 489.7	28	11–1957	448.214 \pm 210.7	28	160–1240

Otsego Schools, Wood County (OTSS)

Sampling Locations

Table B6.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project.

Location Code	Location Description
OTSS_01	Emergent Wetland West
OTSS_02	Tontogany Creek
OTSS_03	Emergent Wetland East
OTSS_04	Root Wad Hollow
OTSS_05	SE Hollow
OTSS_06	Vernal Pool
OTSS_07	Deadwood Hollow
OTSS_08	West Tributary
OTSS_09	Meadow
OTSS_10	Food Forest
OTSS_11	Agricultural Field
OTSS_12	Center Hollow
OTSS_13	Wet Meadow
OTSS_14	West Hollow

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Emergent Wetland West
 - 02. Tontogany Creek
 - 03. Emergent Wetland East
 - 04. Root Wad Hollow
 - 05. SE Hollow
 - 06. Vernal Pool
 - 07. Deadwood Hollow
 - 08. West Tributary
 - 09. Meadow
 - 10. Food Forest
 - 11. Agricultural Field
 - 12. Center Hollow
 - 13. Wet Meadow
 - 14. West Hollow

Figure B6.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B6.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	7 \pm 5	6	0–11
02. Tontogany Creek	13 \pm 12	9	0–30
03. Emergent Wetland East	10 \pm 7	6	0–18
04. Root Wad Hollow	16 \pm 12	5	0–30
05. SE Hollow	20 \pm 17	7	0–40
06. Vernal Pool	18 \pm 19	5	0–40
07. Deadwood Hollow	15 \pm 15	4	0–35
08. West Tributary	8 \pm NA	1	8–8
09. Meadow	0 \pm 0	2	0–0
10. Food Forest	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
11. Agricultural Field	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
12. Center Hollow	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
13. Wet Meadow	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
14. West Hollow	0 \pm NA	1	0–0

Figure B6.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B6.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	10 \pm 11	40	0–40
Fall	21 \pm 15	10	0–40

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B6.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.11 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.08–0.14
02. Tontogany Creek	0.01 \pm 0	5 (2)	0–0.02	0.128 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.02–0.28
03. Emergent Wetland East	0.024 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.07	0.255 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0.08–0.43
04. Root Wad Hollow	0.085 \pm 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.25	0.085 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.06–0.11
05. SE Hollow	0.025 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.06	0.395 \pm 0.5	2 (0)	0.05–0.74
06. Vernal Pool	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.03 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.04
07. Deadwood Hollow	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.04 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.04
08. West Tributary	0.15 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.15–0.15	0.171 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.17–0.17

Table B6.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Summer	0.011 \pm 0	17 (13)	0–0.15	0.149 \pm 0.2	16 (0)	0.02–0.74
Fall	0.081 \pm 0.1	5 (1)	0–0.25	NA	NA	NA

Figure B6.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B6.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	0.318 \pm 0.4	3 (0)	0.09–0.74	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.035 \pm 0.7	2 (0)	0.56–1.51
02. Tontogany Creek	1.176 \pm 1.2	5 (0)	0.31–3.12	0.037 \pm 0	5 (1)	0–0.1	2.258 \pm 2.1	3 (0)	0.86–4.67
03. Emergent Wetland East	0.547 \pm 0.8	3 (0)	0.06–1.5	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.555 \pm 1.4	2 (0)	0.57–2.54
04. Root Wad Hollow	0.11 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.06–0.18	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.03 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	0.8–1.26
05. SE Hollow	0.05 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.08	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	2.075 \pm 1.9	2 (0)	0.72–3.43
06. Vernal Pool	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.705 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.69–0.72
07. Deadwood Hollow	0.025 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.05	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.815 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.8–0.83
08. West Tributary	0.721 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.72–0.72	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	1.109 \pm NA	1 (0)	1.11–1.11

Table B6.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Summer	0.443 \pm 0.8	17 (4)	0–3.12	0.011 \pm 0	17 (13)	0–0.1	1.395 \pm 1.2	16 (0)	0.56–4.67
Fall	0.44 \pm 0.7	5 (0)	0.07–1.75	0 \pm 0	5 (5)	0–0	NA	NA	NA

Soil Characteristics

Table B6.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	7.419 \pm 0.6	3	6.9–8.09	642 \pm 599.5	3	186–1321
02. Tontogany Creek	8 \pm 0	2	8–8	1039.5 \pm 14.8	2	1029–1050
03. Emergent Wetland East	8.046 \pm 0.1	2	8–8.09	837 \pm 239	2	668–1006
04. Root Wad Hollow	7.908 \pm 0.1	2	7.82–8	1011.5 \pm 528.2	2	638–1385
05. SE Hollow	7.08 \pm 0	2	7.08–7.08	735 \pm 299.8	2	523–947
06. Vernal Pool	6.494 \pm 0.9	3	5.69–7.54	295.3 \pm 218.4	3	66.9–502
07. Deadwood Hollow	6.666 \pm 1	2	5.98–7.36	336.3 \pm 194.7	2	198.6–474
09. Meadow	5.25 \pm 0	2	5.25–5.25	117.85 \pm 64.4	2	72.3–163.4
10. Food Forest	7.05 \pm NA	1	7.05–7.05	196.9 \pm NA	1	196.9–196.9
11. Agricultural Field	6.81 \pm NA	1	6.81–6.81	114.1 \pm NA	1	114.1–114.1
12. Center Hollow	4.68 \pm NA	1	4.68–4.68	121.8 \pm NA	1	121.8–121.8
13. Wet Meadow	6.4 \pm NA	1	6.4–6.4	113 \pm NA	1	113–113
14. West Hollow	6.51 \pm NA	1	6.51–6.51	82.6 \pm NA	1	82.6–82.6

Table B6.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	6.917 \pm 1	23	4.68–8.09	504.113 \pm 424.5	23	66.9–1385

Table B6.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	51.5 \pm NA	1	51.5–51.5	150.5 \pm NA	1	150.5–150.5	244.7 \pm NA	1	244.7–244.7	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
06. Vernal Pool	32.5 \pm NA	1	32.5–32.5	213.7 \pm NA	1	213.7–213.7	863.7 \pm NA	1	863.7–863.7	78 \pm NA	1	78–78
09. Meadow	24.25 \pm 0.6	2	23.8–24.7	205.7 \pm 43.7	2	174.8–236.6	865.35 \pm 21.6	2	850.1–880.6	86.5 \pm 0.7	2	86–87
10. Food Forest	11.9 \pm NA	1	11.9–11.9	115.2 \pm NA	1	115.2–115.2	293.9 \pm NA	1	293.9–293.9	28 \pm NA	1	28–28
11. Agricultural Field	20.9 \pm NA	1	20.9–20.9	113.1 \pm NA	1	113.1–113.1	622.9 \pm NA	1	622.9–622.9	57 \pm NA	1	57–57
12. Center Hollow	27.3 \pm NA	1	27.3–27.3	260.6 \pm NA	1	260.6–260.6	985.5 \pm NA	1	985.5–985.5	100 \pm NA	1	100–100
13. Wet Meadow	16.8 \pm NA	1	16.8–16.8	129.8 \pm NA	1	129.8–129.8	655.9 \pm NA	1	655.9–655.9	66 \pm NA	1	66–66
14. West Hollow	24 \pm NA	1	24–24	121.7 \pm NA	1	121.7–121.7	713.4 \pm NA	1	713.4–713.4	65 \pm NA	1	65–65

Table B6.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	25.933 \pm 11.3	9	11.9–51.5	168.444 \pm 56	9	113.1–260.6	678.967 \pm 259.7	9	244.7–985.5	63 \pm 31.5	9	0–100

Figure B6.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B6.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	1.021 \pm 1.1	3	0–2.21	0.375 \pm 0.6	3	0–1.12	2722.333 \pm 4419.4	3	111–7825	345.333 \pm 203.3	3	136–542
02. Tontogany Creek	1.228 \pm 0.6	2	0.82–1.63	1.098 \pm 0.8	2	0.56–1.64	760.5 \pm 201.5	2	618–903	455 \pm 155.6	2	345–565
03. Emergent Wetland East	0.841 \pm 0.6	2	0.43–1.25	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	465.5 \pm 176.1	2	341–590	373.5 \pm 9.2	2	367–380
04. Root Wad Hollow	2.458 \pm 3.5	2	0–4.92	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	524 \pm 569.9	2	121–927	503 \pm 159.8	2	390–616
05. SE Hollow	1.926 \pm 1.6	2	0.8–3.06	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	1389.5 \pm 46	2	1357–1422	667 \pm 38.2	2	640–694
06. Vernal Pool	0.972 \pm 1.4	3	0–2.56	0.409 \pm 0.7	3	0–1.23	1321.333 \pm 979.8	3	267–2204	609.667 \pm 191.9	3	390–745
07. Deadwood Hollow	0.991 \pm 1.4	2	0–1.98	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	634 \pm 479.4	2	295–973	454.5 \pm 50.2	2	419–490
09. Meadow	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	980.5 \pm 33.2	2	957–1004	498.5 \pm 146.4	2	395–602
10. Food Forest	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	612 \pm NA	1	612–612	345 \pm NA	1	345–345
11. Agricultural Field	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	1167 \pm NA	1	1167–1167	413 \pm NA	1	413–413
12. Center Hollow	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	1537 \pm NA	1	1537–1537	614 \pm NA	1	614–614

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
13. Wet Meadow	0 ± NA	1	0–0	0 ± NA	1	0–0	1152 ± NA	1	1152–1152	448 ± NA	1	448–448
14. West Hollow	0.24 ± NA	1	0.24–0.24	0 ± NA	1	0–0	1718 ± NA	1	1718–1718	679 ± NA	1	679–679

Table B6.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.918 \pm 1.3	23	0–4.92	0.198 \pm 0.5	23	0–1.64	1209.783 \pm 1545.2	23	111–7825	489.87 \pm 152.6	23	136–745

Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections (OTTN)

Sampling Locations

Table B7.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project.

Location Code	Location Description
OTTN_01	Pool 3 Center
OTTN_02	Pool 3 Veler Ditch
OTTN_03	Pool 3 WCS
OTTN_04	MS5 Center
OTTN_05	MS5 Veler Ditch
OTTN_06	MS5 WCS
OTTN_07	Crane Creek

Sampling Locations

- 01. Pool 3 Center
- 02. Pool 3 Veler Ditch
- 03. Pool 3 WCS
- 04. MS5 Center
- 05. MS5 Veler Ditch
- 06. MS5 WCS
- 07. Crane Creek

Figure B7.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B7.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Pool 3 Center	48 \pm 24	8	0–70
02. Pool 3 Veler Ditch	33 \pm 16	14	15–78
03. Pool 3 WCS	37 \pm 14	20	15–72
04. MS5 Center	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
05. MS5 Veler Ditch	38 \pm 19	14	0–85
06. MS5 WCS	38 \pm 15	19	20–70
07. Crane Creek	58 \pm 18	11	15–75

Figure B7.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B7.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	43 \pm 17	17	23–72
Summer	42 \pm 21	40	0–85
Fall	36 \pm 16	30	0–70

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B7.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pool 3 Center	0.002 \pm 0	8 (0)	0–0.01	0.055 \pm 0	8 (0)	0.03–0.09
02. Pool 3 Veler Ditch	0.023 \pm 0	16 (0)	0–0.1	0.093 \pm 0	16 (0)	0.04–0.17
03. Pool 3 WCS	0.008 \pm 0	17 (0)	0–0.02	0.084 \pm 0	17 (0)	0.03–0.17
04. MS5 Center	0.008 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.02	0.119 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.08–0.16
05. MS5 Veler Ditch	0.025 \pm 0	15 (0)	0–0.1	0.091 \pm 0	15 (0)	0.04–0.15
06. MS5 WCS	0.011 \pm 0	16 (0)	0–0.04	0.197 \pm 0.4	16 (0)	0.03–1.6
07. Crane Creek	0.01 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.02	0.081 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.13

Table B7.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.008 \pm 0	26 (1)	0–0.02	0.084 \pm 0	26 (0)	0.03–0.16
Summer	0.023 \pm 0	35 (0)	0–0.1	0.112 \pm 0	35 (0)	0.06–0.24
Fall	0.007 \pm 0	24 (0)	0–0.03	0.122 \pm 0.3	24 (0)	0–1.6

Figure B7.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B7.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pool 3 Center	0.353 \pm 0.6	8 (0)	0–1.42	0.029 \pm 0	8 (0)	0.02–0.07	1.016 \pm 0.7	8 (0)	0.5–2.2
02. Pool 3 Veler Ditch	0.293 \pm 0.6	16 (0)	0–2.36	0.053 \pm 0	16 (0)	0.01–0.16	1.173 \pm 0.8	16 (0)	0.49–3.06
03. Pool 3 WCS	0.261 \pm 0.6	17 (0)	0.01–2.37	0.047 \pm 0	17 (0)	0–0.14	1.118 \pm 0.7	17 (0)	0.45–3.08
04. MS5 Center	1.609 \pm 0.9	2 (0)	0.95–2.27	0.045 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.07	2.494 \pm 1	2 (0)	1.81–3.18
05. MS5 Veler Ditch	0.317 \pm 0.6	15 (0)	0–2.47	0.054 \pm 0	15 (0)	0.02–0.13	1.056 \pm 0.6	15 (0)	0.52–3.1
06. MS5 WCS	0.257 \pm 0.6	16 (0)	0–2.17	0.064 \pm 0.1	16 (0)	0–0.2	1.146 \pm 0.6	16 (0)	0.72–2.86
07. Crane Creek	0.288 \pm 0.4	11 (0)	0–1.4	0.066 \pm 0.1	11 (0)	0.02–0.19	1.009 \pm 0.4	11 (0)	0.72–1.98

Table B7.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate (mg N/L)			Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	NA	NA	NA	0.837 \pm 0.9	26 (0)	0–2.47	0.049 \pm 0	26 (0)	0.02–0.16	1.684 \pm 0.9	26 (0)	0.45–3.18
Summer	0.016 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.05	0.118 \pm 0.2	35 (0)	0–0.78	0.06 \pm 0.1	35 (0)	0–0.2	1.004 \pm 0.4	35 (0)	0.67–2.42
Fall	NA	NA	NA	0.055 \pm 0.1	24 (0)	0–0.21	0.048 \pm 0	24 (0)	0.01–0.19	0.718 \pm 0.2	24 (0)	0.49–1.07

Soil Characteristics

Table B7.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
03. Pool 3 WCS	6.925 \pm 0.2	4	6.7–7.1	8144 \pm NA	1	8144–8144	1653 \pm 614.7	4	771–2154
06. MS5 WCS	7.3 \pm 0.3	4	6.9–7.6	57819 \pm NA	1	57819–57819	1438.75 \pm 391.6	4	869–1758

Table B7.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Total Carbon (mg C/kg)			Soil Conductivity (μ S/cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	7.175 \pm 0.2	4	6.9–7.4	32981.5 \pm 35125.5	2	8144–57819	1687.75 \pm 569.3	4	869–2154
Summer	6.8 \pm 0.1	2	6.7–6.9	NA	NA	NA	1624 \pm 131.5	2	1531–1717
Fall	7.3 \pm 0.4	2	7–7.6	NA	NA	NA	1184 \pm 584.1	2	771–1597

Table B7.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
03. Pool 3 WCS	15.975 \pm 10.2	4	6.6–29	916.75 \pm 757.4	4	251–1955	831.75 \pm 276.3	4	588–1140	130.25 \pm 58.1	4	75–193
06. MS5 WCS	13.5 \pm 5.6	4	9.3–21.7	454 \pm 260.8	4	148–700	456.5 \pm 188.5	4	230–639	64 \pm 23	4	34–90

Table B7.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	14.225 \pm 10.1	4	6.6–29	748.25 \pm 831.8	4	148–1955	633.75 \pm 257.1	4	376–990	100 \pm 62.1	4	66–193
Summer	20.35 \pm 1.9	2	19–21.7	843 \pm 202.2	2	700–986	889.5 \pm 354.3	2	639–1140	128 \pm 53.7	2	90–166
Fall	10.15 \pm 1.2	2	9.3–11	402 \pm 103.2	2	329–475	419.5 \pm 268	2	230–609	60.5 \pm 37.5	2	34–87

Figure B7.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B7.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
03. Pool 3 WCS	0.688 \pm 0.6	4	0–1.27	4.848 \pm 3.6	4	0–8.53	1.46 \pm 0.9	4	0.31–2.47	1170.5 \pm 315.9	4	849–1587	521.75 \pm 93.6	4	395–593
06. MS5 WCS	1.596 \pm 1.3	4	0.02–3.17	4.906 \pm 2.9	4	2.96–9.12	2.264 \pm 1.9	4	0–4.67	934.75 \pm 139.2	4	836–1138	477.5 \pm 38.5	4	438–513

Table B7.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	0.535 \pm 0.8	4	0–1.64	6.763 \pm 2.8	4	2.96–9.12	1.679 \pm 2.1	4	0–4.67	1076.25 \pm 351.3	4	836–1587	536 \pm 69.3	4	451–593
Summer	2.083 \pm 1.5	2	1–3.17	1.583 \pm 2.2	2	0–3.17	2.479 \pm 0	2	2.47–2.48	1064.5 \pm 217.1	2	911–1218	416.5 \pm 30.4	2	395–438
Fall	1.416 \pm 0.2	2	1.27–1.56	4.399 \pm 0	2	4.37–4.43	1.613 \pm 0.4	2	1.32–1.9	993.5 \pm 204.4	2	849–1138	510 \pm 4.2	2	507–513

St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection (SJCO)

Sampling Locations

Table B8.14. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project.

Location Code	Location Description
SJCO_01	Wetland Pool 1
SJCO_02	Wetland Pool 2
SJCO_03	Wetland Pool 3
SJCO_04	Oxbow Wetland
SJCO_05	St. Joseph River West Branch
SJCO_06	Wetland Pool 4
SJCO_07	Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe
SJCO_08	Wetland Pool 5
SJCO_09	Wetland Pool 5 Extension
SJCO_10	Wetland Pool 6
SJCO_11	Wetland Pool 7
SJCO_12	Wetland Pool 8
SJCO_13	St. Joseph River East Branch
SJCO_14	Unnamed tributary
SJCO_15	Oxbow off the river near pool 3
SJCO_16	St. Joseph loop tributary

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Oxbow Wetland
- 05. St Joe River West Branch
- 06. Wetland Pool 4
- 07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe
- 08. Wetland Pool 5
- 09. Wetland Pool 5 Extension
- 10. Wetland Pool 6
- 11. Wetland Pool 7
- 12. Wetland Pool 8
- 13. St Joe River East Branch
- 14. Unnamed tributary
- 15. Oxbow off the river near pool 3
- 16. St Joe loop tributary

Figure B8.5. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B8.15. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	2 \pm 5	11	0–17
02. Wetland Pool 2	0 \pm 0	8	0–0
03. Wetland Pool 3	0 \pm 0	9	0–0
04. Oxbow Wetland	1 \pm 5	11	0–15
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	25 \pm 13	9	0–40
06. Wetland Pool 4	1 \pm 4	7	0–10
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	0 \pm 0	8	0–0
08. Wetland Pool 5	1 \pm 3	9	0–10
09. Wetland Pool 5 Extension	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
10. Wetland Pool 6	0 \pm 0	9	0–0
11. Wetland Pool 7	1 \pm 2	10	0–7
12. Wetland Pool 8	0 \pm 0	9	0–0
14. Unnamed tributary	10 \pm 8	10	0–20

Figure B8.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B8.16. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	10 \pm 12	12	0–40
Summer	3 \pm 8	73	0–30
Fall	3 \pm 8	26	0–40

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B8.17. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.043 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.03–0.05
02. Wetland Pool 2	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.059 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.06–0.06
04. Oxbow Wetland	0.098 \pm 0.2	4 (2)	0–0.36	0.179 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.04–0.46
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	0.013 \pm 0	9 (5)	0–0.04	0.052 \pm 0	9 (0)	0.03–0.11
06. Wetland Pool 4	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.116 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.09–0.13
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	0.014 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.085 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09
08. Wetland Pool 5	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.038 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.02–0.06
10. Wetland Pool 6	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.05 \pm 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.1
11. Wetland Pool 7	0.006 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.02	0.061 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.04–0.08
13. St. Joseph River East Branch	0.04 \pm 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.08	0.124 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0.01–0.23
14. Unnamed tributary	0.045 \pm 0	7 (2)	0–0.09	0.216 \pm 0.2	7 (0)	0.05–0.46
16. St. Joseph loop tributary	0.018 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.04	0.364 \pm 0.4	2 (0)	0.09–0.63

Table B8.18. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.006 \pm 0	16 (14)	0–0.07	0.067 \pm 0.1	15 (0)	0.01–0.25
Summer	0.037 \pm 0	8 (2)	0–0.09	0.244 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.04–0.63
Fall	0.032 \pm 0.1	18 (11)	0–0.36	0.091 \pm 0.1	18 (1)	0–0.46

Figure B8.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B8.19. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.252 \pm 0.3	4 (1)	0–0.65	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.889 \pm 0.2	4 (0)	0.66–1
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.078 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.08–0.08	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.898 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.9–0.9
04. Oxbow Wetland	0.036 \pm 0	4 (2)	0–0.07	0.057 \pm 0.1	4 (3)	0–0.23	0.951 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.82–1.13
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	0.405 \pm 0.5	9 (3)	0–1.62	0.021 \pm 0	9 (7)	0–0.1	1.186 \pm 0.5	9 (0)	0.46–2.15
06. Wetland Pool 4	0.022 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.07	0.026 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.08	1.156 \pm 0.6	3 (0)	0.51–1.52
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	0.092 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.858 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.86–0.86
08. Wetland Pool 5	0.2 \pm 0.3	4 (1)	0–0.65	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.676 \pm 0.3	4 (0)	0.45–1.06
10. Wetland Pool 6	0.035 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.07	0.054 \pm 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.11	0.862 \pm 0.9	2 (0)	0.2–1.52
11. Wetland Pool 7	0.068 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.05–0.08	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.999 \pm 0.4	3 (0)	0.74–1.45
13. St. Joseph River East Branch	0.35 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.28–0.42	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.166 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	1.02–1.31

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Unnamed tributary	0.233 ± 0.2	7 (1)	0–0.7	0.434 ± 0.4	7 (1)	0–0.97	2.058 ± 0.7	7 (0)	1.12–3.05
16. St. Joseph loop tributary	0.046 ± 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.06	0.252 ± 0.4	2 (1)	0–0.5	2.91 ± 2.3	2 (0)	1.3–4.52

Table B8.20. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.188 \pm 0.3	16 (9)	0–0.8	0.039 \pm 0.1	16 (11)	0–0.23	1.207 \pm 0.3	15 (0)	0.45–1.58
Summer	0.233 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.04–0.7	0.238 \pm 0.3	8 (3)	0–0.63	2.01 \pm 1.3	8 (0)	0.77–4.52
Fall	0.204 \pm 0.4	18 (2)	0–1.62	0.09 \pm 0.3	18 (16)	0–0.97	1.006 \pm 0.6	18 (0)	0.2–2.57

Soil Characteristics

Table B8.21. Summarized soil characteristics at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	7.632 \pm 0.3	2	7.45–7.82	1030.5 \pm 791.3	2	471–1590
02. Wetland Pool 2	7.724 \pm NA	1	7.72–7.72	647 \pm NA	1	647–647
03. Wetland Pool 3	7.77 \pm 0.1	2	7.72–7.82	596.5 \pm 64.3	2	551–642
04. Oxbow Wetland	7.448 \pm 0.4	2	7.17–7.72	783.5 \pm 747.4	2	255–1312
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	7.908 \pm 0	2	7.91–7.91	2496 \pm 2465	2	753–4239
06. Wetland Pool 4	7.448 \pm NA	1	7.45–7.45	1345 \pm NA	1	1345–1345
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	7.724 \pm NA	1	7.72–7.72	560 \pm NA	1	560–560
08. Wetland Pool 5	7.264 \pm 0.4	2	6.99–7.54	580 \pm 1.4	2	579–581
10. Wetland Pool 6	6.758 \pm 0.3	2	6.53–6.99	478 \pm 325.3	2	248–708
11. Wetland Pool 7	6.804 \pm 0	2	6.8–6.8	463 \pm 4.2	2	460–466
12. Wetland Pool 8	7.31 \pm 0.8	2	6.71–7.91	562.5 \pm 150.6	2	456–669
14. Unnamed tributary	7.816 \pm 0	2	7.82–7.82	1148 \pm 428.5	2	845–1451

Table B8.22. Summarized soil characteristics at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	7.444 \pm 0.5	21	6.53–7.91	896.571 \pm 854.1	21	248–4239

Table B8.23. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	2.904 \pm 1.8	2	1.6–4.21	588.675 \pm 667	2	117–1060.35	281.295 \pm 120.4	2	196.19–366.4	62 \pm 21.2	2	47–77
02. Wetland Pool 2	3.415 \pm 2	2	2.03–4.8	217.123 \pm 40.1	2	188.8–245.45	562.171 \pm 41.8	2	532.6–591.74	73 \pm 8.5	2	67–79
03. Wetland Pool 3	2.8 \pm NA	1	2.8–2.8	183.4 \pm NA	1	183.4–183.4	466 \pm NA	1	466–466	61 \pm NA	1	61–61
04. Oxbow Wetland	8.613 \pm 6.4	3	4.34–16	357.646 \pm 163.7	3	206.14–531.3	447.305 \pm 291.1	3	111.2–621.2	62.333 \pm 42	3	15–95
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	20.5 \pm NA	1	20.5–20.5	1119.9 \pm NA	1	1119.9–1119.9	17.9 \pm NA	1	17.9–17.9	44 \pm NA	1	44–44
06. Wetland Pool 4	8.863 \pm 3	3	5.62–11.57	380.129 \pm 223.5	3	213.9–634.25	656.81 \pm 71.8	3	574.1–703.07	87.333 \pm 21.2	3	68–110
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	24.432 \pm 12.8	2	15.4–33.46	286.442 \pm 55.2	2	247.4–325.48	412.884 \pm 152.8	2	304.87–520.9	39 \pm 26.9	2	20–58
08. Wetland Pool 5	8.2 \pm NA	1	8.2–8.2	177.1 \pm NA	1	177.1–177.1	616.6 \pm NA	1	616.6–616.6	72 \pm NA	1	72–72
10. Wetland Pool 6	3.2 \pm NA	1	3.2–3.2	60 \pm NA	1	60–60	636.1 \pm NA	1	636.1–636.1	73 \pm NA	1	73–73
11. Wetland Pool 7	16.499 \pm 10.1	6	4.67–30.5	225.809 \pm 110	6	103.9–361.2	672.026 \pm 81.8	6	589.5–804.93	73.167 \pm 19.2	6	43–102

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Wetland Pool 8	6.419 ± 3.6	2	3.9–8.94	224.251 ± 44.5	2	192.8–255.7	291.196 ± 389.3	2	15.9–566.49	39.5 ± 43.1	2	9–70
14. Unnamed tributary	22.5 ± 4.9	2	19–26	828.9 ± 629.7	2	383.6–1274.2	203.2 ± 89.2	2	140.1–266.3	46.5 ± 50.2	2	11–82
16. St. Joseph loop tributary	4.168 ± NA	1	4.17–4.17	208.225 ± NA	1	208.22–208.22	549.056 ± NA	1	549.06–549.06	70 ± NA	1	70–70

Table B8.24. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	11.468 \pm 9.2	27	1.6–33.46	355.836 \pm 313.7	27	60–1274.2	486.357 \pm 225.1	27	15.9–804.93	64 \pm 26.2	27	9–110

Figure B8.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B8.25. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.689 \pm 0.8	3	0–1.6	6.429 \pm 3.9	3	2.53–10.3	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	1401.75 \pm 649.8	4	707–2215	500.25 \pm 264.5	4	179–814
02. Wetland Pool 2	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	1.536 \pm 2.2	2	0–3.07	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	1124.333 \pm 397.2	3	678–1439	479 \pm 124.7	3	368–614
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.097 \pm 0.2	3	0–0.29	1.385 \pm 2.4	3	0–4.15	0.18 \pm 0.3	3	0–0.54	1145.667 \pm 122.6	3	1042–1281	562.333 \pm 141.5	3	399–649
04. Oxbow Wetland	2.839 \pm 5.4	4	0–10.93	10.071 \pm 7.8	4	0–18.67	0 \pm 0	4	0–0	1627.4 \pm 978.6	5	907–3350	508.6 \pm 92.3	5	358–604
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	3.929 \pm 3	3	1.49–7.28	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	990.667 \pm 667.7	3	306–1640	491 \pm 76.2	3	432–577
06. Wetland Pool 4	1.246 \pm 1.8	2	0–2.49	10.698 \pm 9.8	2	3.8–17.6	0.368 \pm 0.5	2	0–0.74	1420 \pm 536.4	4	833–2115	507.5 \pm 137.8	4	309–607
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	0.679 \pm 0.5	2	0.33–1.03	6.142 \pm 6.6	2	1.51–10.78	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	1221.667 \pm 360.4	3	817–1508	515.333 \pm 91.4	3	410–573
08. Wetland Pool 5	0.547 \pm 0.7	3	0–1.38	6.894 \pm 3.8	3	3.87–11.18	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	1151.333 \pm 341.9	3	889–1538	420 \pm 200.8	3	251–642
10. Wetland Pool 6	0.518 \pm 0.5	3	0–0.91	5.397 \pm 7.8	3	0–14.36	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	682.333 \pm 641.5	3	265–1421	325 \pm 172.8	3	205–523
11. Wetland Pool 7	0.075 \pm 0.1	4	0–0.3	8.838 \pm 2.2	4	7.66–12.17	0 \pm 0	4	0–0	849.25 \pm 258.3	8	305–1116	346.875 \pm 115.7	8	206–535

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
12. Wetland Pool 8	0.465 ± 0.4	3	0–0.74	4.185 ± 4.3	3	1.42–9.19	0 ± 0	3	0–0	633 ± 293.4	4	254–970	350.75 ± 73.8	4	247–405
14. Unnamed tributary	1.074 ± 0.8	4	0–2.02	7.464 ± 6.4	4	2.27–16.56	0 ± 0	4	0–0	2088.75 ± 228.7	4	1798–2318	618.75 ± 82.7	4	528–698
16. St. Joseph loop tributary	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	840 ± NA	1	840–840	379 ± NA	1	379–379

Table B8.26. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.743 \pm 1.9	36	0–10.93	6.303 \pm 5.3	36	0–18.67	0.035 \pm 0.2	36	0–0.74	1185.271 \pm 604.7	48	254–3350	458 \pm 150.2	48	179–814

Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands (SPRC)
Sampling Locations

Table B9.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project.

Location Code	Location Description
SPRC_01	Spring Creek
SPRC_02	North Pool
SPRC_03	Connecting Channel
SPRC_04	South Pool
SPRC_05	Great Miami River Downstream
SPRC_06	Great Miami River Upstream
SPRC_07	Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Spring Creek
 - 02. North Pool
 - 03. Connecting Channel
 - 04. South Pool
 - 05. Great Miami River Downstream
 - 06. Great Miami River Upstream
 - 07. Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park

Figure B9.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B9.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Spring Creek	17 \pm 26	23	0–100
02. North Pool	50 \pm 19	24	15–87
03. Connecting Channel	22 \pm 27	17	0–72
04. South Pool	37 \pm 21	25	8–91
05. Great Miami River Downstream	47 \pm 20	22	4–100
06. Great Miami River Upstream	35 \pm 23	21	10–100
07. Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park	30 \pm 14	13	12–55

Figure B9.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B9.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	43 \pm 23	32	0–90
Spring	34 \pm 20	19	4–78
Summer	40 \pm 26	59	0–100
Fall	19 \pm 18	35	0–50

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B9.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Spring Creek	0.018 \pm 0	25 (10)	0–0.18	0.044 \pm 0.1	25 (8)	0–0.22
02. North Pool	0.007 \pm 0	31 (25)	0–0.17	0.03 \pm 0.1	32 (14)	0–0.37
03. Connecting Channel	0.024 \pm 0	17 (10)	0–0.18	0.055 \pm 0.1	17 (4)	0–0.36
04. South Pool	0.011 \pm 0	31 (25)	0–0.17	0.064 \pm 0.1	32 (4)	0–0.38
05. Great Miami River Downstream	0.171 \pm 0.2	32 (2)	0–0.51	0.283 \pm 0.2	32 (0)	0.04–0.75
06. Great Miami River Upstream	0.214 \pm 0.2	30 (0)	0.02–0.59	0.331 \pm 0.2	30 (0)	0.06–0.76
07. Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park	0.296 \pm 0.2	12 (0)	0.08–0.72	0.409 \pm 0.2	12 (0)	0.19–0.8

Table B9.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.057 \pm 0.1	41 (14)	0–0.18	0.146 \pm 0.1	41 (8)	0–0.38
Spring	0.042 \pm 0.1	37 (18)	0–0.2	0.092 \pm 0.1	37 (12)	0–0.38
Summer	0.166 \pm 0.2	48 (19)	0–0.72	0.245 \pm 0.3	48 (2)	0–0.8
Fall	0.096 \pm 0.2	52 (21)	0–0.51	0.144 \pm 0.2	54 (8)	0–0.58

Figure B9.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B9.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Spring Creek	3.802 \pm 1.9	25 (0)	0.45–7.23	0.005 \pm 0	18 (8)	0–0.01	4.381 \pm 2.1	25 (0)	0.96–7.9
02. North Pool	2.164 \pm 1.3	32 (1)	0–4.76	0.016 \pm 0	23 (6)	0–0.12	2.77 \pm 1.5	32 (0)	0.45–6.59
03. Connecting Channel	2.123 \pm 1	17 (0)	0.08–3.52	0.058 \pm 0.2	15 (4)	0–0.59	3.027 \pm 1.3	17 (0)	0.49–5.15
04. South Pool	0.949 \pm 0.9	32 (2)	0–3.24	0.019 \pm 0	23 (6)	0–0.13	1.94 \pm 1.2	32 (0)	0.65–5.62
05. Great Miami River Downstream	2.782 \pm 2	32 (1)	0–7.37	0.034 \pm 0	23 (3)	0–0.17	3.784 \pm 2.1	32 (0)	0.37–8.33
06. Great Miami River Upstream	2.871 \pm 2	30 (0)	0.36–7.97	0.036 \pm 0	21 (0)	0–0.09	3.811 \pm 2.3	30 (0)	1.04–9.34
07. Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park	2.387 \pm 1.9	12 (0)	0.41–5.73	0.058 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.01–0.12	3.603 \pm 2.3	12 (0)	1.24–7.92

Table B9.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	3.763 \pm 1.5	41 (0)	0.76–7.23	0.042 \pm 0	40 (3)	0–0.17	4.585 \pm 1.8	41 (0)	1.31–8.42
Spring	2.944 \pm 1.6	37 (1)	0–6.12	0.009 \pm 0	24 (1)	0–0.04	3.923 \pm 1.8	37 (0)	0.92–7.92
Summer	1.358 \pm 1.2	48 (1)	0–4.76	0.067 \pm 0.1	18 (3)	0–0.59	2.486 \pm 1.5	48 (0)	0.65–6.59
Fall	1.966 \pm 1.9	54 (2)	0–7.97	0.008 \pm 0	44 (20)	0–0.05	2.553 \pm 2	54 (0)	0.37–9.34

Soil Characteristics

Table B9.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. North Pool	7.678 \pm NA	1	7.68–7.68	150 \pm NA	1	150–150
03. Connecting Channel	7.798 \pm NA	1	7.8–7.8	124.4 \pm NA	1	124.4–124.4
04. South Pool	7.862 \pm NA	1	7.86–7.86	442 \pm NA	1	442–442

Table B9.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	7.779 \pm 0.1	3	7.68–7.86	238.8 \pm 176.4	3	124.4–442

Table B9.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. North Pool	12.874 \pm 2.2	2	11.29–14.46	322.952 \pm 26.5	2	304.19–341.72	223.546 \pm 172.9	2	101.29–345.8	30.67 \pm 16.1	2	19.26–42.08
03. Connecting Channel	13.875 \pm 18.5	2	0.81–26.94	250.534 \pm 15.5	2	239.54–261.52	266.079 \pm 376.3	2	0–532.16	30.544 \pm 23.9	2	13.67–47.42
04. South Pool	14.97 \pm 10.1	2	7.82–22.12	394.952 \pm 74.1	2	342.54–447.36	20.13 \pm 28.5	2	0–40.26	9.206 \pm 10.9	2	1.46–16.95

Table B9.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	20.115 \pm 8	3	11.29–26.94	307.933 \pm 59.2	3	239.54–342.54	224.571 \pm 268.1	3	40.26–532.16	22.715 \pm 23.2	3	1.46–47.42
Fall	7.697 \pm 6.8	3	0.81–14.46	337.692 \pm 97.3	3	261.52–447.36	115.266 \pm 199.6	3	0–345.8	24.231 \pm 15.5	3	13.67–42.08

Figure B9.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B9.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. North Pool	0.886 \pm 0.9	2	0.28–1.49	4.96 \pm 3.9	2	2.2–7.72	0.684 \pm 1	2	0–1.37	833.82 \pm 306.9	2	616.82–1050.82	490.192 \pm 130.1	2	398.17–582.21
03. Connecting Channel	0.124 \pm 0.2	2	0–0.25	6.056 \pm 1.2	2	5.2–6.91	0.118 \pm 0.2	2	0–0.24	682.362 \pm 151.2	2	575.46–789.26	484.134 \pm 125	2	395.75–572.52
04. South Pool	0.034 \pm 0	2	0–0.07	12.742 \pm 0.2	2	12.62–12.87	0.746 \pm 0.7	2	0.28–1.21	2236.418 \pm 1401.9	2	1245.1–3227.74	476.708 \pm 13.4	2	467.2–486.22

Table B9.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.176 \pm 0.2	3	0–0.28	6.672 \pm 5.4	3	2.2–12.62	0.404 \pm 0.7	3	0–1.21	1473.339 \pm 1519.5	3	575.46–3227.74	479.296 \pm 87.8	3	398.17–572.52
Fall	0.521 \pm 0.8	3	0–1.49	9.167 \pm 3.2	3	6.91–12.87	0.628 \pm 0.6	3	0.24–1.37	1028.394 \pm 228.7	3	789.26–1245.1	488.06 \pm 93.2	3	395.75–582.21

Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration (SRHE)
Sampling Locations

Table B10.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
SRHE_01	Primary Inflow
SRHE_02	East Wetland Inflow
SRHE_03	East Wetland A
SRHE_04	East Wetland B
SRHE_05	East Outflow A
SRHE_06	East Outflow B
SRHE_07	West Wetland Inflow
SRHE_08	West Wetland A
SRHE_09	West Wetland B
SRHE_10	West Outflow A
SRHE_11	West Outflow B
SRHE_12	Cow Pond
SRHE_13	Sandusky River
SRHE_14	Vernal Pool 1
SRHE_15	Vernal Pool 2
SRHE_16	Vernal Pool 3
SRHE_17	Vernal Pool 4
SRHE_18	Vernal Pool 5
SRHE_19	Vernal Pool 6

Sampling Locations

- 01. Primary Inflow
- 02. East Wetland Inflow
- 03. East Wetland A
- 04. East Wetland B
- 05. East Outflow A
- 06. East Outflow B
- 07. West Wetland Inflow
- 08. West Wetland A
- 09. West Wetland B
- 10. West Outflow A
- 11. West Outflow B
- 12. Cow Pond
- 13. Sandusky River
- 14. Vernal Pool 1
- 15. Vernal Pool 2
- 16. Vernal Pool 3
- 17. Vernal Pool 4
- 18. Vernal Pool 5
- 19. Vernal Pool 6

Figure B10.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B10.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Primary Inflow	24 \pm 7	9	13–34
02. East Wetland Inflow	34 \pm 23	7	10–60
03. East Wetland A	44 \pm 18	16	0–67
04. East Wetland B	55 \pm 21	4	25–69
05. East Outflow A	0 \pm NA	1	0–0
06. East Outflow B	12 \pm 4	2	10–15
07. West Wetland Inflow	15 \pm 22	3	0–40
08. West Wetland A	30 \pm 21	12	0–56
09. West Wetland B	29 \pm 17	5	0–44
10. West Outflow A	20 \pm 16	4	0–34
11. West Outflow B	24 \pm 7	3	16–28
12. Cow Pond	21 \pm 12	4	13–38
13. Sandusky River	39 \pm 18	13	11–77
14. Vernal Pool 1	35 \pm 23	5	0–58
15. Vernal Pool 2	23 \pm 6	2	19–27
16. Vernal Pool 3	39 \pm NA	1	39–39
18. Vernal Pool 5	38 \pm 18	2	25–50

Figure B10.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B10.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	40 \pm 14	19	19–69
Spring	35 \pm 18	12	10–62
Summer	30 \pm 24	32	0–77
Fall	29 \pm 17	30	0–59

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B10.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Primary Inflow	0.04 \pm 0	9 (0)	0.01–0.1	0.091 \pm 0.1	9 (0)	0.03–0.17
02. East Wetland Inflow	0.029 \pm 0	6 (1)	0–0.07	0.065 \pm 0	6 (0)	0.03–0.11
03. East Wetland A	0.027 \pm 0	12 (2)	0–0.15	0.12 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0.02–0.47
04. East Wetland B	0.047 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.07	0.146 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.1–0.22
06. East Outflow B	0.019 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.03	0.103 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.09–0.12
07. West Wetland Inflow	0.029 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.176 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.09–0.27
08. West Wetland A	0.024 \pm 0	7 (2)	0–0.07	0.091 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.01–0.22
09. West Wetland B	0.024 \pm 0	4 (1)	0–0.09	0.164 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.05–0.22
10. West Outflow A	0.044 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0–0.12	0.153 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.08–0.29
11. West Outflow B	0 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0	0.054 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.04–0.06
12. Cow Pond	0.014 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.03	0.173 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.07–0.24
13. Sandusky River	0.063 \pm 0	13 (1)	0–0.13	0.152 \pm 0.1	13 (0)	0.03–0.32

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Vernal Pool 1	0.016 ± 0	4 (1)	0–0.04	0.038 ± 0	4 (0)	0–0.09
15. Vernal Pool 2	0.038 ± 0	2 (0)	0.03–0.05	0.17 ± 0	2 (0)	0.15–0.19
16. Vernal Pool 3	0.02 ± NA	1 (0)	0.02–0.02	0.22 ± NA	1 (0)	0.22–0.22
18. Vernal Pool 5	0.064 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.12	0.212 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.14–0.28

Table B10.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.025 \pm 0	19 (0)	0–0.07	0.158 \pm 0.1	19 (0)	0.02–0.32
Spring	0.002 \pm 0	12 (4)	0–0.01	0.042 \pm 0	12 (0)	0–0.09
Summer	0.038 \pm 0	19 (4)	0–0.1	0.117 \pm 0.1	19 (0)	0.04–0.27
Fall	0.053 \pm 0	27 (2)	0–0.15	0.135 \pm 0.1	27 (0)	0.01–0.47

Figure B10.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B10.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Primary Inflow	0.87 \pm 0.9	9 (0)	0–2.62	0.018 \pm 0	9 (2)	0–0.04	1.267 \pm 1	9 (0)	0.31–3.42
02. East Wetland Inflow	0.185 \pm 0.3	6 (0)	0–0.77	0.016 \pm 0	6 (0)	0–0.04	0.63 \pm 0.4	6 (0)	0.14–1.21
03. East Wetland A	0.559 \pm 0.8	12 (0)	0–2.39	0.041 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.01–0.17	1.552 \pm 1.3	12 (0)	0.28–4.27
04. East Wetland B	1.449 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	1.17–1.69	0.029 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.04	2.189 \pm 0.7	3 (0)	1.67–3.04
06. East Outflow B	0.076 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.15	0.015 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.02	0.817 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	0.6–1.03
07. West Wetland Inflow	0.145 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0–0.29	0.055 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.03–0.08	1.72 \pm 1.7	2 (0)	0.52–2.92
08. West Wetland A	0.516 \pm 0.7	7 (0)	0–1.57	0.025 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0.06	1.118 \pm 1	7 (0)	0.16–2.67
09. West Wetland B	0.805 \pm 0.7	4 (0)	0.01–1.63	0.022 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.06	1.65 \pm 0.8	4 (0)	0.5–2.38
10. West Outflow A	0.525 \pm 0.8	3 (0)	0.06–1.42	0.136 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.01–0.38	1.108 \pm 1	3 (0)	0.43–2.31
11. West Outflow B	0 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0	0.01 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.02	0.398 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.27–0.47

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
12. Cow Pond	0.032 ± 0.1	4 (0)	0–0.13	0.098 ± 0.1	4 (0)	0–0.18	0.935 ± 0.5	4 (0)	0.27–1.5
13. Sandusky River	1.948 ± 1.3	13 (0)	0.22–4.87	0.065 ± 0.1	13 (0)	0–0.45	2.68 ± 1.6	13 (0)	0.67–6.62
14. Vernal Pool 1	0.177 ± 0.3	4 (0)	0–0.66	0.017 ± 0	4 (0)	0–0.04	0.305 ± 0.4	4 (0)	0.04–0.82
15. Vernal Pool 2	0.448 ± 0.3	2 (0)	0.24–0.66	0.019 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.03	1.298 ± 0.7	2 (0)	0.78–1.81
16. Vernal Pool 3	0 ± NA	1 (0)	0–0	0.031 ± NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03	1.05 ± NA	1 (0)	1.05–1.05
18. Vernal Pool 5	0 ± 0	2 (0)	0–0	0.028 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.05	0.765 ± 0.4	2 (0)	0.46–1.07

Table B10.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	1.177 \pm 1.3	19 (0)	0–4.87	0.019 \pm 0	19 (0)	0–0.06	1.989 \pm 1.7	19 (0)	0.11–6.62
Spring	0.308 \pm 0.5	12 (0)	0–1.4	0.051 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0–0.45	0.735 \pm 0.7	12 (0)	0.04–2.25
Summer	0.405 \pm 0.6	19 (0)	0–1.83	0.033 \pm 0	19 (2)	0–0.17	1.239 \pm 0.8	19 (0)	0.41–2.92
Fall	0.82 \pm 1	27 (0)	0–3.96	0.056 \pm 0.1	27 (0)	0.01–0.38	1.452 \pm 1.1	27 (0)	0.14–4.83

Soil Characteristics

Table B10.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. East Wetland Inflow	6.777 \pm 0.3	2	6.58–6.97	318.1 \pm 422.7	2	19.2–617
03. East Wetland A	8.143 \pm 1.1	2	7.38–8.9	126.725 \pm 151.7	2	19.45–234
04. East Wetland B	6.689 \pm 0.4	2	6.39–6.99	370.55 \pm 492.8	2	22.1–719
05. East Outflow A	7.089 \pm 0.1	2	7.05–7.13	386 \pm 33.9	2	362–410
07. West Wetland Inflow	7.292 \pm 0.2	2	7.18–7.4	233.2 \pm 211.8	2	83.4–383
08. West Wetland A	7.282 \pm 0.2	3	7.1–7.48	350.967 \pm 198.4	3	121.9–468
10. West Outflow A	7.54 \pm NA	1	7.54–7.54	177.7 \pm NA	1	177.7–177.7
11. West Outflow B	7.181 \pm NA	1	7.18–7.18	268 \pm NA	1	268–268
14. Vernal Pool 1	7.43 \pm NA	1	7.43–7.43	69.9 \pm NA	1	69.9–69.9

Table B10.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	7.248 \pm 0.5	16	6.39–8.9	277.353 \pm 220.9	16	19.2–719

Table B10.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. East Wetland Inflow	18.16 \pm 25	2	0.51–35.81	1352.271 \pm 1867.5	2	31.72–2672.82	357.252 \pm 270.1	2	166.29–548.22	97.715 \pm 47.4	2	64.19–131.24
03. East Wetland A	10.923 \pm 14.5	2	0.69–21.16	538.482 \pm 685.8	2	53.53–1023.43	485.931 \pm 219.9	2	330.46–641.4	74.678 \pm 1.8	2	73.44–75.92
04. East Wetland B	28.643 \pm 23.8	2	11.82–45.47	1208.262 \pm 1497.6	2	149.3–2267.22	556.822 \pm 283.6	2	356.31–757.34	102.175 \pm 26.6	2	83.4–120.95
05. East Outflow A	34.926 \pm 15.7	2	23.8–46.05	2616.458 \pm 1699.3	2	1414.85–3818.07	651.219 \pm 43.5	2	620.46–681.98	184.683 \pm 73.3	2	132.82–236.55
07. West Wetland Inflow	20.112 \pm 23.8	2	3.3–36.92	1251.683 \pm 1572.1	2	140.06–2363.3	318.219 \pm 349.6	2	71.03–565.4	85.715 \pm 23.1	2	69.37–102.06
08. West Wetland A	12.987 \pm 10.7	3	1.41–22.5	1181.999 \pm 944.4	3	92.1–1758.65	387.231 \pm 284.8	3	92.47–660.93	96.905 \pm 53	3	50.57–154.67
10. West Outflow A	23.729 \pm NA	1	23.73–23.73	1538.037 \pm NA	1	1538.04–1538.04	35.554 \pm NA	1	35.55–35.55	65.494 \pm NA	1	65.49–65.49
11. West Outflow B	22.582 \pm NA	1	22.58–22.58	810.737 \pm NA	1	810.74–810.74	810.398 \pm NA	1	810.4–810.4	115.344 \pm NA	1	115.34–115.34
14. Vernal Pool 1	2.957 \pm NA	1	2.96–2.96	134.966 \pm NA	1	134.97–134.97	701.971 \pm NA	1	701.97–701.97	85.111 \pm NA	1	85.11–85.11

Table B10.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	19.61 \pm 15.6	16	0.51–46.05	1247.753 \pm 1144.5	16	31.72–3818.07	465.532 \pm 260.7	16	35.55–810.4	102.912 \pm 46.2	16	50.57–236.55

Figure B10.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B10.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
02. East Wetland Inflow	0.282 \pm 0	2	0.25–0.31	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	7.71 \pm 10.9	2	0–15.42	2536.802 \pm 2570.9	2	718.87–4354.74	833.316 \pm 844.4	2	236.23–1430.4
03. East Wetland A	0.278 \pm 0.1	2	0.19–0.37	1.32 \pm 1.9	2	0–2.64	4.016 \pm 5.7	2	0–8.03	1183.33 \pm 177.8	2	1057.62–1309.04	319.416 \pm 31.8	2	296.93–341.9
04. East Wetland B	0.315 \pm 0	2	0.29–0.34	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	5.842 \pm 6.4	2	1.33–10.36	3451.778 \pm 253.4	2	3272.62–3630.93	1078.41 \pm 242.4	2	907.01–1249.81
05. East Outflow A	0.476 \pm 0	2	0.47–0.48	0.578 \pm 0.8	2	0–1.16	20.579 \pm 6	2	16.34–24.81	5289.345 \pm 951.7	2	4616.37–5962.32	1257.708 \pm 103.2	2	1184.72–1330.7
07. West Wetland Inflow	0.482 \pm 0	2	0.47–0.49	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	15.523 \pm 22	2	0–31.05	2877.51 \pm 1743.6	2	1644.63–4110.39	940.093 \pm 397	2	659.35–1220.84
08. West Wetland A	0.486 \pm 0	3	0.48–0.5	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	11.716 \pm 11.7	3	0–23.49	1846.074 \pm 1669.7	3	390.29–3668.75	627.552 \pm 421	3	262.4–1088.09
10. West Outflow A	0.515 \pm NA	1	0.52–0.52	1.475 \pm NA	1	1.48–1.48	15.522 \pm NA	1	15.52–15.52	2840.892 \pm NA	1	2840.89–2840.89	1002.502 \pm NA	1	1002.5–1002.5
11. West Outflow B	1.063 \pm NA	1	1.06–1.06	1.776 \pm NA	1	1.78–1.78	4.696 \pm NA	1	4.7–4.7	1701.254 \pm NA	1	1701.25–1701.25	1103.581 \pm NA	1	1103.58–1103.58
14. Vernal Pool 1	0.725 \pm NA	1	0.72–0.72	3.694 \pm NA	1	3.69–3.69	0 \pm NA	1	0–0	613.461 \pm NA	1	613.46–613.46	442.109 \pm NA	1	442.11–442.11

Table B10.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Summer	0.464 \pm 0.2	16	0.19–1.06	0.671 \pm 1.2	16	0–3.69	10.169 \pm 10.2	16	0–31.05	2585.71 \pm 1689.8	16	390.29–5962.32	830.546 \pm 424.9	16	236.23–1430.4

Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat (SUGB)

Sampling Locations

Table B11.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project.

Location Code	Location Description
SUGB_01	HH Pool 1
SUGB_02	HH Pool 2
SUGB_03	HH Pool 3
SUGB_04	HH Pool 4
SUGB_05	HH Pool 5
SUGB_06	HH Pool 6
SUGB_07	Outflow
SUGB_08	Main Pool
SUGB_09	Grass Inflow
SUGB_10	Tile Inflow
SUGB_11	Septic Inflow
SUGB_12	Inflow 2
SUGB_13	River
SUGB_14	Vernal Pool

Sampling Locations

- 01. HH Pool 1
- 02. HH Pool 2
- 03. HH Pool 3
- 04. HH Pool 4
- 05. HH Pool 5
- 06. HH Pool 6
- 07. Outflow
- 08. Main Pool
- 09. Grass Inflow
- 10. Tile Inflow
- 11. Septic Inflow
- 12. Inflow 2
- 13. River
- 14. Vernal Pool

Figure B11.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B11.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. HH Pool 1	28 \pm 20	6	0–61
02. HH Pool 2	29 \pm 13	3	17–42
03. HH Pool 3	36 \pm 27	4	16–76
04. HH Pool 4	25 \pm 8	3	20–34
05. HH Pool 5	24 \pm 18	2	11–36
06. HH Pool 6	42 \pm 2	2	41–44
07. Outflow	25 \pm 28	2	5–45
08. Main Pool	53 \pm 18	5	35–79
09. Grass Inflow	2 \pm NA	1	2–2
11. Septic Inflow	11 \pm 5	3	7–17
12. Inflow 2	7 \pm NA	1	7–7

Figure B11.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B11.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	78 \pm 2	2	76–79
Spring	34 \pm 10	9	17–45
Summer	31 \pm 27	7	0–64
Fall	21 \pm 13	14	2–42

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B11.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. HH Pool 1	0.2 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.06–0.46	0.592 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.34–0.92
02. HH Pool 2	0.104 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.01–0.27	0.6 \pm 0.6	3 (0)	0.12–1.22
03. HH Pool 3	0.14 \pm 0.2	4 (0)	0–0.42	0.512 \pm 0.5	4 (0)	0.1–1.22
04. HH Pool 4	0.219 \pm 0.4	3 (2)	0–0.66	0.454 \pm 0.7	3 (0)	0.06–1.23
05. HH Pool 5	0.24 \pm 0.3	2 (1)	0–0.48	0.53 \pm 0.7	2 (0)	0.07–0.99
06. HH Pool 6	0.164 \pm 0.2	2 (1)	0–0.33	0.425 \pm 0.5	2 (0)	0.07–0.78
07. Outflow	0.13 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.07–0.19	0.669 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.44–1.02
08. Main Pool	0.065 \pm 0.1	6 (1)	0–0.14	0.446 \pm 0.3	6 (0)	0.13–1.07
09. Grass Inflow	0.059 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.06–0.06	0.388 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.39–0.39
10. Tile Inflow	0.132 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.13–0.13	0.498 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.5–0.5
11. Septic Inflow	0.035 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.05	0.401 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.22–0.66
12. Inflow 2	0.249 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.25–0.25	0.503 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.5–0.5

Table B11.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.126 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.12–0.13	0.526 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.5–0.55
Spring	0.012 \pm 0	9 (4)	0–0.06	0.16 \pm 0.1	9 (0)	0.07–0.34
Summer	0.104 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.04–0.19	0.798 \pm 0.3	4 (0)	0.44–1.07
Fall	0.205 \pm 0.2	17 (1)	0–0.66	0.617 \pm 0.4	17 (0)	0.06–1.23

Figure B11.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B11.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. HH Pool 1	0.013 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.04	0.016 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	1.353 \pm 0.4	3 (0)	0.9–1.7
02. HH Pool 2	0.053 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0–0.16	0.017 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	2.257 \pm 1.3	3 (0)	0.75–3.17
03. HH Pool 3	1.76 \pm 3	4 (0)	0–6.26	0.02 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.03	2.93 \pm 2.9	4 (0)	0.46–7.15
04. HH Pool 4	0.7 \pm 1.1	3 (0)	0–2	0.035 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.07	1.867 \pm 1.3	3 (0)	0.52–3.01
05. HH Pool 5	0.065 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.13	0.023 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.03	1.18 \pm 0.8	2 (0)	0.58–1.78
06. HH Pool 6	0.105 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.21	0.018 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.02	1.18 \pm 0.8	2 (0)	0.64–1.72
07. Outflow	2.702 \pm 1.4	3 (0)	1.47–4.15	0.098 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.02–0.18	5.468 \pm 2.7	3 (0)	2.95–8.31
08. Main Pool	2.032 \pm 2	6 (0)	0.02–4.84	0.037 \pm 0	6 (0)	0.01–0.11	3.908 \pm 2.6	6 (0)	1.54–7.85
09. Grass Inflow	2.79 \pm NA	1 (0)	2.79–2.79	0.119 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.12–0.12	5.74 \pm NA	1 (0)	5.74–5.74
10. Tile Inflow	2.4 \pm NA	1 (0)	2.4–2.4	0.025 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03	5.08 \pm NA	1 (0)	5.08–5.08

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
11. Septic Inflow	0.908 ± 1.6	3 (0)	0–2.72	0.027 ± 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.04	2.767 ± 2.4	3 (0)	0.9–5.45
12. Inflow 2	4.49 ± NA	1 (0)	4.49–4.49	0.049 ± NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	6.47 ± NA	1 (0)	6.47–6.47

Table B11.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	5.549 \pm 1	2 (0)	4.84–6.26	0.013 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.01	6.249 \pm 1.3	2 (0)	5.35–7.15
Spring	0.098 \pm 0.2	9 (0)	0–0.45	0.018 \pm 0	9 (0)	0.01–0.03	0.942 \pm 0.5	9 (0)	0.46–1.98
Summer	3.069 \pm 1.2	4 (0)	1.47–4.15	0.108 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.04–0.18	6.138 \pm 2.5	4 (0)	2.95–8.31
Fall	1.066 \pm 1.4	17 (0)	0–4.49	0.032 \pm 0	17 (0)	0.01–0.12	3.105 \pm 1.7	17 (0)	1.46–6.47

Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland (TIPC)

Sampling Locations

Table B12.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project.

Location Code	Location Description
TIPC_01	Great Miami River Upstream
TIPC_02	Wetland Inflow
TIPC_03	Mid Wetland (near HOBO)
TIPC_04	Great Miami River Downstream

Sampling Locations

- 01. Great Miami River (upstream)
- 02. Wetland Inflow
- 03. Mid Wetland (near HOBO)
- 04. Great Miami River (downstream)

Figure B12.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B12.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Great Miami River Upstream	37 \pm 16	17	10–62
02. Wetland Inflow	31 \pm 16	18	0–64
03. Mid Wetland (near HOBO)	41 \pm 27	20	0–100
04. Great Miami River Downstream	60 \pm 25	17	30–121

Figure B12.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B12.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	57 \pm 28	20	25–121
Spring	41 \pm 17	12	15–62
Summer	35 \pm 16	25	10–60
Fall	36 \pm 26	15	0–90

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B12.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Great Miami River Upstream	0.228 \pm 0.2	14 (0)	0–0.5	0.335 \pm 0.2	14 (0)	0.15–0.7
02. Wetland Inflow	0.029 \pm 0.1	15 (6)	0–0.24	0.087 \pm 0.1	16 (3)	0–0.44
03. Mid Wetland (near HOBO)	0.003 \pm 0	14 (10)	0–0.03	0.111 \pm 0.2	16 (3)	0–0.71
04. Great Miami River Downstream	0.129 \pm 0.1	16 (2)	0–0.46	0.214 \pm 0.1	16 (0)	0.03–0.53

Table B12.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.033 \pm 0	16 (8)	0–0.11	0.093 \pm 0.1	16 (4)	0–0.29
Spring	0.057 \pm 0.1	12 (2)	0–0.19	0.158 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0.03–0.29
Summer	0.118 \pm 0.2	22 (6)	0–0.5	0.244 \pm 0.2	22 (0)	0.03–0.71
Fall	0.213 \pm 0.2	9 (2)	0–0.43	0.21 \pm 0.2	12 (2)	0–0.55

Figure B12.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B12.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Great Miami River Upstream	2.783 \pm 1.9	14 (0)	0.65–6.02	0.09 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.01–0.29	3.503 \pm 1.9	14 (0)	1.48–7.39
02. Wetland Inflow	0.567 \pm 0.8	16 (6)	0–2.77	0.005 \pm 0	6 (2)	0–0.01	1.514 \pm 1.4	16 (0)	0.17–5.24
03. Mid Wetland (near HOBO)	0.552 \pm 0.9	16 (7)	0–2.69	0.005 \pm 0	6 (2)	0–0.01	1.691 \pm 1.3	16 (0)	0.52–4.73
04. Great Miami River Downstream	2.216 \pm 1.3	16 (1)	0–4.24	0.061 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.01–0.23	2.8 \pm 1.1	16 (0)	1.25–5.58

Table B12.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	2.387 \pm 1.8	16 (0)	0.64–5.51	0.025 \pm 0	16 (2)	0–0.08	2.601 \pm 1.8	16 (0)	0.67–6.31
Spring	2.047 \pm 2	12 (4)	0–6.02	0.009 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.01	3.422 \pm 2	12 (0)	1.18–7.39
Summer	0.88 \pm 1	22 (10)	0–2.93	NA	NA	NA	2.076 \pm 1.3	22 (0)	0.44–4.73
Fall	0.85 \pm 0.8	12 (0)	0.01–2.03	0.13 \pm 0.2	4 (2)	0–0.29	1.397 \pm 0.9	12 (0)	0.17–2.65

Trumbull Creek H2Ohio (TRUC)

Sampling Locations

Table B13.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project.

Location Code	Location Description
TRUC_01	Hummock Pool
TRUC_02	Borrow Pool 1
TRUC_03	Borrow Pool 2
TRUC_04	WCS
TRUC_05	Outflow

Sampling Locations

- 01. Hummock Pool
- 02. Borrow Pool 1
- 03. Borrow Pool 2
- 04. WCS
- 05. Outflow

Figure B13.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B13.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Hummock Pool	27 \pm 10	5	18–43
02. Borrow Pool 1	24 \pm 11	8	10–45
03. Borrow Pool 2	51 \pm 17	8	28–78
04. WCS	31 \pm 13	11	14–48
05. Outflow	12 \pm NA	1	12–12

Figure B13.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B13.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	37 \pm 9	5	25–48
Summer	35 \pm 19	17	10–78
Fall	28 \pm 14	11	12–56

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B13.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Hummock Pool	0.01 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.052 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05
02. Borrow Pool 1	0.008 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.01	0.033 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03
03. Borrow Pool 2	0.008 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.01	0.02 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.02–0.02
04. WCS	0.009 \pm 0	7 (0)	0.01–0.02	0.021 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.02–0.02
05. Outflow	0.006 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.018 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.02–0.02

Table B13.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.006 \pm 0	5 (0)	0–0.01	NA	NA	NA
Summer	0.012 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.02	NA	NA	NA
Fall	0.009 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.01	0.029 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.02–0.05

Figure B13.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B13.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Hummock Pool	0.008 \pm 0	5 (1)	0–0.01	0.029 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.06	0.529 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.53–0.53
02. Borrow Pool 1	0.012 \pm 0	4 (1)	0–0.04	0.024 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.03	0.461 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.46–0.46
03. Borrow Pool 2	0.005 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.01	0.01 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.4 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.4–0.4
04. WCS	0.005 \pm 0	7 (2)	0–0.01	0.017 \pm 0	7 (0)	0.01–0.02	0.468 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.47–0.47
05. Outflow	0.036 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04	0.042 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04	0.432 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.43–0.43

Table B13.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.003 \pm 0	5 (2)	0–0.01	0.025 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.06	NA	NA	NA
Summer	0.002 \pm 0	5 (2)	0–0	0.018 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.02	NA	NA	NA
Fall	0.014 \pm 0	11 (0)	0–0.04	0.02 \pm 0	11 (0)	0.01–0.04	0.458 \pm 0	5 (0)	0.4–0.53

Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration (VANO)
Sampling Locations

Table B14.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
VANO_01	Wetland Pool 1
VANO_02	Wetland Pool 2
VANO_03	Wetland Pool 3
VANO_04	Wetland Pool 4
VANO_05	Wetland Pool 5
VANO_06	Wetland Pool 6
VANO_07	Wetland Pool 7
VANO_08	Wetland Pool 8
VANO_09	South Ditch

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Wetland Pool 1
 - 02. Wetland Pool 2
 - 03. Wetland Pool 3
 - 04. Wetland Pool 4
 - 05. Wetland Pool 5
 - 06. Wetland Pool 6
 - 07. Wetland Pool 7
 - 08. Wetland Pool 8
 - 09. South Ditch

Figure B14.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B14.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	10 \pm 16	17	0–60
02. Wetland Pool 2	5 \pm 11	9	0–30
03. Wetland Pool 3	19 \pm 18	9	0–52
04. Wetland Pool 4	4 \pm 9	10	0–27
05. Wetland Pool 5	11 \pm 16	10	0–45
06. Wetland Pool 6	18 \pm 22	9	0–70
07. Wetland Pool 7	9 \pm 14	12	0–35
08. Wetland Pool 8	9 \pm 15	13	0–45
09. South Ditch	15 \pm 20	6	0–45

Figure B14.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B14.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	16 \pm 12	8	0–32
Spring	22 \pm 20	27	0–70
Summer	6 \pm 11	51	0–40
Fall	0 \pm 0	9	0–0

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B14.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.005 \pm 0	6 (5)	0–0.03	0.29 \pm 0.4	6 (1)	0–0.85
02. Wetland Pool 2	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.123 \pm 0.2	4 (1)	0–0.42
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.022 \pm 0	6 (4)	0–0.12	0.255 \pm 0.4	6 (1)	0–1.15
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.014 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	0.086 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.03–0.12
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.005 \pm 0	4 (3)	0–0.02	0.102 \pm 0.2	4 (1)	0–0.34
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.046 \pm 0.1	6 (4)	0–0.22	0.363 \pm 0.6	6 (0)	0.02–1.5
07. Wetland Pool 7	0 \pm 0	5 (5)	0–0	0.074 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.02–0.13
08. Wetland Pool 8	0 \pm 0	7 (7)	0–0	0.017 \pm 0	7 (2)	0–0.06
09. South Ditch	0.014 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.03	0.01 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.02

Table B14.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.002 \pm 0	21 (20)	0–0.04	0.024 \pm 0	20 (6)	0–0.1
Summer	0.03 \pm 0.1	14 (9)	0–0.22	0.346 \pm 0.5	14 (1)	0–1.5
Fall	0.008 \pm 0	8 (6)	0–0.05	0.214 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.06–0.48

Figure B14.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B14.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.426 \pm 0.7	6 (0)	0.03–1.86	0.024 \pm 0.1	6 (5)	0–0.14	3.019 \pm 4.2	6 (0)	0.11–9.64
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.229 \pm 0.3	4 (0)	0.05–0.71	0.037 \pm 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.12	0.73 \pm 0.7	4 (0)	0.09–1.75
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.659 \pm 1.1	6 (0)	0.01–2.95	0.047 \pm 0.1	6 (3)	0–0.13	2.244 \pm 3.6	6 (0)	0.18–9.37
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.159 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.05–0.37	0.007 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.02	0.863 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.55–1.19
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.135 \pm 0.2	4 (0)	0.01–0.4	0.01 \pm 0	4 (3)	0–0.04	0.518 \pm 0.5	4 (0)	0.11–1.25
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.745 \pm 1.6	6 (1)	0–3.99	0.013 \pm 0	6 (5)	0–0.08	2.157 \pm 3.6	6 (0)	0.18–9.46
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.158 \pm 0.1	5 (1)	0–0.33	0.003 \pm 0	5 (4)	0–0.01	0.794 \pm 0.6	4 (0)	0.26–1.68
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.091 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.01–0.3	0 \pm 0	7 (7)	0–0	0.421 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.24–0.52
09. South Ditch	2.269 \pm 1.8	2 (0)	1.02–3.52	0.018 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.04	3.015 \pm 1.9	2 (0)	1.69–4.34

Table B14.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.236 \pm 0.8	21 (0)	0.05–3.52	0.004 \pm 0	21 (18)	0–0.04	0.654 \pm 0.9	20 (0)	0.09–4.34
Summer	0.761 \pm 1.3	14 (2)	0–3.99	0.032 \pm 0.1	14 (10)	0–0.14	3.131 \pm 3.9	14 (0)	0.14–9.64
Fall	0.409 \pm 0.1	8 (0)	0.3–0.71	0.028 \pm 0	8 (4)	0–0.12	0.919 \pm 0.5	8 (0)	0.46–1.75

Soil Characteristics

Table B14.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	7.554 \pm 0.3	4	7.08–7.8	90.165 \pm 69.9	4	18.06–167.2
02. Wetland Pool 2	7.362 \pm 0.3	3	6.99–7.58	57.967 \pm 40.2	3	22.8–101.8
03. Wetland Pool 3	7.414 \pm 0.4	3	6.99–7.72	72.867 \pm 41.5	3	25.1–99.8
04. Wetland Pool 4	7.234 \pm 0.6	4	6.62–7.78	81.05 \pm 42.9	4	33.7–127.2
05. Wetland Pool 5	7.508 \pm 0.1	4	7.45–7.63	69.425 \pm 48.4	4	37.9–141.6
06. Wetland Pool 6	6.939 \pm 0.6	3	6.5–7.6	41.057 \pm 24.9	3	18.57–67.8
07. Wetland Pool 7	5.846 \pm 0.3	6	5.49–6.34	27.177 \pm 10.1	6	16.91–44.3
08. Wetland Pool 8	7.654 \pm 0.3	7	7.14–7.91	65.729 \pm 21.5	7	36.6–93.5
09. South Ditch	7.306 \pm 0.3	2	7.08–7.53	464 \pm 275.8	2	269–659

Table B14.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	7.166 \pm 0.6	15	5.88–7.91	72.809 \pm 73.4	15	16.91–269
Summer	7.148 \pm 0.8	21	5.49–7.8	92.25 \pm 133.3	21	21.56–659

Table B14.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	25.819 \pm 26.7	7	4.4–73.1	134.474 \pm 41.2	7	90.18–217.9	574.157 \pm 118.5	7	348.9–714.2	51.286 \pm 29.4	7	0–76
02. Wetland Pool 2	16.6 \pm 17.6	3	3.8–36.7	71.833 \pm 25	3	55.9–100.7	773.033 \pm 209.4	3	628.5–1013.2	76 \pm 9.5	3	66–85
03. Wetland Pool 3	6.467 \pm 7.9	3	1.9–15.6	145.533 \pm 33.5	3	117.5–182.7	507.4 \pm 47.1	3	453.8–542.1	60 \pm 11.4	3	47–68
04. Wetland Pool 4	65.525 \pm 31.6	4	26.9–101	163.75 \pm 100.2	4	59.4–300.2	1059.65 \pm 587.4	4	437.3–1602.8	65.25 \pm 41.1	4	30–113
05. Wetland Pool 5	36.625 \pm 24.3	4	5.8–56.8	131.525 \pm 74.7	4	83.4–240.9	746.35 \pm 151.8	4	592.9–938.7	56.5 \pm 20.4	4	26–69
06. Wetland Pool 6	25.7 \pm 5.9	3	19.7–31.5	205.067 \pm 14.6	3	196.3–221.9	797.7 \pm 76.3	3	710.8–853.5	77.333 \pm 5.1	3	73–83
07. Wetland Pool 7	22.567 \pm 19.5	6	1.8–42.7	168.233 \pm 69.8	6	92.3–247.4	857.65 \pm 352.4	6	475–1209.1	85.333 \pm 22.9	6	58–115
08. Wetland Pool 8	9.957 \pm 12.7	7	0.3–33.3	115.357 \pm 76.2	7	51.3–229	306.02 \pm 250.5	5	36.2–570.8	28.8 \pm 22.4	5	3–50
09. South Ditch	9.75 \pm 9.5	2	3–16.5	770.65 \pm 322.2	2	542.8–998.5	188.5 \pm NA	1	188.5–188.5	60 \pm NA	1	60–60

Table B14.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	24.224 \pm 23	18	1.8–78	199.351 \pm 213.2	18	51.3–998.5	622.861 \pm 364.5	18	36.2–1517.3	58.389 \pm 31.4	18	3–115
Summer	24.962 \pm 26.7	21	0.3–101	150.457 \pm 104.8	21	58.9–542.8	729.472 \pm 322	18	348.9–1602.8	63.944 \pm 25	18	0–101

Figure B14.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B14.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.505 \pm 1	4	0–2.02	9.783 \pm 10.7	4	2.7–25.51	0.215 \pm 0.4	4	0–0.86	1016 \pm 826.4	7	192–2338	260.143 \pm 171.6	7	72–542
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.132 \pm 0.2	3	0–0.4	2.603 \pm 3	3	0–5.92	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	392.333 \pm 590.1	3	0–1071	129 \pm 120.4	3	40–266
03. Wetland Pool 3	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	3.831 \pm 3.4	3	0–6.56	0.636 \pm 0.6	3	0–1.3	385.333 \pm 110.6	3	285–504	126.667 \pm 23.7	3	112–154
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.653 \pm 0.5	4	0–1.27	5 \pm 3.7	4	1.29–9.28	0 \pm 0	4	0–0	533 \pm 257.8	4	223–846	191.25 \pm 92.1	4	108–296
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.477 \pm 0.6	4	0–1.1	5.537 \pm 6	4	0–14.09	0.318 \pm 0.6	4	0–1.27	244.75 \pm 151.5	4	43–398	206.5 \pm 167	4	103–456
06. Wetland Pool 6	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	3.825 \pm 3.4	3	0–6.52	0 \pm 0	3	0–0	306.667 \pm 172.8	3	128–473	130.333 \pm 35.7	3	97–168
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.046 \pm 0.1	6	0–0.28	4.396 \pm 3.3	6	0–9.06	0.536 \pm 1.3	6	0–3.21	531 \pm 445.5	6	4–1047	205.833 \pm 73.5	6	93–280
08. Wetland Pool 8	0 \pm 0	7	0–0	3.216 \pm 2.7	7	0–7.25	0.377 \pm 1	7	0–2.64	563.857 \pm 864.2	7	0–2091	245 \pm 139.2	7	9–418
09. South Ditch	0 \pm 0	2	0–0	32.085 \pm 31.6	2	9.74–54.43	1.809 \pm 0.3	2	1.62–2	3808 \pm 4644.3	2	524–7092	393 \pm 301.2	2	180–606

Table B14.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)		TP (mg P/kg)			
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	0.235 \pm 0.4	15	0–1.1	11.562 \pm 13	15	4.75–54.43	0.609 \pm 1.1	15	0–3.21	927.944 \pm 1663.9	18	0–7092	241.722 \pm 168.9	18	9–606
Summer	0.176 \pm 0.5	21	0–2.02	2.461 \pm 2.5	21	0–9.74	0.209 \pm 0.5	21	0–1.62	548.667 \pm 548.2	21	0–2091	188.333 \pm 98.5	21	40–418

Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration (WALC)

Sampling Locations

Table B15.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
WALC_01	Walnut Creek Inflow
WALC_02	Early Wetland
WALC_03	Mid Wetland
WALC_04	Late Wetland
WALC_05	Walnut Creek Outflow

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Walnut Creek Inflow
 - 02. Early Wetland
 - 03. Mid Wetland
 - 04. Late Wetland
 - 05. Walnut Creek Outflow

Figure B15.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B15.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Walnut Creek Inflow	52 \pm 18	8	25–80
02. Early Wetland	24 \pm 24	10	0–62
03. Mid Wetland	0 \pm 0	6	0–0
04. Late Wetland	62 \pm 39	7	0–105
05. Walnut Creek Outflow	73 \pm 36	6	40–140

Figure B15.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B15.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	34 \pm 31	10	0–70
Summer	49 \pm 42	17	0–140
Fall	36 \pm 27	10	0–85

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B15.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Walnut Creek Inflow	0.153 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.02–0.48	0.316 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.1–0.69
02. Early Wetland	0.003 \pm 0	6 (3)	0–0.01	0.1 \pm 0	6 (0)	0.03–0.18
04. Late Wetland	0 \pm 0	6 (5)	0–0	0.08 \pm 0	6 (0)	0.01–0.15
05. Walnut Creek Outflow	0.197 \pm 0.2	6 (0)	0.05–0.48	0.3 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.16–0.5

Table B15.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	0.053 \pm 0.1	6 (2)	0–0.13	0.097 \pm 0.1	6 (0)	0.01–0.16
Summer	0.054 \pm 0.1	12 (5)	0–0.17	0.185 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0.04–0.47
Fall	0.182 \pm 0.2	8 (1)	0–0.48	0.325 \pm 0.2	8 (0)	0.09–0.69

Figure B15.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B15.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Walnut Creek Inflow	2.01 \pm 0.9	8 (0)	1.36–4.09	0.014 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	2.865 \pm 1.1	8 (0)	1.9–4.78
02. Early Wetland	0.736 \pm 1.6	6 (3)	0–3.92	0.095 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.1–0.1	2.964 \pm 3	6 (0)	0.98–8.99
04. Late Wetland	1.335 \pm 1.9	6 (2)	0–4.64	0.094 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09	2.808 \pm 2.8	6 (0)	1.06–8.3
05. Walnut Creek Outflow	2.108 \pm 1	6 (0)	1.28–4.09	0.012 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	2.996 \pm 1.2	6 (0)	1.97–4.8

Table B15.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Spring	1.383 \pm 0.7	6 (0)	0.37–2.01	0.04 \pm 0	6 (0)	0.01–0.1	1.815 \pm 0.5	6 (0)	0.98–2.3
Summer	1.82 \pm 1.5	12 (3)	0–4.64	NA	NA	NA	3.547 \pm 2.6	12 (0)	1.21–8.99
Fall	1.377 \pm 1.8	8 (2)	0–4.09	NA	NA	NA	2.759 \pm 1.4	8 (0)	1.06–4.8

Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration (WEIP)

Sampling Locations

Table B16.1. Standardized identification code and brief description of sampling locations at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project.

Location Code	Location Description
WEIP_01	Vernal Pool 1
WEIP_02	Vernal Pool 2
WEIP_03	Vernal Pool 3
WEIP_04	Vernal Pool 4
WEIP_05	Vernal Pool 5
WEIP_06	Floodplain wetland
WEIP_07	Existing wetland
WEIP_08	Tiffin River
WEIP_09	Seepage spring

Sampling Locations

- 01. Vernal Pool 1
- 02. Vernal Pool 2
- 03. Vernal Pool 3
- 04. Vernal Pool 4
- 05. Vernal Pool 5
- 06. Flood plain wetland
- 07. Existing wetland
- 08. Tiffin River
- 09. Seepage spring

Figure B16.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling point.

Hydrology

Table B16.2. Discrete, manually measured water depths for each sampling location of the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	1 \pm 1	14	0–4
02. Vernal Pool 2	1 \pm 3	9	0–8
03. Vernal Pool 3	5 \pm 6	11	0–15
04. Vernal Pool 4	4 \pm 5	10	0–12
05. Vernal Pool 5	0 \pm 0	11	0–0
06. Floodplain wetland	3 \pm 5	19	0–15
07. Existing wetland	0 \pm 0	7	0–0
08. Tiffin River	43 \pm 32	10	0–100
09. Seepage spring	21 \pm 20	3	0–39

Figure B16.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Table B16.3. Discrete, manually measured water depths for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project by season. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Depth (cm)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	14 \pm 18	9	0–50
Spring	5 \pm 5	24	0–15
Summer	6 \pm 17	48	0–70
Fall	9 \pm 28	13	0–100

Surface Water Chemistry

Table B16.4. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0
02. Vernal Pool 2	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.091 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.07–0.11
03. Vernal Pool 3	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.09 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.03–0.15
04. Vernal Pool 4	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.025 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.03
05. Vernal Pool 5	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.12 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.12–0.12
06. Floodplain wetland	0.015 \pm 0	3 (1)	0–0.03	0.108 \pm 0.2	3 (1)	0–0.3
07. Existing wetland	0.071 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.07–0.07	0.333 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.33–0.33
08. Tiffin River	0.071 \pm 0	10 (0)	0.02–0.1	0.119 \pm 0.1	10 (0)	0.07–0.21
09. Seepage spring	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.047 \pm 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.09

Table B16.5. Summarized surface water phosphorus concentrations for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (mg P/L)			Total Phosphorus (mg P/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	0.022 \pm 0	9 (5)	0–0.07	0.108 \pm 0.1	9 (1)	0–0.33
Spring	0.008 \pm 0	4 (3)	0–0.03	0.171 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0.11–0.3
Summer	0.051 \pm 0	8 (2)	0–0.09	0.072 \pm 0	8 (1)	0–0.13
Fall	0.049 \pm 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.1	0.06 \pm 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.12

Figure B16.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table B16.6. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0
02. Vernal Pool 2	0.103 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.08–0.12	0.008 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.02	1.381 \pm 1.4	2 (0)	0.42–2.34
03. Vernal Pool 3	0.108 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.08–0.13	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.737 \pm 1.8	2 (0)	0.45–3.02
04. Vernal Pool 4	0.481 \pm 0.6	2 (0)	0.07–0.89	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.715 \pm 0.6	2 (0)	0.31–1.12
05. Vernal Pool 5	0.104 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.1–0.1	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	1.956 \pm NA	1 (0)	1.96–1.96
06. Floodplain wetland	1.57 \pm 2.6	3 (1)	0–4.58	0.013 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	3.53 \pm 1.9	3 (0)	1.31–4.8
07. Existing wetland	2.592 \pm NA	1 (0)	2.59–2.59	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	3.575 \pm NA	1 (0)	3.58–3.58
08. Tiffin River	2.578 \pm 3.7	10 (0)	0.05–12.18	0.013 \pm 0	10 (7)	0–0.08	3.117 \pm 4.3	10 (0)	0.35–14.29
09. Seepage spring	3.506 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	3.35–3.67	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	3.885 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	3.67–4.1

Table B16.7. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
Winter	2.025 \pm 1.7	9 (0)	0.07–3.78	0.008 \pm 0	9 (8)	0–0.08	2.457 \pm 1.8	9 (0)	0.31–4.5
Spring	0.123 \pm 0	4 (0)	0.1–0.13	0.004 \pm 0	4 (3)	0–0.02	2.949 \pm 1.1	4 (0)	1.96–4.47
Summer	2.842 \pm 4.1	8 (1)	0–12.18	0.012 \pm 0	8 (5)	0–0.04	3.513 \pm 4.6	8 (0)	0.65–14.29
Fall	0.032 \pm 0	4 (2)	0–0.08	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.178 \pm 0.2	4 (2)	0–0.36

Soil Characteristics

Table B16.8. Summarized soil characteristics at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	7.572 \pm 0.6	4	6.64–8.09	298.6 \pm 246.1	4	109.1–634
02. Vernal Pool 2	7.678 \pm 0.3	2	7.45–7.91	664 \pm 294.2	2	456–872
03. Vernal Pool 3	7.122 \pm 0.8	5	6.28–8.09	427.46 \pm 507	5	69.4–1278
04. Vernal Pool 4	6.543 \pm 0.2	4	6.33–6.8	90.773 \pm 91.5	4	12.59–208.4
05. Vernal Pool 5	6.066 \pm 0.8	6	5.23–7.26	89.805 \pm 136.4	6	11.93–357
06. Floodplain wetland	6.297 \pm 0.2	10	6.03–6.68	72.38 \pm 35.6	10	27.5–139.2
07. Existing wetland	6.566 \pm 0.2	2	6.42–6.71	104.05 \pm 103.7	2	30.7–177.4
08. Tiffin River	7.724 \pm 0.1	2	7.63–7.82	939.5 \pm 212.8	2	789–1090

Table B16.9. Summarized soil characteristics at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). Soil pH, total carbon and soil conductivity are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	Soil pH			Soil Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Spring	6.366 \pm 0.5	21	5.23–7.74	61.563 \pm 42.6	21	11.93–139.2
Summer	7.264 \pm 0.8	14	5.42–8.09	505.693 \pm 378.1	14	112.7–1278

Table B16.10. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	0.478 \pm 0.2	5	0.3–0.74	110.308 \pm 35.1	5	70.84–142.09	522.208 \pm 333.6	4	25.73–742.2	66 \pm 40.4	4	6–93
02. Vernal Pool 2	1.026 \pm 0.5	3	0.55–1.54	151.23 \pm 11.8	3	142.62–164.62	644.2 \pm 18.2	3	630.4–664.8	81.667 \pm 2.1	3	80–84
03. Vernal Pool 3	3.902 \pm 4	6	0.46–10.1	140.445 \pm 58.3	6	76.3–251	437.5 \pm 248.6	6	22.8–649.7	51 \pm 32.5	6	2–81
04. Vernal Pool 4	2.237 \pm 0.9	5	1.12–3.31	118.788 \pm 35.7	5	64.4–151.94	723.64 \pm 193.8	5	407–924.8	81.2 \pm 30.7	5	37–113
05. Vernal Pool 5	17.795 \pm 17	7	1.56–41.9	136.013 \pm 34.9	7	110–199.01	679.486 \pm 126	7	539–916.8	63.143 \pm 34.4	7	30–115
06. Floodplain wetland	23.751 \pm 43.3	14	0.52–113	200.69 \pm 133	14	56–383	506.671 \pm 230.5	14	255–959	51.071 \pm 43	14	0–127
07. Existing wetland	10.532 \pm 9.3	3	2.73–20.8	437.01 \pm 170.3	3	271–611.38	828.267 \pm 220.1	3	585–1013.6	104.333 \pm 49	3	48–137

Table B16.11. Summary of soil available phosphorus and sorption indices from Mehlich 3 (M3) extractions for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project by season (SPSC = Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min–max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	M3-P (mg P/kg)			M3-Fe (mg Fe/kg)			M3-Al (mg Al/kg)			SPSC (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min–Max
Winter	1.667 \pm 1.6	22	0.35–8.06	204.099 \pm 122.3	22	127.2–611.38	750.214 \pm 132.1	22	582.4–1013.6	95.818 \pm 19	22	73–137
Spring	23.432 \pm 35.6	21	0.3–113	144.021 \pm 109.7	21	56–383	404.726 \pm 183.3	20	22.8–704	29.15 \pm 18.3	20	0–63

Figure B16.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Table B16.12. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min-max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	0 \pm 0	7	0-0	3.004 \pm 1.1	7	1.49-4.97	0.397 \pm 0.6	7	0-1.55	727.143 \pm 448.6	7	158-1360	358.143 \pm 53.6	7	272-427
02. Vernal Pool 2	0.41 \pm 0.5	5	0.02-1.32	3.826 \pm 1.4	5	2.64-6.19	0.766 \pm 1	5	0-2.43	1099.6 \pm 363.3	5	502-1390	403.8 \pm 98.8	5	269-535
03. Vernal Pool 3	0.004 \pm 0	8	0-0.03	4.172 \pm 1.8	8	1.86-6.79	1.297 \pm 2.5	8	0-7.06	1090.375 \pm 338.4	8	509-1557	391 \pm 117.2	8	233-583
04. Vernal Pool 4	0.458 \pm 0.8	7	0-2.18	3.174 \pm 1.4	7	1.36-5.56	0.287 \pm 0.4	7	0-0.93	786.429 \pm 521.1	7	105-1304	360.429 \pm 184.4	7	112-529
05. Vernal Pool 5	0.126 \pm 0.3	9	0-0.63	2.622 \pm 1	9	1.32-4.1	0.196 \pm 0.3	9	0-0.81	889.222 \pm 389.1	9	415-1701	415.778 \pm 64.4	9	324-531
06. Floodplain wetland	0.997 \pm 1.3	15	0-3.87	5.709 \pm 5.5	15	2.11-24.5	0.567 \pm 1.5	15	0-5.91	1189.467 \pm 696.8	15	257-2601	499.733 \pm 217.8	15	186-855
07. Existing wetland	1.112 \pm 1.2	4	0-2.69	4.114 \pm 0.8	4	3.25-5.14	4.603 \pm 9	4	0-18.17	1127.75 \pm 1030.7	4	50-2502	500.25 \pm 398	4	78-1037
08. Tiffin River	0.558 \pm 0.1	2	0.49-0.62	5.851 \pm 2	2	4.41-7.29	0 \pm 0	2	0-0	631.5 \pm 156.3	2	521-742	421.5 \pm 111	2	343-500

Table B16.13. Summary of easily mobilizable (water-extractable) soil nutrients at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project by season. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations and range (min-max). NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Season	H ₂ O-PO ₄ (mg P/kg)			H ₂ O-NO ₃ (mg N/kg)			H ₂ O-NH ₃ (mg N/kg)			TN (mg N/kg)			TP (mg P/kg)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size	Min-Max
Winter	0.697 \pm 0.9	22	0–2.69	3.448 \pm 1.5	22	1.32–7.46	2.096 \pm 4	22	0.24–18.17	1317.773 \pm 490.6	22	50–2502	514.136 \pm 193	22	78–1037
Spring	0.397 \pm 1.1	21	0–3.87	4.748 \pm 4.8	21	1.36–24.5	0.074 \pm 0.3	21	0–1.55	809.714 \pm 615.1	21	105–2601	359.095 \pm 168.1	21	112–755
Summer	0.233 \pm 0.3	14	0–0.72	4.113 \pm 1.6	14	1.36–7.29	0 \pm 0	14	0–0	745.714 \pm 250.8	14	443–1304	386.214 \pm 81.5	14	244–506

Appendix C

Vegetation Data for Focal Projects

Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure C1.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative from 2021–2023.

Figure C1.2 Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative summarized for the sampling year 2022–2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C1.1. Key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes adapted from the USDA PLANTS Database¹.

Wetland Indicator Status	Code	Description
Upland	UPL	Almost never occur in wetlands
Facultative Upland	FACU	Usually occur in non-wetlands, but may occur in wetlands
Facultative	FAC	Occur in wetlands and non-wetlands
Facultative Wetland	FACW	Usually occur in wetlands, but may occur in non-wetlands
Obligate Wetland	OBL	Almost always occur in wetlands

Table C1.2. Vegetation sampling effort at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project from 2021–2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass and detritus. At this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient content. No belowground biomass has been sampled at this Project to date.

Sample Type	2021	2022	2023
Site Visits	2	2	2
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	31	20	17
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	–	15	3
Aboveground Samples	–	47	10
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Content	–	32	9
Belowground Samples	–	–	–
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Content	–	–	–

¹ USDA, NRCS. 2024. The PLANTS Database (<http://plants.usda.gov>, 3/25/2024). National Plant Data Team, Greensboro, NC USA.

Table C1.3. List of morphospecies encountered at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project during 2021–2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa-Panicum</i> -Unspecified ND	Grasses		1	95 \pm NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus</i> ND	Bulrush		1	60 \pm NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia palustris</i>	Water purslane	OBL	6	52 \pm 24
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia peploides</i>	Floating Primrose-willow	OBL	1	50 \pm NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		1	50 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum</i> ND	Panic grass		12	36 \pm 24
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		10	30 \pm 13
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria-Panicum</i> ND	Grasses		1	30 \pm NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		18	22 \pm 14
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		4	22 \pm 25
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		4	18 \pm 10
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		6	17 \pm 29
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> ND	Water purslane		18	16 \pm 12
	Algae	ND	Algae		12	13 \pm 12
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		24	12 \pm 8
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		12	11 \pm 10
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia</i> ND	Coneflowers		1	10 \pm NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa</i> ND	Yellowcress		1	10 \pm NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> ND	Docks and sorrels		1	10 \pm NA

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		6	9 ± 5
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red maple	FAC	4	9 ± 7
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		12	8 ± 5
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer</i> ND	Unk. Maple		7	8 ± 4
	Lamiaceae	<i>Pycnanthemum virginianum</i>	Virginia Mountain Mint		6	6 ± 7
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		4	5 ± 5
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		7	5 ± 5
	Salicaceae	<i>Salix nigra</i>	Black willow	OBL	3	5 ± 0
		Unknown			7	5 ± 6
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia</i> ND	False Pimpernel		3	3 ± 3
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago</i> ND	Plantains		4	2 ± 2
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma</i> ND	Water plantain	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> ND	Amaranths		1	1 ± NA
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Betulaceae	<i>Betula</i> ND	Birch		1	1 ± NA
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha rhomboidea</i>	Common threeseed mercury	FACU	3	1 ± 0
	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	Flower-of-an-hour		1	1 ± NA
Sapindaceae	<i>Acer saccharinum</i> *	Silver Maple	FACW	1	1 ± NA	
Malvaceae	ND	Mallows		1	1 ± NA	
2022		Submerged Vegetation			3	92 ± 4
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	13	54 ± 34
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	1	50 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus torreyi</i>	Torrey's Rush	FACW	1	50 ± NA
	Nelumbonaceae	<i>Nelumbo lutea</i>	American Lotus	OBL	1	50 ± NA

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Poaceae	<i>Hordeum</i> ND	Barley		1	50 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	3	48 ± 46
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> ND	Flatsedge		1	40 ± NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		1	40 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Desmodium canadense</i> *	Showy Tick Trefoil	FACU	3	38 ± 32
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i> *	Woolgrass	OBL	1	35 ± NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		6	31 ± 21
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	1	30 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Digitaria</i> ND	Crabgrass		1	30 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex comosa</i>	Longhair sedge	OBL	3	28 ± 25
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	9	28 ± 19
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	Pale Smartweed		7	28 ± 29
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia palustris</i>	Water purslane	OBL	1	25 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Guizotia abyssinica</i>	Ramtilla		3	22 ± 25
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Yellow Nutsedge	FACW	10	22 ± 25
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	1	20 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Paspalum</i> ND	Crowngrass		3	20 ± 28
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	1	20 ± NA
	Algae	ND	Algae		1	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia</i> ND	Ragweed		1	15 ± NA
Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		1	15 ± NA	
Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		1	15 ± NA	
Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus atrovirens</i> *	Dark Green Bulrush	OBL	1	15 ± NA	
Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia repens</i>	Creeping primrose-willow		1	15 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer</i> ND	Unk. Maple		9	15 ± 10
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria punctata</i>	Dotted smartweed	OBL	6	14 ± 5
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha virginica</i>	Virginia threeseed mercury	FACU	3	12 ± 11
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		4	12 ± 12
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	6	11 ± 12
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	10 ± NA
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha</i> ND	Copperleaf		1	10 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	FACU	3	10 ± 0
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	4	10 ± 10
	Verbenaceae	<i>Phyla lanceolata</i>	Lanceleaf fogfruit	OBL	1	10 ± NA
		Unknown			3	10 ± 7
	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		3	8 ± 4
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	FAC	4	8 ± 3
	Poaceae	<i>Poa</i> ND	Bluegrass		3	8 ± 4
	Violaceae	<i>Viola</i> ND	Violet		4	8 ± 3
		Seedlings			9	8 ± 4
	Lamiaceae	<i>Physostegia virginiana</i> *	Obedient Plant	FACW	4	6 ± 8
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		1	5 ± NA
	Campanulaceae	<i>Lobelia siphilitica</i>	Great Blue Lobelia	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	Strawcolored flatsedge	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus</i> ND	Rosemallow		1	5 ± NA
Salicaceae	<i>Populus</i> ND	Poplar/Cottonwood		4	5 ± 5	
Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	1	5 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Lamiaceae	ND	Mints		1	5 ± NA
	Malvaceae	ND	Mallows		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i> *	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	3	3 ± 3
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		1	1 ± NA
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	Creeping Jenny	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Fabaceae	ND	Legumes		1	1 ± NA
2023	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i> *	Woolgrass	OBL	1	95 ± NA
	Nelumbonaceae	<i>Nelumbo lutea</i>	American Lotus	OBL	1	85 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus torreyi</i>	Torrey's Rush	FACW	1	60 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia peploides</i>	Floating Primrose-willow	OBL	1	60 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Leersia oryzoides</i>	Rice Cutgrass	OBL	16	60 ± 45
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia palustris</i>	Water purslane	OBL	6	31 ± 46
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex hystericina</i>	Bottlebrush Sedge	OBL	3	30 ± 14
	Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii</i> *	Big Bluestem	FAC	4	20 ± 22
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria hydropiper</i>	Marshpepper knotweed	OBL	3	20 ± 14
	Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium coloratum</i>	Purpleleaf Willowherb	OBL	3	18 ± 11
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha virginica</i>	Virginia threeseed mercury	FACU	7	16 ± 25
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	1	15 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	3	15 ± 7
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton pusillus</i>	Slender pondweed	OBL	1	15 ± NA
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		1	15 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	3	12 ± 4
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	6	11 ± 12
Phrymaceae	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Square Stemmed Monkeyflower	OBL	1	10 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Poaceae	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> *	Switchgrass	FAC	1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		1	10 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Desmodium canadense</i> *	Showy Tick Trefoil	FACU	3	8 ± 4
	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus moscheutos</i> *	Swamp Rose Mallow	OBL	6	5 ± 4
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	Creeping Jenny	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Salix</i> ND	Willow		1	5 ± NA
		Seedlings			1	5 ± NA
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		4	4 ± 2
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens cernua</i>	Nodding Bur Marigold	OBL	3	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i>	American Burnweed		3	3 ± 3
	Balsaminaceae	<i>Impatiens capensis</i>	Jewelweed	FACW	3	3 ± 3
	Lamiaceae	<i>Physostegia virginiana</i> *	Obedient Plant	FACW	3	3 ± 3
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red maple	FAC	7	2 ± 2
	Acoraceae	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Sweetflag	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i> *	Common Milkweed	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens tripartita</i>	Threelobe beggarticks	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>	False Daisy	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Yellow Nutsedge	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		3	1 ± 0
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	1	1 ± NA
Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	1	1 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	American elm	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Phyla lanceolata</i>	Lanceleaf fogfruit	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		1	1 ± NA

Table C1.4. Project-level aboveground mean biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient content (% of dry mass) at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project for sampling years 2022–2023. Dashes indicate where data were not collected.

Biomass Type		2022			2023		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)	Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	978.94 ± 678.07 (n = 14)	1.28 ± 0.49 (n = 70)	0.27 ± 0.11 (n = 70)	429.23 ± 282.23 (n = 3)	1 ± 0.59 (n = 14)	0.22 ± 0.12 (n = 14)
	Detritus	175.87 ± 265.6 (n = 14)	–	–	23.68 ± NA (n = 1)	–	–

Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure C2.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project in 2023.

Figure C2.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project summarized for 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C2.1. Vegetation sampling effort at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project in 2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as detritus; at this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient concentration. Belowground biomass samples are taken in 2 depth intervals ranging from 0–15 cm in depth.

Sample Type	2023
Project Visits	2
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	25
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	16
Aboveground Samples	45
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	30
Belowground Samples	19
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	10

Table C2.2. List of morphospecies encountered at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project during 2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Algae	ND	Algae		12	50 \pm 26
	Typhaceae	ND	Cattails		36	41 \pm 29
	Asteraceae	<i>Coreopsis tinctoria</i>	Golden Tickseed	FACU	60	30 \pm 20
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	16	26 \pm 27
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i> *	White Clover	FACU	16	25 \pm 37
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Annual Ragweed	FACU	12	23 \pm 13
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	12	22 \pm 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia trifida</i>	Great Ragweed	FAC	8	18 \pm 11
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		64	16 \pm 18
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	FAC	4	15 \pm NA
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	8	12 \pm 4
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	Curly Dock	FAC	4	10 \pm NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa palustris</i>	Bog Yellowcress	OBL	36	9 \pm 7
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	20	8 \pm 4
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		24	7 \pm 5
	Asteraceae	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> *	Common Yarrow	FACU	4	5 \pm NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Rough cocklebur	FAC	4	5 \pm NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> ND	Flatsedge		4	5 \pm NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	4	5 \pm NA

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Fabaceae	<i>Medicago sativa</i> *	Alfalfa	FACU	4	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Lycopus americanus</i>	American Water Horehound	OBL	4	5 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Salix</i> ND	Willow		4	5 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	8	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		8	3 ± 3
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	8	1 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Packera</i> ND	Ragwort		4	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i> *	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	4	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Phleum pratense</i>	Timothy	FACU	4	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		4	1 ± NA

Table C2.3. Project-level mean above- and belowground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient concentration (% of dry mass) at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project for sampling year 2023. Dashes indicate where data were not collected.

Biomass Type		2023		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	N (%)	P (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	238.4 ± 240.31 (n = 15)	1.14 ± 0.57 (n = 44)	0.35 ± 0.23 (n = 44)
	Detritus	175.68 ± 209. (n = 13)	–	–
<i>Belowground</i>	0–5 cm	20.34 ± 13.08 (n = 11)	0.71 ± 0.34 (n = 11)	0.14 ± 0.15 (n = 11)
	5–15 cm	11.77 ± 8.49 (n = 11)	0.41 ± 0.03 (n = 11)	0.06 ± 0.01 (n = 11)

Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure C3.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project from 2021–2023.

Figure C3.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project for sampling year 2022. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C3.1. Vegetation sampling effort at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as detritus; at this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient concentration. Belowground biomass samples are taken in 2–3 depth intervals ranging from 0–25 cm in depth.

Sample Type	2021	2022	2023
Site Visits	2	11	2
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	41	106	30
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	–	49	–
Aboveground Samples	–	173	–
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	61	–
Belowground Samples	–	121	–
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	112	–

Table C3.2. List of morphospecies encountered at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project during 2021–2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	Creeping Jenny	FACW	1	85 \pm NA
	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> ND	Blackberry		1	70 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa-Setaria</i> spp.	Grasses		1	60 \pm 14
	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus</i> ND	Teasel		4	53 \pm 29
		Unknown			2	52 \pm 36
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		3	47 \pm 35
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		1	45 \pm 21
	Onagraceae	<i>Oenothera biennis</i>	Common evening primrose	FACU	1	45 \pm NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		1	40 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		2	35 \pm 15
	Rubiaceae	<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i>	Common buttonbush	OBL	1	35 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		6	32 \pm 12
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia</i> ND	Ragweed		4	30 \pm 16
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		3	28 \pm 8
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	2	27 \pm 8
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	1	25 \pm NA
	Algae	ND	Algae		4	24 \pm 18
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	2	21 \pm 5
Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle	FACU	1	20 \pm NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	20 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		1	20 ± 0
	Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i> ND	Grape		1	20 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens-pratense</i>	Clovers		1	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Echinacea purpurea</i> *	Eastern purple coneflower		1	15 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Pycnanthemum</i> ND	Mountainmint		1	15 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	Strawcolored flatsedge	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus pumila</i>	Siberian elm		1	1 ± 0
2022	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa muricata</i>	American Barnyard Grass	OBL	1	90 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Pycnanthemum tenuifolium</i> *	Narrow-Leaved Mountain Mint	FAC	1	85 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	1	85 ± NA
	Rubiaceae	ND	Madders		1	65 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Echinacea</i> ND	Purple Coneflower		1	60 ± NA
	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i>	Cutleaf Teasel	UPL	5	54 ± 35
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		18	53 ± 27
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		1	40 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i> *	Soft Rush	OBL	2	37 ± 39
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		7	31 ± 23
	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus argutus</i>	Sawtooth Blackberry		4	30 ± 20
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i> *	Woolgrass	OBL	1	30 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum</i> ND	Panic grass		1	30 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		24	29 ± 27
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	Creeping Jenny	FACW	6	29 ± 23
Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus</i> ND	Teasel		28	28 ± 21	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Algae	ND	Algae		10	26 ± 20
	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus fullonum</i>	Fuller's Teasel	FACU	1	25 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Oenothera gaura</i>	Biennial Gaura		1	25 ± 7
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	6	23 ± 25
	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> ND	Blackberry		7	23 ± 21
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	26	22 ± 23
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		1	22 ± 25
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus atrovirens</i> *	Dark Green Bulrush	OBL	8	21 ± 25
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	12	21 ± 18
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		37	21 ± 22
	Anacardiaceae	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	Eastern Poison Ivy	FAC	1	20 ± 28
	Poaceae	<i>Agrostis</i> ND	Bentgrass		1	20 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Dactylis</i> ND	Orchardgrass		1	20 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		1	20 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria punctata</i>	Dotted smartweed	OBL	1	20 ± NA
	Apiaceae	<i>Daucus carota</i>	Queen Anne's Lace	UPL	2	19 ± 20
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle	FACU	5	19 ± 17
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	2	18 ± 19
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		33	18 ± 16
	Fabaceae	<i>Melilotus</i> ND	Sweetclover		1	18 ± 11
	Poaceae	<i>Bromus</i> ND	Brome		3	18 ± 26
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		1	18 ± 4
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	FACU	8	17 ± 16
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus</i> ND	Bulrush		3	16 ± 11

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	American elm	FACW	5	16 ± 11
	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> ND	Elm		4	16 ± 11
	Asparagaceae	<i>Polygonatum</i> ND	Solomon's Seal		1	15 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		6	15 ± 20
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	Canada Goldenrod	FACU	1	15 ± NA
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus sericea</i>	Red-Osier Dogwood		1	15 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Melilotus officinalis</i>	Sweetclover	FACU	2	15 ± 10
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	1	15 ± 14
	Poaceae	<i>Lolium</i> ND	Ryegrass		1	15 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	3	14 ± 19
	Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum</i> ND	Knotweed		2	14 ± 23
	Lamiaceae	<i>Pycnanthemum muticum</i>	Clustered mountainmint	FAC	2	13 ± 14
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i> *	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	20	12 ± 11
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	7	12 ± 11
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		2	12 ± 10
	Rubiaceae	<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i>	Common buttonbush	OBL	1	12 ± 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	Eastern daisy fleabane	FACU	18	11 ± 12
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		7	11 ± 15
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium</i> ND	Thistle		1	10 ± 7
	Asteraceae	<i>Crepis capillaris</i>	Smooth Hawksbeard	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Euthamia graminifolia</i>	Flat-Topped Goldentop	FACW	2	10 ± 7
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia</i> ND	Coneflowers		6	10 ± 10
	Convolvulaceae	<i>Calystegia sepium</i>	Hedge False Bindweed	FAC	1	10 ± NA
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	Strawcolored flatsedge	FACW	2	10 ± 5	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	7	10 ± 6
	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus rubra</i>	Northern Red Oak	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		4	10 ± 8
	Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus americana</i>	White Ash	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Oenothera biennis</i>	Common evening primrose	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Chasmanthium</i> ND	Woodoats		1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus</i> ND	Wildrye		1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Phleum pratense</i>	Timothy	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus pubescens</i>	Dwarf Red Blackberry	FACW	1	10 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena urticifolia</i>	White Vervain	FAC	1	10 ± NA
	Bryophyta	ND	Mosses		1	10 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum</i> ND	Aster		3	9 ± 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		2	9 ± 7
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista</i> ND	Sensitive Pea		3	9 ± 6
	Fabaceae	<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	Black Medick	FACU	3	9 ± 15
	Onagraceae	<i>Oenothera</i> ND	Evening Primrose		2	9 ± 10
	Apiaceae	ND	Umbellifers		30	9 ± 8
			Seedlings		7	9 ± 6
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		1	8 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex stricta</i>	Upright Sedge	OBL	1	8 ± 4
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	FAC	2	8 ± 3
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> ND	Docks and sorrels		4	8 ± 10
Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron</i> ND	Fleabanes		7	7 ± 7	
Convolvulaceae	<i>Calystegia</i> ND	False Bindweed		3	6 ± 8	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer saccharinum</i>	Silver Maple	FACW	2	6 ± 4
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		9	6 ± 6
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma</i> ND	Water plantain	OBL	1	5 ± 0
	Apocynaceae	<i>Apocynum cannabinum</i>	Indianhemp		4	5 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia</i> ND	Ragweed		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Aster puniceus</i> *	Purplestem Aster	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i> *	False Sunflower	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Ratibida columnifera</i>	Upright Prairie Coneflower		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia laciniata</i>	Cutleaf Coneflower	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa</i> ND	Yellowcress		1	5 ± NA
	Cannabaceae	<i>Celtis occidentalis</i>	Common Hackberry	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera</i> ND	Honeysuckle		1	5 ± 0
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus</i> ND	Dogwood		1	5 ± 0
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus pendulus</i>	Rufous Bulrush	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Elaeagnaceae	<i>Elaeagnus umbellata</i>	Autumn olive		1	5 ± NA
	Juglandaceae	<i>Juglans</i> ND	Walnut		1	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Lycopus americanus</i>	American Water Horehound	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Monarda</i> ND	Beebalm		1	5 ± 0
	Lamiaceae	<i>Physostegia</i> ND	Lionsheart		1	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Physostegia virginiana</i> *	Obedient Plant	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Magnoliaceae	<i>Liriodendron</i> ND	Tulip Tree		1	5 ± NA
Magnoliaceae	<i>Liriodendron tulipifera</i>	Tulip Tree	FACU	1	5 ± NA	
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago</i> ND	Plantains		3	5 ± 5	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Platanaceae	<i>Platanus occidentalis</i>	American Sycamore	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Chasmanthium latifolium</i> *	River Oats	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium</i> ND	Rosette Grass		1	5 ± 0
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> *	Switchgrass	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	Yellow Foxtail		1	5 ± NA
	Rosaceae	<i>Potentilla</i> ND	Cinquefoil		3	5 ± 4
	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa setigera</i>	Climbing Rose	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena</i> ND	Vervain		2	5 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Lactuca canadensis</i>	Canada Lettuce		1	5 ± NA
		Unknown			3	5 ± 4
	Euphorbiaceae	ND	Spurges		1	5 ± NA
		Unknown			1	5 ± NA
	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus</i> ND	Oaks		2	4 ± 5
	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		8	4 ± 4
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia</i> ND	Yellow Loosestrife		2	4 ± 4
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer</i> ND	Unk. Maple		2	4 ± 7
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus racemosa</i>	Gray Dogwood	FAC	1	3 ± 3
	Lamiaceae	<i>Monarda fistulosa</i> *	Wild Bergamot	FACU	3	3 ± 2
	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium clandestinum</i>	Deer-tongue Grass	FACW	1	3 ± 3
	Rosaceae	<i>Agrimonia</i> ND	Agrimony		1	3 ± 3
	Rosaceae	<i>Potentilla norvegica</i>	Norwegian cinquefoil	FAC	3	3 ± 2
	Salicaceae	<i>Salix</i> ND	Willow		1	3 ± 3
Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red maple	FAC	2	3 ± 2	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Violaceae	<i>Viola</i> ND	Violet		2	3 ± 4
	Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i> ND	Grape		1	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Conyza</i> ND	Horseweed		3	3 ± 2
	Poaceae	<i>Hordeum</i> ND	Barley		2	2 ± 2
	Rosaceae	<i>Geum</i> ND	Avens		3	2 ± 2
	Lamiaceae	ND	Mints		2	2 ± 2
	Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria</i> ND	Arrowhead		1	1 ± NA
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias</i> ND	Milkweed		1	1 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia trifida</i>	Great Ragweed	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Coreopsis</i> ND	Tickseed		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Echinacea purpurea</i> *	Eastern purple coneflower		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus</i> ND	Sunflower		1	1 ± NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Lepidium</i> ND	Pepperweed		1	1 ± NA
	Clusiaceae	<i>Hypericum mutilum</i>	Dwarf St. Johnswort	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus sanguinea</i>	Bloodtwig Dogwood		1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex molesta</i>	Troublesome sedge	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i>	Honeylocust	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> ND	Water purslane		1	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Arthraxon</i> ND	Carpetgrass		1	1 ± NA
Poaceae	<i>Elymus repens</i>	Quackgrass	FACU	1	1 ± NA	
Poaceae	<i>Sorghastrum nutans</i> *	Indiangrass	FACU	1	1 ± NA	
Rosaceae	<i>Fragaria</i> ND	Strawberry		2	1 ± 0	
Rosaceae	<i>Geum macrophyllum</i>	Largeleaf Avens		1	1 ± 0	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
	Malvaceae	ND	Mallows		1	1 ± NA
	Rosaceae	ND	Roses		1	1 ± NA
2023	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	5	53 ± 37
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		6	46 ± 28
	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i>	Cutleaf Teasel	UPL	2	42 ± 38
	Lamiaceae	<i>Pycnanthemum muticum</i>	Clustered mountainmint	FAC	1	40 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	Reed Canary Grass	FACW	2	40 ± 45
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens aristosa</i> *	Tickseed Sunflower	FACW	2	38 ± 10
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i> *	Woolgrass	OBL	1	36 ± 49
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	3	31 ± 24
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		1	30 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens cernua</i> *	Nodding Bur Marigold	OBL	2	29 ± 32
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	2	23 ± 20
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	3	22 ± 43
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	2	22 ± 12
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	3	18 ± 22
	Asteraceae	<i>Erechtites hieracifolius</i>	American Burnweed		1	15 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Euthamia graminifolia</i>	Flat-Topped Goldentop	FACW	1	15 ± NA
	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	American elm	FACW	1	15 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	Yellow Foxtail		3	13 ± 15
	Rubiaceae	<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i>	Common buttonbush	OBL	1	12 ± 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	Canada Goldenrod	FACU	2	11 ± 6
Poaceae	<i>Setaria faberi</i>	Japanese bristlegrass	FACU	3	11 ± 8	
Poaceae	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> *	Switchgrass	FAC	1	10 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus sericea</i>	Red-Osier Dogwood		1	8 ± 4
	Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium coloratum</i>	Purpleleaf Willowherb	OBL	1	8 ± 10
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides*</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	1	8 ± 4
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria hydropiper</i>	Marshpepper knotweed	OBL	2	7 ± 11
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		2	5 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus atrovirens*</i>	Dark Green Bulrush	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria pensylvanica</i>	Pennsylvania Smartweed	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Salix nigra</i>	Black willow	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum carolinense</i>	Virginia horsenettle	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum</i> ND	Nightshade		1	5 ± 0
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		2	5 ± 0
	Rubiaceae	ND	Madders		1	5 ± NA
	Apiaceae	<i>Daucus carota</i>	Queen Anne's Lace	UPL	2	4 ± 2
	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus fullonum</i>	Fuller's Teasel	FACU	3	4 ± 4
		<i>Seedlings</i>			5	4 ± 4
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	FACU	1	3 ± 3
	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> ND	Blackberry		1	3 ± 3
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		2	3 ± 2
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Annual Ragweed	FACU	3	2 ± 2	
Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	2	2 ± 2	
Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red maple	FAC	3	2 ± 2	
Apocynaceae	<i>Apocynum cannabinum</i>	Indianhemp		1	1 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i> *	Common Milkweed	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum</i> ND	Aster		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		1	1 ± 0
	Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus</i> ND	Bindweed		1	1 ± NA
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus racemosa</i>	Gray Dogwood	FAC	1	1 ± 0
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		1	1 ± NA
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia nutans</i>	Eyebane	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	2	1 ± 0
	Rosaceae	<i>Potentilla</i> ND	Cinquefoil		1	1 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	1	1 ± NA
			Unknown		1	1 ± NA

Table C3.3. Project-level mean above- and belowground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient concentration (% of dry mass) at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project for sampling year 2022. Dashes indicate where data were not collected.

Biomass Type		2022		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	1537.99 ± 1830.09 (n = 48)	0.3 ± 0.11 (n = 138)	1.06 ± 0.39 (n = 138)
	Detritus	762.8 ± 735.45 (n = 43)	–	–
<i>Belowground</i>	0–5 cm	51.21 ± 46.26 (n = 50)	0.13 ± 0.06 (n = 50)	0.71 ± 0.32 (n = 50)
	5–15 cm	38.35 ± 47.21 (n = 45)	0.09 ± 0.06 (n = 45)	0.61 ± 0.33 (n = 45)
	15–25 cm	20.72 ± 19.24 (n = 37)	0.07 ± 0.04 (n = 37)	0.52 ± 0.31 (n = 37)

Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

Figure C4.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project for sampling year 2023.

Figure C4.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project summarized for sampling year 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C4.1. Vegetation sampling effort at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project in 2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.3x1 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as floating aquatic vegetation. Belowground biomass samples were not taken.

Sample Type	2023
Site Visits	4
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	18
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	11
Aboveground Samples	36
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Content	16
Belowground Samples	–
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Content	–

Table C4.2. List of morphospecies encountered at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project during 2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Haloragaceae	<i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i>	Eurasian watermilfoil	OBL	1	80 \pm NA
	Pontederiaceae	<i>Pontederia cordata</i>	Pickerelweed	OBL	1	80 \pm NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria hydropiperoides</i>	Swamp smartweed	OBL	1	70 \pm NA
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		1	40 \pm NA
		Unknown			1	40 \pm NA
	Hydrocharitaceae	<i>Hydrocharis morsus-ranae</i>	Common frogbit	OBL	3	25 \pm 5
	Nymphaeaceae	<i>Nuphar</i> ND	Waterlily		1	25 \pm NA
	Hydrocharitaceae	<i>Elodea canadensis</i>	American waterweed	OBL	1	20 \pm NA
	Nymphaeaceae	<i>Nymphaea odorata</i>	American White Waterlily	OBL	2	20 \pm 7
	Nymphaeaceae	<i>Nymphaea</i> ND	Waterlily		1	15 \pm NA
Hydrocharitaceae	<i>Elodea</i> sp.	Waterweed		1	10 \pm NA	

Table C4.3. Project-level mean aboveground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient content (% of dry mass) at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project for sampling year 2023.

Biomass Type		2023		
		Biomass (g/m²)	N (%)	P (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	1372.68 ± 850.81 (n = 9)	1.74 ± 0.27 (n = 32)	0.33 ± 0.09 (n = 32)

Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East (OAKE)

Figure C5.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East from 2021–2023.

Figure C5.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East summarized across 2021–2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C5.1. Vegetation sampling effort at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East from 2021–2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as detritus; at this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient content. Belowground biomass samples are taken in 2–3 depth intervals ranging from 5–25 cm in depth.

Sample Type	2021	2022	2023
Site Visits	3	4	2
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	41	49	33
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	–	21	17
Aboveground Samples	–	66	55
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Content	–	42	38
Belowground Samples	–	57	17
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Content	–	51	10

Table C5.2. List of morphospecies encountered at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East during 2021–2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa-Setaria</i> ND	Grasses		1	90 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii</i> ; <i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Grasses		1	65 \pm NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		7	64 \pm 22
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		19	53 \pm 27
	Poaceae	<i>Avena sativa</i> ; <i>Setaria-Echinochloa</i> ND	Grasses		1	50 \pm NA
	Apocynaceae	<i>Apocynum cannabinum</i>	Indian Hemp		1	45 \pm NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium</i> ND	Thistle		1	40 \pm NA
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Atriplex prostrata</i>	Triangle orache		1	30 \pm NA
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia coccinea</i>	Valley Redstem	OBL	2	28 \pm 32
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		3	26 \pm 20
	Poaceae	<i>Hordeum jubatum</i>	Foxtail barley	FAC	1	20 \pm NA
	Pontederiaceae	<i>Pontederia cordata</i>	Pickernelweed	OBL	1	20 \pm NA
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	1	15 \pm NA
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> ND	Amaranths		1	15 \pm NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		2	13 \pm 17
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		2	10 \pm 13
			Unknown		5	10 \pm 10
	Algae	ND	Algae		4	7 \pm 5
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Yellow Nutsedge	FACW	1	1 \pm NA

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus</i> ND	Teasel		2	1 ± 0
	Poaceae	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	Hairy Crabgrass	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton nodosus</i>	Longleaf Pondweed	OBL	1	1 ± NA
2022	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	100 ± NA
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton nodosus</i>	Longleaf Pondweed	OBL	6	86 ± 12
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		1	65 ± NA
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton</i> ND	Pondweed		3	60 ± 41
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	25	55 ± 31
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lupulina</i>	Hop Sedge	OBL	1	40 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i>	Common Spikerush	OBL	1	35 ± NA
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		6	34 ± 26
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	17	33 ± 30
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	2	30 ± 28
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis erythropoda</i>	Bald Spikerush		2	30 ± 7
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	5	30 ± 29
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		6	27 ± 28
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		1	25 ± NA
	Algae	ND	Algae		5	24 ± 33
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	4	21 ± 24
	Bryophyta	ND	Mosses		3	21 ± 26
Cyperaceae	<i>Carex hystericina</i>	Bottlebrush Sedge	OBL	2	20 ± 14	
Poaceae	<i>Poa</i> ND	Bluegrass		1	20 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	7	19 ± 17
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		2	18 ± 14
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i> *	Soft Rush	OBL	2	18 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex comosa</i>	Longhair sedge	OBL	1	15 ± NA
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton natans</i>	Floating Pondweed	OBL	1	15 ± NA
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	8	11 ± 7
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		2	10 ± 7
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		2	10 ± 7
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		1	10 ± NA
	Asteraceae	ND	Grasses		7	9 ± 11
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria parviflora</i>	Marsh bristlegrass	FAC	2	7 ± 7
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	Pale Smartweed		2	6 ± 6
	Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria latifolia</i>	Broadleaf arrowhead	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus</i> ND	Dogwood		1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> ND	Flatsedge		2	5 ± 0
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	3	5 ± 0
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia robusta</i>	Grand redstems	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia</i> ND	Redstem		1	5 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	Flower-of-an-hour		1	5 ± NA
	Phrymaceae	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Square Stemmed Monkeyflower	OBL	4	5 ± 6
Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	1	5 ± NA	
		Unknown		2	5 ± 5	
Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	6	4 ± 3	
Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf	FACU	2	3 ± 3	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	Yellow Foxtail		3	3 ± 4
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		2	3 ± 3
		Seedlings			15	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		2	2 ± 2
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i>	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus odoratus</i>	Fragrant flatsedge	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	Curly Dock	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Veronica scutellata</i>	Skullcap speedwell	OBL	1	1 ± NA
Lamiaceae	ND	Mints		2	1 ± 0	
	Unknown			1	1 ± NA	
2023	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex hystericina</i>	Bottlebrush Sedge	OBL	1	60 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	4	45 ± 38
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		1	40 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i>	Woolgrass	OBL	2	33 ± 6
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i>	Common Spikerush	OBL	2	32 ± 50
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	19	25 ± 21
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		4	20 ± 28
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		22	19 ± 17
	Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	Eastern daisy fleabane	FACU	2	18 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	11	16 ± 17
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Annual Ragweed	FACU	1	15 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	2	15 ± 0

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	1	15 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	2	15 ± 7
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		1	15 ± NA
	Phrymaceae	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Square Stemmed Monkeyflower	OBL	2	12 ± 3
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton natans</i>	Floating Pondweed	OBL	3	12 ± 8
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	10 ± NA
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	5	10 ± 8
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		3	10 ± 10
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i>	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago altissima</i>	Canada Goldenrod		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus</i> ND	Bulrushes		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum</i> ND	American Asters		2	4 ± 2
	Asteraceae	ND	Grasses		7	4 ± 3
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	2	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Rough cocklebur	FAC	2	1 ± 0
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf	FACU	9	1 ± 1
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	Curly Dock	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	1	1 ± NA
Malvaceae	ND	Mallows		1	1 ± NA	
		Unknown		1	1 ± NA	

Table C5.3. Project-level mean above- and belowground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient content (% of dry mass) at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East for years 2021–2023. Dashes indicate where data were not collected.

Biomass Type		2022			2023		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	N (%)	P (%)	Biomass (g/m ²)	N (%)	P (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	483.89 ± 250.63 (n = 20)	0.96 ± 0.42 (n = 81)	0.32 ± 0.13 (n = 81)	294.96 ± 302.25 (n = 17)	1.06 ± 0.39 (n = 67)	0.36 ± 0.18 (n = 67)
	Detritus	175.9 ± 186.38 (n = 20)	–	–	361.7 ± 333.32 (n = 15)	–	–
<i>Belowground</i>	0–5 cm	44.76 ± 36.43 (n = 20)	0.67 ± 0.33 (n = 20)	0.11 ± 0.06 (n = 20)	112.65 ± 151.79 (n = 7)	0.75 ± 0.24 (n = 7)	0.15 ± 0.07 (n = 7)
	5–15 cm	21.02 ± 15.11 (n = 20)	0.57 ± 0.29 (n = 20)	0.08 ± 0.06 (n = 20)	34.22 ± 36.82 (n = 7)	0.85 ± 0.53 (n = 7)	0.09 ± 0.02 (n = 7)
	15–25 cm	15.78 ± 23.17 (n = 18)	0.66 ± 0.19 (n = 18)	0.08 ± 0.04 (n = 18)	–	–	–

Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West (OAKW)

Figure C6.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West from 2021–2023.

Figure C6.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West summarized across 2021–2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C6.1. Vegetation sampling effort at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West from 2021–2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as detritus; at this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient concentration. Belowground biomass samples are taken in 2–3 depth intervals ranging from 0–25 cm in depth.

Sample Type	2021	2022	2023
Site Visits	2	3	4
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	51	29	33
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	–	22	19
Aboveground Samples	–	73	45
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	49	29
Belowground Samples	–	42	21
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	37	14

Table C6.2. List of morphospecies encountered at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West during 2021–2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		1	80 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	1	50 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		32	46 \pm 28
	Pontederiaceae	<i>Pontederia cordata</i>	Pickernelweed	OBL	1	40 \pm NA
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	4	36 \pm 18
	Algae	ND	Algae		5	34 \pm 30
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	5	32 \pm 15
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		1	30 \pm NA
		Unknown			6	26 \pm 11
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		8	23 \pm 17
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	20 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa muricata</i> *	American Barnyard Grass	OBL	1	20 \pm NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		3	18 \pm 13
	Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria latifolia</i>	Broadleaf arrowhead	OBL	3	17 \pm 6
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		3	17 \pm 3
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	2	12 \pm 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle	FACU	2	10 \pm 13
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia</i> ND	False Pimpernel		2	10 \pm 0
	Najadaceae	<i>Najas minor</i>	Brittle waternymph	OBL	1	10 \pm NA

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		2	6 ± 6
	Asteraceae	<i>Euthamia graminifolia</i>	Flat-Topped Goldentop	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		1	1 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		1	1 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria faberi</i>	Japanese bristlegrass	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	Yellow Foxtail		1	1 ± NA
2022	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	7	57 ± 29
	Algae	ND	Algae		2	40 ± 0
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		9	38 ± 24
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	10	34 ± 26
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum</i> ND	Aster		1	30 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	1	30 ± NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		14	26 ± 21
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		4	25 ± 10
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton</i> ND	Pondweed		1	25 ± NA
		Unknown			4	23 ± 32
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		9	20 ± 20
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		2	20 ± 7
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i> *	Soft Rush	OBL	2	20 ± 7
	Salicaceae	<i>Salix</i> ND	Willow		1	20 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		1	20 ± NA
Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus</i> ND	Bulrush		3	18 ± 10	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	5	18 ± 18
	Pontederiaceae	<i>Pontederia cordata</i>	Pickernelweed	OBL	2	18 ± 11
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	5	17 ± 21
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	9	15 ± 11
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Shallow Sedge	OBL	1	15 ± NA
		Unknown			4	11 ± 6
	Phrymaceae	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Square Stemmed Monkeyflower	OBL	2	10 ± 7
	Poaceae	<i>Hordeum</i> ND	Barley		1	10 ± NA
	Rosaceae	<i>Geum macrophyllum</i>	Largeleaf Avens		1	10 ± NA
		Seedlings			14	10 ± 12
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		2	8 ± 10
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		5	7 ± 8
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	2	6 ± 6
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i> *	Fox Sedge	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus</i> ND	Bulrush		1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton natans</i>	Floating Pondweed	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		2	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Rough cocklebur	FAC	3	2 ± 2
	Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	Eastern daisy fleabane	FACU	1	1 ± NA
Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium</i> ND	Cocklebur		1	1 ± NA	
Lamiaceae	<i>Lycopus</i> ND	Waterhorehound		1	1 ± NA	
Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium clandestinum</i>	Deer-tongue Grass	FACW	1	1 ± NA	
Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		1	1 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		1	1 ± NA
2023	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i> *	Soft Rush	OBL	4	65 ± 29
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton natans</i>	Floating Pondweed	OBL	4	52 ± 53
	Acoraceae	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Sweetflag	OBL	1	50 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i>	Woolgrass	OBL	5	44 ± 24
		Unknown				2
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex scoparia</i>	Blunt Broom Sedge	FACW	2	40 ± 56
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		2	35 ± 35
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		16	34 ± 21
	Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria latifolia</i>	Broadleaf arrowhead	OBL	4	29 ± 13
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphotrichum</i> ND	Aster		2	22 ± 25
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		22	13 ± 13
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	14	12 ± 15
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	2	12 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Shallow Sedge	OBL	4	12 ± 9
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	8	12 ± 17
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	1	10 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		8	9 ± 15
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		2	8 ± 10
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i> *	Fox Sedge	FACW	2	6 ± 6
Phrymaceae	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Square Stemmed Monkeyflower	OBL	2	6 ± 6	
Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	1	5 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i>	Common Spikerush	OBL	2	5 ± 0
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	Reed Canary Grass	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i> *	Red maple	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	7	4 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Rough cocklebur	FAC	4	3 ± 2
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Annual Ragweed	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis compressa</i>	Flatstem spikerush	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	2	1 ± 0
	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum carolinense</i>	Virginia horsenettle	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		2	1 ± 0

Table C6.3. Project-level mean above- and belowground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient concentration (% of dry mass) at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West for years 2021–2023. Dashes indicate where no data were collected.

Biomass Type		2022			2023		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)	Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	743.69 ± 813.23 (n = 22)	0.39 ± 0.15 (n = 89)	1.18 ± 0.57 (n = 89)	710 ± 809.23 (n = 17)	0.38 ± 0.18 (n = 62)	1.13 ± 0.51 (n = 62)
	Detritus	200.5 ± 152.29 (n = 22)	–	–	409.38 ± 295.52 (n = 11)	–	–
<i>Belowground</i>	0–5 cm	42.3 ± 40.76 (n = 16)	0.16 ± 0.1 (n = 16)	0.65 ± 0.26 (n = 16)	85.33 ± 44.46 (n = 7)	0.14 ± 0.05 (n = 7)	0.55 ± 0.18 (n = 7)
	5–15 cm	24.82 ± 14.73 (n = 15)	0.15 ± 0.11 (n = 15)	0.7 ± 0.31 (n = 15)	77.92 ± 59.6 (n = 11)	0.09 ± 0.05 (n = 11)	0.42 ± 0.16 (n = 11)
	15–25 cm	12.7 ± 12.27 (n = 11)	0.16 ± 0.12 (n = 11)	0.65 ± 0.24 (n = 11)	–	–	–

Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Figure C7.1. Map of Sampling Locations at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project from 2022–2023.

Figure C7.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project summarized for 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C7.1. Vegetation sampling effort at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project from 2022–2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as detritus; at this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient concentration. Belowground biomass samples are taken in 2 depth intervals ranging from 0–15 cm in depth.

Sample Type	2022	2023
Site Visits	1	2
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	31	32
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	10	17
Aboveground Samples	10*	55
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	10*	39
Belowground Samples	–	19
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	19

* Samples not separated by species

Table C7.2. List of morphospecies encountered at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project during 2022–2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Pontederiaceae	<i>Pontederia</i> ND	Pickerelweed		2	65 \pm NA
	Algae	ND	Algae		18	51 \pm 26
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		3	50 \pm 57
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma</i> ND	Water plantain	OBL	3	45 \pm 21
	Poaceae	<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	Reed Canary Grass	FACW	2	40 \pm NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	5	35 \pm 5
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	2	35 \pm NA
	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Veronica arvensis</i>	Corn speedwell	FACU	2	35 \pm NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grass		6	35 \pm 17
	Poaceae	ND	Grass		19	33 \pm 29
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium</i> ND	Thistle		5	30 \pm 23
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	2	30 \pm NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus</i> ND	Bulrush		2	30 \pm NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Teucrium canadense</i>	Canada germander	FACW	2	30 \pm NA
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		23	29 \pm 15
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	3	28 \pm 4
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago</i> ND	Plantains		18	26 \pm 26
	Lamiaceae	<i>Stachys palustris</i>	Marsh Hedgenettle	OBL	2	25 \pm NA
Anacardiaceae	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	Eastern Poison Ivy	FAC	2	20 \pm NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Poaceae	<i>Phalaris</i> ND	Canary Grass		2	20 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	2	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		3	16 ± 21
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	2	15 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		2	15 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	2	15 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Secale</i> ND	Rye		2	15 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Conyza</i> ND	Horseweed		2	15 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	5	12 ± 16
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton</i> ND	Pondweed		6	12 ± 16
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	3	12 ± 11
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle	FACU	8	10 ± 10
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	Canada Goldenrod	FACU	2	10 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Shallow Sedge	OBL	6	10 ± 10
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex scoparia</i>	Blunt Broom Sedge	FACW	5	10 ± 9
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis obtusa</i>	Blunt Spikerush	OBL	2	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Agrostis</i> ND	Bentgrass		2	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus repens</i>	Quackgrass	FACU	2	10 ± NA
	Apiaceae	ND	Umbellifers		5	10 ± 10
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		11	9 ± 8
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		8	8 ± 4
	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium clandestinum</i>	Deer-tongue Grass	FACW	6	6 ± 6
	Asteraceae	<i>Helenium</i> ND	Sneezeweed		2	5 ± NA
Asteraceae	<i>Senecio</i> ND	Ragwort		2	5 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	FACU	2	5 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	2	5 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum lapathifolia</i>	Pale Smartweed	FACW	2	5 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> ND	Docks and sorrels		2	5 ± NA
	Ranunculaceae	<i>Ranunculus</i> ND	Buttercup		2	5 ± NA
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer negundo</i>	Boxelder Maple	FAC	2	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	ND	Mints		2	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus pungens</i>	Common three-square bulrush		2	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		6	3 ± 2
	Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium leptophyllum</i>	Bog Willowherb	OBL	3	3 ± 3
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum</i> ND	Penthorum		3	3 ± 3
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		5	2 ± 2
	Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron</i> ND	Fleabanes		2	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Packera aurea</i>	Golden ragwort	FACW	2	1 ± NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa palustris</i>	Bog Yellowcress	OBL	2	1 ± NA
	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Cerastium</i> ND	Mouse-ear chickweed		2	1 ± NA
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus</i> ND	Dogwood		3	1 ± 0
	Lamiaceae	<i>Monarda fistulosa</i> *	Wild Bergamot	FACU	2	1 ± NA
	Moraceae	<i>Morus</i> ND	Mulberries		2	1 ± NA
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	Narrowleaf Plantain	FACU	2	1 ± NA
Ranunculaceae	<i>Ranunculus sceleratus</i>	Cursed buttercup	OBL	2	1 ± NA	
Salicaceae	<i>Populus</i> ND	Poplar/Cottonwood		2	1 ± NA	
Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> ND	Elm		2	1 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata*</i>	Partridge pea	FACU	11	44 ± 38
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	8	38 ± 23
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex hystericina</i>	Bottlebrush Sedge	OBL	2	35 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus torreyi</i>	Torrey's Rush	FACW	2	35 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i>	Soft Rush	OBL	5	34 ± 41
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Barnyard Millet	FACW	16	28 ± 22
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Path Rush	FAC	2	25 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	6	21 ± 32
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		32	20 ± 14
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	Yellow Foxtail		5	18 ± 12
	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium clandestinum</i>	Deer-tongue Grass	FACW	8	16 ± 25
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens cernua</i>	Nodding Bur Marigold	OBL	5	15 ± 17
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	8	15 ± 8
	Fabaceae	<i>Desmodium paniculatum</i>	Panickedleaf ticktrefoil	FACU	2	15 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	Strawcolored flatsedge	FACW	5	11 ± 17
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Yellow Nutsedge	FACW	10	10 ± 13
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha virginica</i>	Virginia threeseed mercury	FACU	2	10 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	3	10 ± 7
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	Pale smartweed		2	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		21	10 ± 8
	Asteraceae	<i>Eupatorium perfoliatum*</i>	Common Boneset	OBL	15	9 ± 8
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex scoparia</i>	Blunt Broom Sedge	FACW	11	9 ± 8
	Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii*</i>	Big Bluestem	FAC	6	9 ± 5
Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata*</i>	Blue vervain	FACW	6	9 ± 6	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Asteraceae	<i>Helenium autumnale</i> *	Common Sneezeweed	FACW	5	8 ± 6
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Shallow Sedge	OBL	8	8 ± 12
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	6	8 ± 11
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia coccinea</i>	Valley Redstem	OBL	3	6 ± 6
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	6	6 ± 7
	Poaceae	<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	Reed Canary Grass	FACW	3	6 ± 6
		<i>Seedlings</i>			8	6 ± 5
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	6	5 ± 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium</i> ND	Thistle		5	5 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron</i> ND	Fleabanes		2	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum novae-angliae</i>	New England Aster	FACW	2	5 ± NA
	Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Field Horsetail	FAC	2	5 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	FACU	2	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Monarda fistulosa</i> *	Wild Bergamot	FACU	2	5 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Pycnanthemum tenuifolium</i>	Narrow-Leaved Mountain Mint	FAC	2	5 ± NA
	Phrymaceae	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Square Stemmed Monkeyflower	OBL	2	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		2	5 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		2	5 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium coloratum</i>	Purpleleaf Willowherb	OBL	5	4 ± 2
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		3	3 ± 3
Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	Softstem Bulrush	OBL	3	3 ± 3	
Solanaceae	<i>Solanum americanum</i>	American black nightshade		3	3 ± 3	
	<i>Unknown</i>			3	3 ± 3	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	American water plantain	OBL	16	2 ± 2
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa palustris</i>	Bog Yellowcress	OBL	5	2 ± 2
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus hybridus</i>	Slim Amaranth		2	1 ± NA
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> ND	Amaranths		2	1 ± NA
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Lambsquarters	FACU	2	1 ± NA
	Apiaceae	<i>Daucus carota</i>	Queen Anne's Lace	UPL	2	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i> *	False Sunflower	FACU	6	1 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphotrichum</i> ND	Aster		3	1 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		2	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Rough cocklebur	FAC	2	1 ± NA
	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus racemosa</i>	Gray Dogwood	FAC	2	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus odoratus</i>	Fragrant flatsedge	FACW	2	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Schoenoplectiella mucronata</i>	Bog Bulrush		3	1 ± 0
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia nutans</i>	Eyebane	FACU	2	1 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus canadensis</i>	Canadian rush	OBL	2	1 ± NA
	Lamiaceae	<i>Lycopus americanus</i>	American Water Horehound	OBL	2	1 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia palustris</i>	Water purslane	OBL	2	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> *	Switchgrass	FAC	2	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria faberi</i>	Japanese bristlegrass	FACU	2	1 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	2	1 ± NA
	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum</i> ND	Nightshade		2	1 ± NA
	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	Stinging nettle	FACW	3	1 ± 0
	Vitaceae	<i>Vitis</i> ND	Grapes		2	1 ± NA
Asteraceae	ND	Asters		10	1 ± 0	

Table C7.3. Project-level mean above- and belowground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient concentration (% of dry mass) at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project for years 2023.

Biomass Type		2023		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	N (%)	P (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	827.99 ± 687.02 (n = 17)	0.86 ± 0.39 (n = 72)	0.21 ± 0.13 (n = 72)
<i>Belowground</i>	0–5 cm	120.28 ± 89.76 (n = 10)	0.7 ± 0.14 (n = 10)	0.16 ± 0.06 (n = 10)
	5–15 cm	84.83 ± 45.77 (n = 9)	0.56 ± 0.24 (n = 9)	0.13 ± 0.05 (n = 9)

St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Figure C8.1. Map of Sampling Locations at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project from 2021–2023.

Figure C8.2. Mean biomass (g/m²) for each species collected at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project summarized across 2022–2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table C8.1. Vegetation sampling effort at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Community composition survey quadrats are 1x1 meter whereas biomass sampling quadrats are 0.25x0.25 meters. Aboveground samples include live biomass as well as detritus; at this time, only live samples have been measured for nutrient concentration. Belowground biomass samples are taken in 2 depth intervals ranging from 0–15 cm in 2023.

Sample Type	2021	2022	2023
Site Visits	3	3	2
Community Composition Survey Quadrats	58	52	48
Biomass Sampling Quadrats	–	19	20
Aboveground Samples	–	69	60
Aboveground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	48	39
Belowground Samples	–	–	22
Belowground Samples Measured for Nutrient Concentration	–	–	18

Table C8.2. List of morphospecies encountered at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project during 2021–2023 sampling. The table shows family, species and common names, Wetland Indicator Status (WIS), the number of total quadrats (i.e., observations) where the morphospecies occurred, and the mean percent cover (\pm std. deviation) in the 1x1 meter quadrats where the morphospecies was present. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1. Asterisk indicates the species was seeded during construction at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project.

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria latifolia</i>	Broadleaf arrowhead	OBL	1	58 \pm 25
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		4	58 \pm 36
	Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii</i> ; <i>Setaria-Panicum</i> ND	Grasses		1	55 \pm 0
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria-Panicum</i> ND	Grasses		6	52 \pm 25
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus-Panicum</i> ND	Grasses		4	50 \pm 30
	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		4	49 \pm 37
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> ND	Flatsedge		1	48 \pm 46
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus-Panicum-Setaria</i> ND	Grasses		2	48 \pm 25
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		1	45 \pm NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> ND	Dandelion		1	40 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus-Setaria</i> ND	Grasses		1	40 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum</i> ND	Panic grass		9	38 \pm 26
	Asteraceae	<i>Conyza canadensis</i>	Canadian horseweed		2	33 \pm 40
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> ND	Water purslane		1	30 \pm 14
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		1	30 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus-Unspecified</i> ND	Grasses		1	30 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum-Unspecified</i> ND	Grasses		1	30 \pm NA
	Poaceae	<i>Avena-Elymus</i> ND	Grasses		1	25 \pm NA
Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii</i> ; <i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Grasses		1	22 \pm 18	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Poaceae	ND	Grasses		3	21 ± 9
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		1	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia</i> ND	Ragweed		1	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		1	20 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> ND	Docks and sorrels		3	20 ± 14
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena</i> ND	Vervain		1	20 ± 0
	Algae	ND	Algae		1	20 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa-Panicum</i> ND	Grasses		1	20 ± NA
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i> *	American water plantain	OBL	1	18 ± 4
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> ND	Amaranthus		4	18 ± 5
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	4	18 ± 5
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	1	18 ± 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia</i> ND	Coneflowers		1	15 ± 7
	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis</i> ND	Spikerushes		1	15 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> ND	Clovers		1	15 ± 7
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	3	14 ± 10
	Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron</i> ND	Fleabanes		1	12 ± 11
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus palmeri</i>	Carelessweed	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggarticks		2	4 ± 5
	Anacardiaceae	<i>Rhus aromatica</i>	Fragrant sumac	UPL	1	1 ± NA
Asteraceae	<i>Helenium</i> ND	Sneezeweed		1	1 ± NA	
Brassicaceae	<i>Lepidium</i> ND	Pepperweed		1	1 ± NA	
Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa</i> ND	Yellowcress		1	1 ± 0	
Lythraceae	<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	Purple Loosestrife	OBL	1	1 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2021	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer negundo</i> *	Boxelder Maple	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i> *	Red maple	FAC	1	1 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Glycine max</i>	Soybean		1	1 ± 0
2022	Algae	ND	Algae		3	56 ± 39
	Asteraceae	<i>Helenium</i> ND	Sneezeweed		1	50 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Annual Ragweed	FACU	1	48 ± 46
	Poaceae	<i>Hordeum</i> ND	Barley		3	41 ± 19
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria italica</i>	Foxtail millet	FACU	1	40 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena</i> ND	Vervain		1	40 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> ND	Water purslane		2	37 ± 23
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	Pale smartweed		2	37 ± 35
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		3	36 ± 11
	Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria</i> ND	Arrowhead		1	35 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Helenium autumnale</i> *	Common Sneezeweed	FACW	4	32 ± 23
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i> *	Soft Rush	OBL	7	32 ± 26
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus</i> ND	Wildrye		4	31 ± 29
	Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Field Horsetail	FAC	1	30 ± NA
	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia palustris</i>	Water purslane	OBL	2	30 ± 39
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum</i> ND	Panic grass		3	30 ± 24
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens cernua</i>	Nodding Bur Marigold	OBL	3	29 ± 38
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> *	Switchgrass	FAC	7	29 ± 23
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	Strawcolored flatsedge	FACW	3	28 ± 27
Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	4	28 ± 31	
Alismataceae	<i>Sagittaria latifolia</i>	Broadleaf arrowhead	OBL	4	27 ± 29	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	Yellow Foxtail		4	27 ± 26
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	8	27 ± 34
	Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus maximiliani</i>	Maximilian Sunflower	UPL	1	25 ± NA
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia coccinea</i>	Valley Redstem	OBL	1	25 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Setaria</i> ND	Foxtails		3	25 ± 30
		<i>Submerged Vegetation</i>			1	25 ± NA
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia robusta</i>	Grand redstems	OBL	4	24 ± 28
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> *	Barnyard Millet	FACW	9	24 ± 22
	Asteraceae	<i>Artemisia</i> ND	Sagebrush		1	22 ± 11
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	6	22 ± 14
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> ND	Carex		3	21 ± 20
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia trifida</i>	Great Ragweed	FAC	1	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	Canada Goldenrod	FACU	1	20 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphotrichum novae-angliae</i>	New England Aster	FACW	1	20 ± 7
	Campanulaceae	<i>Lobelia siphilitica</i> *	Great Blue Lobelia	OBL	1	20 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	4	20 ± 16
	Poaceae	<i>Leersia oryzoides</i>	Rice Cutgrass	OBL	1	20 ± NA
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> ND	Amaranths		2	18 ± 10
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	3	18 ± 19
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Yellow Nutsedge	FACW	2	17 ± 13
Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	Curly Dock	FAC	4	16 ± 8	
Poaceae	ND	Grasses		9	16 ± 13	
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus hybridus</i>	Slim Amaranth		1	15 ± 7	
Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	Eastern daisy fleabane	FACU	2	15 ± 13	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i> *	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	1	15 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	3	15 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lupulina</i> *	Hop Sedge	OBL	1	15 ± NA
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	3	15 ± 12
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggarticks		1	15 ± NA
	Bryophyta	<i>Bryophyta</i> ND	Mosses		1	15 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i>	Jerusalem artichoke	FACU	1	12 ± 4
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus</i> ND	Rushes		1	12 ± 11
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i> *	Path Rush	FAC	5	11 ± 8
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	1	10 ± 7
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia</i> ND	Ragweed		2	10 ± 5
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggarticks		7	10 ± 9
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex comosa</i>	Longhair sedge	OBL	2	10 ± 5
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex cristatella</i>	Crested Sedge	FACW	1	10 ± NA
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha</i> ND	Copperleaf		1	10 ± NA
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	5	10 ± 7
	Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii</i> *	Big Bluestem	FAC	1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	Hairy Crabgrass	FACU	1	10 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Poa</i> ND	Bluegrass		1	10 ± NA
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia</i> ND	Yellow Loosestrife		1	10 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	2	9 ± 7
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> ND	Flatsedge		3	9 ± 5	
Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i> *	American water plantain	OBL	5	8 ± 4	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle	FACU	1	8 ± 10
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> ND	Docks and sorrels		4	8 ± 4
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer</i> ND	Unk. Maple		1	8 ± 4
	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		4	8 ± 7
		Unknown			1	8 ± 4
	Araceae	<i>Lemna</i> ND	Duckweed		4	7 ± 3
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	3	6 ± 7
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia</i> ND	Redstem		3	6 ± 2
		<i>Seedlings</i>			13	6 ± 4
	Anacardiaceae	<i>Toxicodendron</i> ND	Poison Oak		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Erechtites hieracifolius</i>	American Burnweed		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		2	5 ± 5
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum</i> ND	Aster		1	5 ± NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa palustris</i>	Bog Yellowcress	OBL	2	5 ± 5
	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea</i> ND	Morning-glory		1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex bebbii</i>	Bebb's Sedge	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Shallow Sedge	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum palustre</i>	Marsh horsetail		1	5 ± NA
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha virginica</i>	Virginia threeseed mercury	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	Flower-of-an-hour		1	5 ± NA
Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		4	5 ± 8	
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	Narrowleaf Plantain	FACU	3	5 ± 4	
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	FAC	1	5 ± NA	
Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> ND	Barnyardgrass		1	5 ± NA	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2022	Poaceae	<i>Phleum pratense</i>	Timothy	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	Kentucky Bluegrass	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	Creeping Jenny	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Rosaceae	<i>Geum macrophyllum</i>	Largeleaf Avens		1	5 ± NA
	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Veronica peregrina</i>	Neckweed	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena urticifolia</i> *	White Vervain	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	ND	Grasses		3	2 ± 2
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus albus</i>	Prostrate Pigweed	FACU	1	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium clandestinum</i>	Deer-tongue Grass	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Salicaceae	<i>Populus</i> ND	Poplar/Cottonwood		1	1 ± NA
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i> *	Red maple	FAC	1	1 ± NA
Apiaceae	ND	Umbellifers		1	1 ± NA	
2023	Asteraceae	<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i> *	Black-Eyed Susan	FACU	1	80 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus effusus</i> *	Soft Rush	OBL	6	50 ± 32
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria hydropiperoides</i>	Swamp smartweed	OBL	1	40 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf	FACU	1	36 ± 49
	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i> *	Partridge pea	FACU	8	35 ± 34
	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> *	Barnyard Millet	FACW	5	34 ± 27
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	Spotted Ladysthumb	FACW	3	31 ± 21
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> ND	Amaranth		3	29 ± 22
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus hybridus</i>	Slim Amaranth		6	25 ± 20
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum pilosum</i>	Hairy White Oldfield Aster	FACU	1	25 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens cernua</i>	Nodding Bur Marigold	OBL	8	24 ± 28
Poaceae	<i>Elymus virginicus</i> *	Virginia Wild Rye	FACW	8	24 ± 21	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens</i> ND	Beggerticks		5	23 ± 32
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria punctata</i>	Dotted smartweed	OBL	1	22 ± 25
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Yellow Nutsedge	FACW	1	20 ± 14
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	Fox Sedge	FACW	5	18 ± 18
	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthelium clandestinum</i>	Deer-tongue Grass	FACW	2	17 ± 8
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Annual Ragweed	FACU	1	15 ± 14
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle	FACU	1	15 ± NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Rorippa palustris</i>	Bog Yellowcress	OBL	7	15 ± 11
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex hystericina</i>	Bottlebrush Sedge	OBL	1	15 ± 7
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria</i> ND	Smartweeds		4	15 ± 24
	Typhaceae	<i>Typha</i> ND	Cattails		1	15 ± NA
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias incarnata</i> *	Swamp Milkweed	OBL	5	13 ± 12
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	Canada Goldenrod	FACU	1	12 ± 4
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum</i> ND	Aster		2	12 ± 10
	Asteraceae	<i>Helenium autumnale</i> *	Common Sneezeweed	FACW	1	10 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Symphyotrichum novae-angliae</i>	New England Aster	FACW	1	10 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex scoparia</i> *	Blunt Broom Sedge	FACW	4	10 ± 5
	Cyperaceae	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i>	Woolgrass	OBL	1	10 ± NA
	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia coccinea</i>	Valley Redstem	OBL	1	10 ± NA
	Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Little hogweed	FACU	1	10 ± 13
Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	Eastern Cottonwood	FAC	3	10 ± 13	
Poaceae	ND	Grasses		20	10 ± 8	
Ranunculaceae	ND	Buttercups		1	10 ± NA	
Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	Eastern daisy fleabane	FACU	2	9 ± 7	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023		Unknown			4	9 ± 15
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago</i> ND	Goldenrods		4	8 ± 10
		<i>Seedlings</i>			6	8 ± 5
	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	FACU	3	7 ± 5
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus tenuis</i> *	Path Rush	FAC	3	7 ± 9
	Verbenaceae	<i>Verbena hastata</i> *	Blue vervain	FACW	7	7 ± 9
	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	FAC	1	6 ± 6
	Amaranthaceae	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Lambsquarters	FACU	1	5 ± NA
	Anacardiaceae	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	Eastern Poison Ivy	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia trifida</i>	Great Ragweed	FAC	2	5 ± 5
	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	Devil's Beggarticks	FACW	3	5 ± 6
	Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus divaricatus</i>	Woodland sunflower		1	5 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i> *	False Sunflower	FACU	1	5 ± 0
	Asteraceae	<i>Solidago altissima</i>	Canada Goldenrod		1	5 ± NA
	Linderniaceae	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	Yellowseed false pimpernel	OBL	1	5 ± NA
	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis</i> ND	Wood sorrels		1	5 ± 0
	Poaceae	<i>Coleataenia rigidula</i>	Redtop panicgrass		1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostis pectinacea</i>	Tufted Lovegrass	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> *	Switchgrass	FAC	1	5 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	Kentucky Bluegrass	FAC	1	5 ± 0
	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia ciliata</i>	Fringed loosetrife	FACW	1	5 ± NA
	Rosaceae	<i>Potentilla norvegica</i>	Norwegian cinquefoil	FAC	1	5 ± NA
Salicaceae	<i>Salix eriocephala</i>	Missouri River Willow		1	5 ± NA	
Penthoraceae	<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	Ditch Stonecrop	OBL	4	4 ± 4	

	Family	Species	Common Name	WIS	Obs.	Mean % Cover
2023	Cyperaceae	ND	Sedges		2	4 ± 2
	Poaceae	<i>Andropogon gerardii</i> *	Big Bluestem	FAC	1	3 ± 3
	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	Curly Dock	FAC	6	3 ± 3
	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Rough cocklebur	FAC	2	2 ± 2
	Asteraceae	ND	Asters		3	2 ± 2
	Alismataceae	<i>Alisma subcordatum</i> *	American water plantain	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias tuberosa</i> *	Butterfly Weed		1	1 ± NA
	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium</i> ND	Thistle		1	1 ± NA
	Brassicaceae	<i>Lepidium campestre</i>	Field Pepperweed		1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Shallow Sedge	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	Strawcolored flatsedge	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus canadensis</i>	Canadian rush	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon</i> ND	Indian Mallow		1	1 ± NA
	Poaceae	<i>Calamagrostis canadensis</i>	Bluejoint	OBL	1	1 ± NA
	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria pensylvanica</i>	Pennsylvania Smartweed	FACW	1	1 ± NA
	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer rubrum</i> *	Red maple	FAC	2	1 ± 0

Table C8.3. Project-level mean above- and belowground biomass (g/m²) and mean nutrient concentration (% of dry mass) at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project for years 2022–2023. Dashes indicate data were not collected.

Biomass Type		2022			2023		
		Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)	Biomass (g/m ²)	P (%)	N (%)
<i>Aboveground</i>	Dry Live Mass	1025.15 ± 764.96 (n = 19)	0.28 ± 0.15 (n = 95)	0.88 ± 0.39 (n = 95)	1710.64 ± 843.42 (n = 19)	0.32 ± 0.14 (n = 103)	1.08 ± 0.48 (n = 103)
	Detritus	251.98 ± 268.3 (n = 19)	–	–	224.44 ± 218.49 (n = 18)	–	–
<i>Belowground</i>	0–5 cm	–	–	–	65.46 ± 73.54 (n = 10)	0.1 ± 0.03 (n = 10)	0.73 ± 0.28 (n = 10)
	5–15 cm	–	–	–	58.48 ± 72.03 (n = 10)	0.12 ± 0.06 (n = 10)	0.84 ± 0.22 (n = 10)

